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Enzymatic Reactions

And Bifurcation Theory

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1 Chemical kinetics

1.1 Rate of reaction

DEF. 1. Let's consider the generic reaction

We say that R represents the *reactants* while P indicates the products. Each arrow indicates an *elementary reaction* and I_i is an *intermediate*.

For instance, consider the reaction $2\text{ICl} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{HCl} + \text{I}_2$. In this case, we have two elementary reactions. In fact, it has been experimentally determined that the path between reactants and products is the following one:

which means that the two elementary reactions are

DEF. 2. The *molecularity* of an elementary reaction is the number of molecules of the reactants. For instance, both the reactions in Eq. 3 have a molecularity of two. Experimentally, elementary reactions with a molecularity above 3 are unlikely to happen.

DEF. 3. The *rate* of a reaction is the increase in the concentration of products or reagents for unit of time (as $[\text{P}]/\Delta t$) and it is expressed in molarity ($\text{M} = \text{number of moles/L}$) per second (M/s). The *instant rate* is the derivative of $[\text{P}]$ with respect to time. The instant rate is usually expressed as v and in what follows we will call it simply rate. If we consider the generic reaction

then we have

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad v = -\frac{1}{a} \frac{d[\text{A}]}{dt} = -\frac{1}{b} \frac{d[\text{B}]}{dt} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{d[\text{C}]}{dt} = \frac{1}{d} \frac{d[\text{D}]}{dt}$$

DEF. 4. Consider a multi-step reaction. If the rate of the step n is much slower than the ones of the other steps, we say that the n -th step is the *rate-determining step* of the reaction.

1.2 Order of a reaction, first-order reactions

The value of v can be gathered by experimental data. For the reaction

of decomposition of N_2O_5 in a solution of CCl_4 at a temperature of 45°C we have the experimental data:

time (s)	0	184	319	526	867	1198	1877	2315	3144
[N ₂ O ₅] (M)	2.33	2.08	1.91	1.67	1.36	1.11	0.72	0.55	0.34

which are plotted in Figure 1 (blue line). The instant rate is given by the derivative of that plot, but what can be its relationship between v and $[N_2O_5]$? Let's assume that it is a linear one and let's see if it fits the data:

$$-\frac{d[N_2O_5]}{dt} = k[N_2O_5] \Rightarrow -\frac{1}{[N_2O_5]} \frac{d[N_2O_5]}{dt} = -k \int \frac{1}{[N_2O_5]} \frac{d[N_2O_5]}{dt} dt = -k \int dt$$

$$\Rightarrow -\ln[N_2O_5] = kt + C$$

In $t = 0$ we have $[N_2O_5]_0 = 2.33$ M and this gives $C = -\ln 2.33$. Thus, we have found the law

Eq. 7 $\ln \frac{[N_2O_5]}{[N_2O_5]_0} = -kt \Leftrightarrow [N_2O_5] = [N_2O_5]_0 e^{-kt}$

Figure 1. Concentration of N₂O₅ in function of time for the decomposition of N₂O₅ in a solution of CCl₄ at a temperature of 45°C.

Let's now find k using the experimental in Figure 1 we have $k = -\frac{\ln \frac{[N_2O_5]}{[N_2O_5]_0}}{t} = -\frac{\ln \frac{[N_2O_5]}{2.33M}}{t}$ wich gives the following values:

time (s)	184	319	526	867	1198	1877	2315	3144
k (1/s)	0.0006168	0.000623	0.000633	0.000621	0.000619	0.000626	0.000624	0.000612

And the mean value is $k = 0.000622 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Now, if we substitute this value in Eq. 7 we get the expression

Eq. 8 $[N_2O_5] = 2.33e^{-\frac{6.22 \cdot 10^{-4}}{s}t} \frac{\text{moles}}{\text{liter}}$

which gives the concentrations almost identical with respect to those experimentally determined. So we can conclude that in this case $\frac{d[N_2O_5]}{dt}$ has, in fact, a linear dependence with $[N_2O_5]$. This is not true in general, as we'll see.

time (s)	0	184	319	526	867	1198	1877	2315	3144
$[N_2O_5]$ (M)	2.33	2.08	1.91	1.68	1.36	1.11	0.73	0.55	0.33

DEF. 5. In many cases, the rate of the reaction in Eq. 4 can be written

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad v = k[A]^m[B]^n$$

In those cases, we say that m is the *order* with respect to A , n is the order with respect to B , and $m + n$ is the order of the reaction. Eq. 9 is the *rate equation* of the reaction. So, Eq. 7 is a first-order reaction. The assumption that the rate is proportional to the concentrations of the reacting chemical species goes under the name of *mass action kinetics* (MAK).

The orders with respect to reagents are in general different from their stoichiometric coefficients (i.e. $a \neq m$, $b \neq n$, in general) and they must be experimentally determined. For instance, we have deduced from experimental data that the order of N_2O_5 in Eq. 6 is one. *Only for elementary reactions, the orders are equal to the corresponding stoichiometric coefficients.*

The order with respect to each reagent has to be determined experimentally and it can be done by fixing the initial concentration of all the other reagents and measuring the variation of v for any variation of the reagent whose order is unknown. So, if v is two times greater when we double the initial concentration of $[A]$ while keeping constant the initial concentration of $[B]$, then the order with respect to A is one; if v is four times greater, then this order with respect to A is 2.

DEF. 6. We call *rate constant* the parameter k in Eq. 9.

As the reader can easily realize, the unit in which k is expressed varies according to the order of the reaction. For a first-order reaction, we have that k is expressed in s^{-1} ; for a second-order reaction, k is expressed in $s^{-1}M^{-1}$. In general, if r is the order of a reaction, then k is expressed in $s^{-1}M^{(1-r)}$.

DEF. 7. We call *half-time* or *half-life* of a reactant, the time it requires to reach half of the initial concentration. It is usually indicated $t_{1/2}$.

PROP. 1 (*half-life*). The half-time of the reactant of a first-order reaction is a constant, so it doesn't vary in function of the initial concentration.

Proof. This can be demonstrated considering that

$$k = -\frac{\ln \frac{[R]}{[R]_0}}{t} \Rightarrow k = -\frac{\ln \frac{[R]_0}{2[R]_0}}{t_{\frac{1}{2}}} = -\frac{\ln \frac{1}{2}}{t_{\frac{1}{2}}} \Rightarrow t_{\frac{1}{2}} = -\frac{1}{k} \ln \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad t_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{0.69}{k}$$

The higher the half-time, the lower is k ■

1.2.1 Nuclear decay

Unstable atomic nuclei lose energy by emitting radiation and transforming itself into a stable chemical element (this process is called *nuclear decay*, *radioactive decay*, or *radioactivity*). It has been experimentally determined that the number of atoms that decay is directly proportional to that number itself. Thus, nuclear decay follows a first-order equation:

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \frac{dy(t)}{dt} = -ky(t) \Leftrightarrow y(t) = y_0 e^{-kt}$$

where y_0 is the number of nuclei at $t = 0$. The *half-life* of the unstable nucleus is:

$$y(t_{1/2}) = y_0 e^{-kt_{1/2}} = \frac{y_0}{2} \Rightarrow e^{-kt_{1/2}} = \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow t_{1/2} = -\frac{\ln 0.5}{k} = \frac{0.69}{k}$$

For instance, the half-life of C^{14} is 5715 years and it decays into nitrogen-14, through the emission of a beta particle (an electron or a positron), so we have

$$\frac{0.69}{k_{C^{14}}} = 5715 \text{ years} \Rightarrow k_{C^{14}} = 1.2 \frac{10^{-4}}{\text{year}}$$

Let's assume that we find a presumably ancient piece of wood that emits 5 beta particles for minute, while a comparable piece of a tree that has been just cut emits 30 beta particles for minute. We want to know how many years ago the tree from which the ancient piece of wood comes from, died. If $y(t)$ is the number of atoms of C^{14} that are present at time t in the modern piece of wood, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{60s} y_0 e^{-k_{C^{14}}t} dt &= -\frac{y_0}{k_{C^{14}}} \int_0^{60s} e^{-k_{C^{14}}t} d(-k_{C^{14}}t) = \left(-\frac{y_0}{k_{C^{14}}} e^{-k_{C^{14}}t} \right)_0^{60s} = \\ &= \frac{y_0}{k_{C^{14}}} (1 - e^{-k_{C^{14}}60s}) = y_0 0.19 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot \text{year} \end{aligned}$$

where we have considered that $1 \text{ year} = 60 \cdot 60 \cdot 24 \cdot 365 \text{ seconds} \Rightarrow 60 \text{ seconds} \sim 1.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ years}$. But this number must be equal to 30 for the modern piece of wood. So, we have

$$y_0 0.19 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot \text{year} = 30 \cdot \text{minute} \Rightarrow y_0 \sim 157.9 \cdot 10^5 \frac{\text{minute}}{\text{year}} = 30.04$$

This is the number of atoms of C^{14} that the ancient wood had when the tree died. While the number that it has now can be calculated in the same way:

$$y_0 0.19 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot \text{year} = 5 \cdot \text{minute} \Rightarrow y_0 \sim 5.0$$

Then we can write the time required for the piece of wood to go from a content of 30.0 atoms of C^{14} to a content of 5.0, which is an estimation of how many years ago the tree died:

$$5 = 30.04 e^{-k_{C^{14}}t} \Rightarrow e^{-k_{C^{14}}t} = \frac{5}{30.04} \Rightarrow t = -\frac{\ln \frac{5}{30.04}}{k_{C^{14}}} = 14931 \text{ years}$$

1.3 Second-order reactions

Let's consider now an elementary reaction of the second order, with only one reactant, i.e. $2A \rightarrow B$. In this case, we have

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = k[A]^2 \Rightarrow \frac{d[A]}{[A]^2} = k \Rightarrow \int \frac{d[A]}{[A]^2} = \int k dt \Rightarrow \frac{1}{[A]} = kt + C$$

If we indicate the concentration for $t = 0$ as $[A]_0$, then we can find C and we have the law

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad \frac{1}{[A]} = kt + \frac{1}{[A]_0} \Leftrightarrow [A] = \frac{[A]_0}{k[A]_0 t + 1}$$

For the *half-life* for A is in this case we have $\frac{2}{[A]_0} = kt_{1/2} + \frac{1}{[A]_0} \Rightarrow 1 = k[A]_0 t_{1/2}$, hence, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad t_{1/2} = \frac{1}{k[A]_0}$$

Figure 2. Comparison between first and second-order chemical reactions with the same half-life.

So, for a second-order reaction with one reactant only, the half-life depends on the initial concentration. Consider now the two following rate laws:

$$\frac{d[R]}{dt} = k_1[R], \quad \frac{d[R]}{dt} = k_2[R]^2$$

Let's assume that $[R]_0$ is the same in both cases and we will assume that the half-time is the same, too. Thus, we have $k_1 = 0.69[R]_0 k_2$ and the two rate laws can be written

$$[R] = [R]_0 e^{-0.69[R]_0 k_2 t}, \quad [R] = \frac{[R]_0}{k_2 [R]_0 t + 1}$$

If we assume now $[R]_0 = 1M$ and $t_{1/2} = 200s$ we have $k_2 = 0.005Ms$ and the two laws are

$$[R] = 1M e^{-\frac{0.00345}{s} t}, \quad [R] = \frac{1M}{\frac{0.005}{s} t + 1}$$

and their plots are in Figure 2. As you can see, before the half-time the second-order reaction is faster, then the first-order curve is the more rapidly decreasing of the two.

1.4 Steady-state for elementary reactions

Let's consider again the reaction in Eq. 4 and let's assume now that it is reversible. In this case, we have two rate constants, one for the reaction from left to right, and one for the opposite direction. In these cases, we use the following notation:

If the reaction reaches equilibrium, it means that the rate of the transformation from left to right is the same rate of the other reaction. Thus, we have

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad k_1 [A]_{eq}^{m_1} [B]_{eq}^{n_1} = k_2 [C]_{eq}^{m_2} [D]_{eq}^{n_2} \Leftrightarrow \frac{[A]_{eq}^{m_1} [B]_{eq}^{n_1}}{[C]_{eq}^{m_2} [D]_{eq}^{n_2}} = \frac{k_1}{k_2}$$

where *eq* stands for equilibrium because these concentrations are meant to be the ones reached during the steady-state. Now you might remember from chemical thermodynamics, that

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \Delta G = \Delta G^0 + RT \ln \left(\frac{[C]^c [D]^d}{[A]^a [B]^b} \left(\frac{1}{C_0} \right)^{[(c+d)-(a+b)]} \right)$$

where $\Delta G = G_{products} - G_{reagents}$ is the variation of Gibbs's energy when the reaction goes from left to right, ΔG^0 is the same variation, but in standard conditions ($T_0 = 298.15K$, $P_0 = 1\text{Atm}$ and $R = 8.3145 \text{ J} \cdot K^{-1} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ is the so-called *gas constant*; moreover, C_0 is the standard concentration of one mole per litre (1M). When the steady-state is reached, then $\Delta G = 0$, and we have

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad K_{eq} \triangleq \frac{[C]^c [D]^d}{[A]^a [B]^b} \left(\frac{1}{C_0} \right)^{[(c+d)-(a+b)]} = e^{-\frac{\Delta G^0}{RT_0}}$$

where K_{eq} is called *equilibrium constant of concentration*. Now, if the reaction is an elementary one, then $a = m_1$, $b = n_1$, $c = m_2$, $d = n_2$ and from Eq. 15 and Eq. 17 we get

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad \frac{k_1}{k_2} \left(\frac{1}{C_0} \right)^{[(c+d)-(a+b)]} = K_{eq} = e^{-\frac{\Delta G^0}{RT_0}}$$

This formula is of limited practical application because as said, it is true only for elementary reactions.

1.5 Transition state

The commonly accepted model for many chemical reactions is that the reactants form an *activated complex*, which is a state of high energy of the reactants, assumed to be in equilibrium with the reactants themselves; this activated complex – also known as *transition state* – then goes through a second reaction which leads to the products. For example, let's consider the reaction

Then, according to this model, it can be written in the following two steps:

where $(AB)^*$ is the transition state (or activated complex), K_{eq} is the equilibrium constant of the first step and k_2 is the rate constant of the second reaction (which is an elementary reaction). Then, if we consider the reaction in Eq. 19 and the second one in Eq. 20, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{d[C]}{dt} = k_2[(AB)^*] \\ \frac{d[C]}{dt} = k[A][B] \end{cases}$$

If we consider the first step in Eq. 20 we can also write

$$K_{eq} = \frac{[(AB)^*]}{[A][B]} = e^{-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}}$$

and substituting this equation in the first one of Eq. 21 we get the rate law¹:

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad \frac{d[C]}{dt} = k_2 e^{-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}} [A][B]$$

Figure 3. The path followed by the free energy of the reaction. ΔG^* is the free energy required for the formation of the active complex from the reactants (it is positive), while ΔG is the variation of free energy during the reaction, and it is assumed to be negative (spontaneous reaction).

¹ In this case the temperature that appears in the expression of the equilibrium constant is the actual temperature of the reaction, not T_0 . But this also means that the ΔG that appears in that same expression is the variation in Gibbs's energy at that temperature.

DEF. 8. Now, consider that ΔG^* is – in this case – the Gibbs’s energy required for the formation of the active complex (*free energy of activation*) from the reactants.

So, the higher this energy is, the slower the rate of the reaction in Eq. 19 is. The plot of Gibbs’s energy of a spontaneous reaction is indicated in Figure 3.

1.6 Rate constant and temperature

So, we have found that the rate constant of the reaction in Eq. 19, is given by the so-called *Arrhenius’s equation*:

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad k = k_2 e^{-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}}$$

It is possible to further demonstrate that $k_2 = k_B T/h$, where $k_B = 1.3807 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ J} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ is the *Boltzmann constant*, and $h = 6.6261 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}$ is *Plank’s constant*. So, the relationship between rate constant and temperature is given by the following expression:

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad k = \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}}$$

Temperature appears two times in this expression and in both cases there is an inverse relationship between temperature and k . And the higher the temperature, the faster the reaction. The relationship with ΔG^* has been already discussed. The plot of k in function of T and ΔG^* is in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4. The plot of the rate constant in Eq. 24.

CODE 1. To plot this image for different ranges of the variables, you can use the following MATLAB code.

```
% file name = rate_constant
% date of creation = 5/08/2019
clear all
```

```

% constants
K_B = 1.380662*( 10^(-23) ) %Boltzmann
R = 8.31441 %Gas
h_P = 6.626176*( 10^(-34) ) %Plank
% we register the array of the temperature (Kelvin)
delta_T = 1.;
% we register the array
T(1) = 260.;
for i = 2:30
    T(i) = T(i-1) + delta_T;
end
% we define the array of free energy (kJ)
delta_G = 0.2;
G(1) = 8.;
for i = 2:30
    G(i) = G(i-1) + delta_G;
end
% we register the array of the rate constant
for i=1:30
    for j=1:30
        R_C(i,j) = (K_B/h_P)*T(i)*e^( -1*G(j)*1000/(R*T(i)) );
    endfor
endfor
% we plot the rate constant
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(G(1:30), T(1:30), R_C(1:30,1:30));
grid on
xlabel('free energy (k Joule/mole)');
ylabel('temperature (Kelvin)');
zlabel('rate constant');

```

2 Enzyme kinetics

2.1 Catalysis and enzymes

DEF. 9. A *catalyst* is any substance that increases the rate of a reaction without being modified by the reaction itself and without altering its equilibrium constant.

The mechanism by which a catalyst increases the rate of a reaction is by lowering the free energy of activation. Let's assume that a catalyst reduces the free energy of activation of a second-order reaction by a value $\Delta G_c^* > 0$, then Eq. 24 says that the new rate constant (k_c) is given by

$$\text{Eq. 25} \quad k_c = \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{-\frac{\Delta G^* - \Delta G_c^*}{RT}} = k e^{\frac{\Delta G_c^*}{RT}} > k$$

What is the value of ΔG_c^* needed for a n -fold increase in the rate constant? We have

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad e^{\frac{\Delta G_c^*}{RT}} = n \Leftrightarrow \Delta G_c^* = RT \ln n$$

and the plot of in function of T and n is reported in *Figure 5*: for a ten-fold increase the reduction of the free energy of activation provided by catalysis has to be 5.727 kJ/mole, about one hundredth the energy of the chemical bond in H_2 .

Figure 5. Reduction of free energy of activation required for increases in reaction rate from 0 to 30, at different temperatures.

Enzymes are proteins that catalyze specific reactions in cells. Each reaction (or group of similar reactions) has its own enzyme. Some enzymes act on a single substrate, others act on two or more substrates. Moreover, when more than one substrate is present, there might be an order in which they have to bind the enzyme, for the reaction to happen. Enzymatic reactions have their own chemical kinetics.

2.2 The Michaelis-Menten equation for irreversible reactions

We consider the following kinetic mechanism for an enzyme reaction:

where E denotes the enzyme, S is the substrate, P denotes the product, and ES is the *enzyme-substrate complex*. If we consider both the reactions we have

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{d[S]}{dt} = -k_1[E][S] + k_{-1}[ES] \\ \frac{d[E]}{dt} = -k_1[E][S] + k_{-1}[ES] + k_2[ES] \\ \frac{d[ES]}{dt} = k_1[E][S] - k_{-1}[ES] - k_2[ES] \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_2[ES] \end{cases}$$

It has been experimentally determined that, after some milliseconds, the concentration of $[ES]$ remains stable, until exhaustion of the substrate. Hence, the *steady-state assumption*:

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad \frac{d[ES]}{dt} = 0$$

Since what can be measured is, in fact, the total concentration of the enzyme (indicated $[E]_T$), rather than the concentrations of the enzyme-free from the substrate and of the enzyme-substrate bond, it is useful to remember that

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad [E]_T = [ES] + [E] \Leftrightarrow [E] = [E]_T - [ES]$$

If we substitute Eq. 29 and Eq. 30 in the second expression in Eq. 28 we get

$$\begin{aligned} k_1([E]_T - [ES])[S] &= k_{-1}[ES] + k_2[ES] \\ \Leftrightarrow k_1[E]_T[S] - k_1[ES][S] &= k_{-1}[ES] + k_2[ES] \\ \Leftrightarrow k_1[E]_T[S] &= (k_{-1} + k_2 + k_1[S])[ES] \end{aligned}$$

Dividing both sides by k_1 we have

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E]_T[S]}{\frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1} + [S]}$$

DEF. 10. The *Michaelis constant* is defined as

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad K_M = \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1}$$

As an example, its value for the degradation of acetylcholine by acetylcholinesterase is $9.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{M}$, its value for the degradation of urea by urease is $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{M}$. For each reaction, K_M is also a function of temperature and pH. If we consider now the second half of the reaction in Eq. 27 we have

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_2[ES]$$

Then, If we substitute Eq. 31 in this rate equation, we have

$$\text{Eq. 34} \quad \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_2 \frac{[E]_T[S]}{k_{-1} + k_2 + [S]}$$

DEF. 11. The rate indicated in this equation is the one that is achieved when $[ES]$ reaches its steady state (usually after some milliseconds) and – by convention – before up to 10% of the substrate has been consumed. This rate is called *initial velocity* and it is indicated v_0 .

Figure 6. The horizontal axis represents the value n in $[S] = nK_M$. The vertical axis is v_0/v_M .

DEF. 12. The *maximal velocity* v_M (highest rate) will be reached when there is enough substrate to bind all the available enzymes (*saturation*). In this case $[ES] = [E]_T$ and Eq. 33 gives

$$\text{Eq. 35} \quad v_M = k_2[E]_T$$

DEF. 13. All that said, Eq. 34 can be written

$$\text{Eq. 36} \quad v_0 = \frac{v_M[S]}{K_M + [S]}$$

which is called *Michaelis-Menten equation*. A way to plot this equation in order to have an idea of its behaviour is expressing $[S]$ as n times K_M and then plotting $\frac{v_0}{v_M} = \frac{n}{1+n}$ (Figure 6).

From the figure, we see how K_M is the concentration of the substrate in which the initial velocity is half-maximal. It can also be noted that for $[S] \ll K_M$ the reaction behaves as the first-order reaction, while for $[S] \gg K_M$ it behaves like a zero-order reaction.

DEF. 14. The Michael-Menten equation can be written also

$$\text{Eq. 37} \quad \frac{1}{v_0} = \frac{K_M}{v_M} \frac{1}{[S]} + \frac{1}{v_M}$$

which is the equation of a line in $\frac{1}{v_0}$ and $\frac{1}{[S]}$ which meets the $\frac{1}{v_0}$ axis in $\frac{1}{v_M}$ (see Figure 7). This plot of the Michaelis-Menten equation is called *Lineweaver-Burk plot* and it is useful for the determination of v_M from measures of $[S]$ and of v_0 : in fact, you need just two points $\left(\frac{1}{v_0}, \frac{1}{[S]}\right)$ to find the line and, thus, the point in which it encounters the vertical axis, which gives the value of v_M . Note that the same can't be done with the standard plot of the Michaelis-Menten relationship.

Figure 7. The Lineweaver-Burk plot of the Michaelis-Menten equation.

DEF. 15. Another parameter of interest is the *catalytic constant* of an enzyme:

$$\text{Eq. 38} \quad k_{cat} = \frac{v_M}{[E]_T}$$

So, it is the same as k_2 . It is the maximum rate of the reaction for unity of concentration of the enzyme: it is a measure of how efficient the enzyme is. As an example, its value for the degradation of acetylcholine by acetylcholinesterase is $1.4 \cdot 10^4 s^{-1}$, its value for the degradation of fumarate by fumarase is $8.0 \cdot 10^2 M$. Usually, the kinetic parameters available for an enzymatic reaction of the type in Eq. 27 are k_{cat} and K_M . So it is convenient to write the Michaelis-Menten equation as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 39} \quad v_0 = k_{cat} \frac{[S][E]_T}{K_M + [S]}$$

2.2.1 Tryptophan metabolism (IDO-2)

Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase-2 (IDO-2) is one of the three enzymes that catalyze the incorporation of molecular oxygen into L-tryptophan in the first step of the kynurenine pathway. The reaction, in this case, can be written

where ES is the enzyme-substrate complex, which in this case include L-tryptophan, IDO-2 and O_2 . The reader might be disappointed because of the presence of a second substrate so that the reaction doesn't fit Eq. 27. Yet, if we assume that the concentration of O_2 is constant (as is the case in many experimental settings), then it is easy to recognize that the system in Eq. 28 remains unchanged and the concentration of O_2 is basically included in k_1 . In a set of experiments carried in a solution of potassium phosphate (100 μM) at a PH of 7.5 in a buffer at a concentration of 20 mM ascorbate, with a concentration of IDO-2 that varied between 0.4 μM and 2.0 μM , the following kinetic parameters were found: $k_{cat} = 0.103 \text{ s}^{-1}$ $K_M = 6809.0 \mu\text{M}$. In this case, Eq. 39 gives the diagram in Figure 8 which has been plotted by the following code in MATLAB.

Figure 8. Plot of the Michaelis-Menten equation for IDO-2, at different concentrations of the enzyme.

CODE 2. This code plots the Michaelis-Menten curve for the reaction in Eq. 40 and can be used for any irreversible enzymatic reaction (the type in Eq. 27). It has been used to plot both Figure 8 and Figure 9.

```
% file name = MM_irreversible_IDO2
% date of creation = 08/08/2019
clear all

k_cat = 0.103                                % catalitic constant (1/s)
K_M = 6809                                    % Michaelis constant (micro M)

% the array for total enzyme concentration
min_E_T = 0.4                                % lower enzyme concentration (micro M)
max_E_T = 2.0                                % maximal aray concentration (micro M)
```

```

delta_E_T = (max_E_T - min_E_T)/10;
E_T (1) = min_E_T
for i=2:1:11
    E_T (i) = E_T (i-1) + delta_E_T;
endfor

% the array for the substrate
S_M = 30000; % maximal substrate concentration (micro M)
delta_S = S_M/100; % increase in substrate concentration
S(1) = 0.01;
for j=2:1:101
    S(j) = S(j-1) + delta_S;
endfor

% the rate
for i=1:1:11
    for j=1:1:101
        v(i,j) = k_cat*S(j)*E_T(i)/(K_M + S(j)); % micro M/s
    endfor
endfor

% plot
figure (1)
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(S(1:101), E_T(1:11), v(1:11,1:101));
grid on
ylabel('IDO-2 ( $\mu$ M)');
xlabel('L-tryptophan ( $\mu$ M)');
zlabel('rate (1/s)');
figure (2)
n = 5;
v_2 (1:101) = v(n,1:101);
semilogx(S(1:101),v_2(1:101),'-k','linewidth', 2)
grid on
conc = num2str(E_T(n));
xlabel('L-tryptophan ( $\mu$ M)');
ylabel('rate (1/s)');
str = strjoin ('IDO2 at a concentration of ' conc ' $\mu$ M');
title (str)
figure (3)
plot(S(1:101),v_2(1:101),'-k','linewidth', 2)
grid on
conc = num2str(E_T(n));
xlabel('L-tryptophan ( $\mu$ M)');
ylabel('rate (1/s)');
str = strjoin ('IDO2 at a concentration of ' conc ' $\mu$ M');
title (str)

```

2.2.2 Tryptophan metabolism (TDO-2)

Tryptophane 2,3-dioxygenase-2 (TDO-2) is one of the three enzymes that catalyze the incorporation of molecular oxygen into L-tryptophan in the first step of the kynurenine pathway. The reaction, in this case, can be written

where ES is the enzyme-substrate complex, which in this case include L-tryptophan, TDO-2 and O_2 . In a set of experiments carried in a solution of potassium phosphate ($100 \mu\text{M}$) at a PH of 7.0 in a buffer at a concentration of 100 mM sodium ascorbate, with a concentration of TDO-2 of $0.5 \mu\text{M}$, the following kinetic parameters were found: $k_{cat} = 2.1 \text{ s}^{-1}$ $K_M = 0.19 \text{ mM} = 190\mu\text{M}$. The plots for the Michaelis-Menten equation of TDO-2 are in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Plot of the Michaelis-Menten equation for TDO-2, at different concentrations of the enzyme.

2.3 The Michaelis-Menten equation for reversible reactions

What happens when the enzymatic reaction can proceed in both directions? We can express such a reaction as follows:

If we consider both the reactions we have

$$\text{Eq. 43} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{d[S]}{dt} = -k_1[E][S] + k_{-1}[ES] \\ \frac{d[E]}{dt} = -k_1[E][S] + k_{-1}[ES] + k_2[ES] - k_{-2}[E][P] \\ \frac{d[ES]}{dt} = k_1[E][S] - k_{-1}[ES] - k_2[ES] + k_{-2}[E][P] \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_2[ES] - k_{-2}[E][P] \end{cases}$$

The hypothesis of steady-state for $[ES]$ gives

$$\text{Eq. 44} \quad (k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P])[E] = (k_{-1} + k_2)[ES]$$

If we consider also the conservation of the enzyme (Eq. 30), we get

$$(k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P])([E]_T - [ES]) = (k_{-1} + k_2)[ES]$$

$$\text{Eq. 45} \quad [E]_T = \left(\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1 \right) [ES]$$

In this case, we express the rate of the reaction considering the substrate instead of the product:

$$v = -\frac{d[S]}{dt} = k_1[E][S] - k_{-1}[ES] = k_1([E]_T - [ES])[S] - k_{-1}[ES]$$

$$\text{Eq. 46} \quad \frac{v - k_1[E]_T[S]}{k_1[S] + k_{-1}} = -[ES]$$

Combining Eq. 45 and Eq. 46 we get

$$\begin{aligned} [E]_T &= -\left(\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1 \right) \frac{v - k_1[E]_T[S]}{k_1[S] + k_{-1}} \\ \Leftrightarrow [E]_T(k_1[S] + k_{-1}) &= \left(\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1 \right) k_1[E]_T[S] - \left(\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1 \right) v \\ \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} k_1[S] - k_{-1} \right) [E]_T &= \left(\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1 \right) v \end{aligned}$$

Resolving with respect to v we have

$$v = \frac{\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} k_1[S] - k_{-1}}{\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1} [E]_T$$

Let's now divide both the numerator and the denominator of the second term by $k_{-1} + k_2$:

$$v = \frac{\frac{1}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} k_1[S] - \frac{k_{-1}}{k_{-1} + k_2}}{\frac{1}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + \frac{1}{k_{-1} + k_2}} [E]_T$$

We now multiply both the numerator and the denominator of the second term by $k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]$:

$$v = \frac{k_1[S] - \frac{k_{-1}}{k_{-1} + k_2} (k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P])}{1 + \frac{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]}{k_{-1} + k_2}} [E]_T = \frac{\left(k_1 - \frac{k_{-1}}{k_{-1} + k_2} k_1 \right) [S] - k_{-1} \frac{k_{-2}}{k_{-1} + k_2} [P]}{1 + \frac{k_1}{k_{-1} + k_2} [S] + \frac{k_{-2}}{k_{-1} + k_2} [P]} [E]_T$$

With a last effort inside the brackets, we have

$$\text{Eq. 47} \quad v = \frac{k_2 \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}+k_2} [S] - k_{-1} \frac{k_{-2}}{k_{-1}+k_2} [P]}{1 + \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}+k_2} [S] + \frac{k_{-2}}{k_{-1}+k_2} [P]} [E]_T$$

This equation is similar to the one in Eq. 34; actually, this one gives Eq. 34 for $k_{-2} = 0$. So, this is a more general expression of the Michaelis-Menten equation.

DEF. 16. In this case, we define two *Michaelis constants*:

$$\text{Eq. 48} \quad K_M^S = \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1}, \quad K_M^P = \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_{-2}}$$

DEF. 17. We have now two *maximal velocities*:

$$\text{Eq. 49} \quad v_M^f = k_2 [E]_T, \quad v_M^r = k_{-1} [E]_T$$

All that said, Eq. 47 can be written

$$\text{Eq. 50} \quad v = \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S] - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]}{1 + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}}$$

To have an idea of how this function behaves, let's put $[S] = nK_M^S$ and $[P] = mK_M^S$, moreover, we assume that $v_M^f = 2v_M^r$, so that the equation can be written

$$\text{Eq. 51} \quad \frac{v}{v_M^f} = \frac{n-2}{1+n+m} \quad \text{when} \quad [S] = nK_M^S, [P] = mK_M^S, v_M^f = 2v_M^r$$

When the reaction in Eq. 42 reaches equilibrium $v = 0$ (), Eq. 50 gives $\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S]_{eq} = \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]_{eq}$ and at the same time Eq. 17 is true, so we find

$$\text{Eq. 52} \quad K_{eq} = \frac{[P]_{eq}}{[S]_{eq}} = \frac{v_M^f K_M^P}{v_M^r K_M^S} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P}{k_{-1} K_M^S} = \frac{k_2 k_1}{k_{-1} k_{-2}}$$

which is the so-called *Haldane relationship* which indicates that the parameters of an enzymatic reaction are linked to the constant of equilibrium which, as already said, is not modified by the presence of the enzyme, because it depends only on the thermodynamic state of reactants and reagents.

2.3.1 Pentose phosphate pathway

This chain of enzymatic reactions is a very old and conserved one. It is a pathway that is parallel to glycolysis and produces NADPH and molecule of sugar with five carbons (called *pentoses*) that are used to synthesize nucleotides and some amino acids. We will now consider a step of this long chain of reactions, the reversible conversion of *D-ribulose 5-phosphate* (Ru5P) in *D-xylulose 5-phosphate* (X5P) catalyzed by *ribulose-phosphate 3-epimerase* (RPE):

For this reaction in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (a type of yeast), the following parameters have been calculated:

$$\text{Eq. 54} \quad \begin{aligned} K_M^{Ru5P} &= 5.97 \text{ mM} & k_2 &= 4020 \text{ s}^{-1} \\ K_M^{X5P} &= 7.70 \text{ mM} & K_{eq} &= 1.4 \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the concentration of the enzyme in the cytosol is:

$$\text{Eq. 55} \quad [RPE]_T = 0.03 \text{ mM}$$

Figure 10. Plot of the reversible Michaelis-Menten equation for ribulose-phosphate 3-epimerase. The intersection of the surface with the plane is the state of equilibrium of the reaction (the rate of production of X5P is the same as the rate of its transformation into Ru5P).

We can calculate the two maximal velocities (see Eq. 49):

$$\text{Eq. 56} \quad \begin{cases} v_M^f = k_2[E]_T = \frac{4020}{s} 0.03 \text{ mM} = 120.6 \frac{\text{mM}}{s} \\ v_M^r = k_{-1}[E]_T = \frac{3703.5}{s} 0.03 \text{ mM} = 111.10 \frac{\text{mM}}{s} \end{cases}$$

where k_{-1} as been calculated according to Eq. 52:

$$K_{eq} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P}{k_{-1} K_M^S} \Rightarrow k_{-1} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P}{K_{eq} K_M^S} = \frac{3703.5}{s}$$

All that said, the Michalis-Menten equation (Eq. 50) for this reaction is

$$\text{Eq. 57} \quad \frac{d[X5P]}{dt} = \frac{\frac{120.6 \frac{mM}{s}}{7.70mM} [Ru5P] - \frac{17.73 \frac{mM}{s}}{5.97mM} [X5P]}{1 + \frac{[Ru5P]}{7.70mM} + \frac{[X5P]}{5.97mM}}$$

CODE 3. The plot of this surface is in and the code that draws the plot is below. The intersection of the surface with the plane is the state of equilibrium of the reaction (the rate of production of X5P is the same as the rate of its transformation into Ru5P).

```

% file name = MM_reversible
% date of creation = 12/08/2019
clear all

K_M_S = 5.97 %Michaelis constant (mM) for direct reaction
K_M_P = 7.70 %Michaelis constant (mM) for reverse reaction
E_T = 0.03 %total concentration of the enzyme
k2 = 4020
V_M_F = E_T*k2 %Maximal velocity for direct reaction (mM/s)
K_eq = 1.4
k_1 = k2*K_M_P/(K_M_S*K_eq)
V_M_R = E_T*k_1 %Maximal velocity for reverse reaction (mM/s)
nodes = 30 %number of nodes

% the array for the substrate
S_M = 8.; %maximal substrate concentration (mM)
delta_S = S_M/nodes; %increase in substrate concentration
S(1) = 0.;
for i=2:1:nodes + 1
    S(i) = S(i-1) + delta_S;
endfor

% the array for the product
P_M = 12.; %maximal substrate concentration (mM)
delta_P = P_M/nodes; %increase in substrate concentration
P(1) = 0.;
for j=2:1:nodes +1
    P(j) = P(j-1) + delta_P;
endfor

% the rate
for i=1:1:nodes + 1
    for j=1:1:nodes + 1
        v_n = (((V_M_F/K_M_S)*S(i))-((V_M_R/K_M_P)*P(j)));
        v_d = 1 + (S(i)/K_M_S) + (P(j)/K_M_P);
        v(i,j) = v_n/v_d;
    endfor
endfor

% plot
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(P(1:nodes + 1), S(1:nodes + 1), v(1:nodes + 1,1:nodes + 1));
grid on
hold on
plane(1:nodes + 1,1:nodes + 1) = 0;
mesh(P(1:nodes + 1), S(1:nodes + 1), plane(1:nodes + 1,1:nodes + 1));
ylabel('D-ribose 5-phosphate (mM)');
xlabel('D-xylulose 5-phosphate (mM)');
zlabel('rate (mM/s)');

```

2.4 Inhibition

DEF. 18. Any molecule that can combine with an enzyme, interfering with its ability to bind the substrate is considered an *inhibitor* for the enzyme itself.

For instance, the molecule *disulfiram* binds to the enzyme *acetaldehyde dehydrogenases*, thus preventing the reaction catalyzed by this enzyme, a reaction in which *acetaldehyde* is converted into *acetyl coenzyme A*. As we will see, the substrate itself can be an inhibitor, once it reaches a certain concentration, as it is the case of L-tryptophan for IDO-1.

2.4.1 Competitive inhibition

DEF. 19. If the inhibitor binds to the active site of the enzyme, thus preventing or limiting the interaction of the enzyme with its substrate, we say that it is a *competitive inhibitor*. Usually, a competitive inhibitor resembles the substrate and thus it acts by reducing the concentration of the free enzyme available for substrate binding.

2.4.1.1 Irreversible form

The equation of the general irreversible enzymatic reaction with competitive inhibition is the following one.

The reaction between the enzyme and the inhibitor is assumed to be in equilibrium, so if K_I is its equilibrium constant, we can write Eq. 17 as

$$\text{Eq. 58} \quad K_I = \frac{[E][I]}{[EI]}$$

The conservation condition for the enzyme is

$$\text{Eq. 59} \quad [E_T] = [E] + [ES] + [EI]$$

We can still use the steady-state condition (Eq. 29) which gives

$$\text{Eq. 60} \quad [E] = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1} \frac{[ES]}{[S]} = K_M \frac{[ES]}{[S]}$$

Thus, substituting Eq. 60 in Eq. 58 and rearranging we have

$$\text{Eq. 61} \quad [EI] = \frac{K_M}{K_I} \frac{[ES][I]}{[S]}$$

From Eq. 59, Eq. 60, Eq. 61 we get

$$\text{Eq. 62} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T][S]}{K_M\left(1+\frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)+[S]}$$

But the rate of the reaction is given by $k_2[ES]$, thus we have

$$\text{Eq. 63} \quad v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_2[E_T][S]}{K_M\left(1+\frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)+[S]} = \frac{v_M[S]}{K_M\left(1+\frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)+[S]}$$

This is the Michaelis-Menten equation for competitive inhibition. If we express $[S]$ as nK_M and $[I]$ as m times K_I , we have the function

$$\text{Eq. 64} \quad \frac{v_0}{v_M} = \frac{n}{(1+m)+n}$$

whose diagram is plotted in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Michaelis-Menten equation for competitive inhibition, irreversible form.

2.4.1.2 Reversible form

We can further add complexity to the previous case, by considering a reversible enzymatic reaction, as in the following scheme:

The steady-state condition (Eq. 29) in this case gives

$$\text{Eq. 65} \quad [E] = \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} [ES]$$

Thus, substituting Eq. 65 in Eq. 58 and rearranging we have

$$\text{Eq. 66} \quad [EI] = \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} \frac{[ES][I]}{K_I}$$

From Eq. 59, Eq. 65, Eq. 66 we get

$$[E_T] = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} [ES] + [ES] + \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} \frac{[ES][I]}{K_I}$$

$$\text{Eq. 67} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T]}{\frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} + \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} \frac{[I]}{K_I} + 1}$$

By substituting Eq. 65 into the fourth equation in Eq. 43 we get

$$\text{Eq. 68} \quad \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \left(k_2 - k_{-2} \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} [P] \right) [ES]$$

Considering now Eq. 67 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[P]}{dt} &= \frac{k_2 - k_{-2} \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} [P]}{\frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} + \frac{k_{-1}+k_2}{k_1[S]+k_{-2}[P]} \frac{[I]}{K_I} + 1} [E_T] = \frac{k_2 - k_{-2} \frac{[P]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}}}{\frac{1}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} + \frac{1}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \frac{[I]}{K_I} + 1} [E_T] = \\ &= \frac{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{k_{-2}}{k_2} \right) [P]}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} k_2 [E_T] \end{aligned}$$

Remembering Eq. 112, we have

$$\text{Eq. 69} \quad \frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{k_{-2}}{k_2} = \frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_M^P K_{eq} K_M^S} = - \frac{1}{K_{eq} K_M^S}$$

Hence, the rate becomes

$$\text{Eq. 70} \quad \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \frac{k_2 [E_T]}{K_M^S} = \frac{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \frac{v_M}{K_M^S}$$

This is the Michaelis-Menten equation for competitive inhibition of a reversible enzymatic reaction.

2.4.1.3 Tryptophan transport (LAT1)

In the midbrain, L-tryptophan is transported through the cellular membrane by a membrane protein called Large neutral amino acid transporter 1 (LAT-1). The transport is in both the direction: LAT-1

carries cytosolic L-tryptophan (T_{cyt}) outside the cell while also transporting L-tryptophan present in extracellular space (T_{ECS}) in the cytoplasm. Transport phenomena like this can be modeled as reversible enzymatic reactions. In this case, there is also competitive inhibition due to large amino acids present both inside and outside the cell (A). That said, we can use Eq. 70 with the following notation:

$$\text{Eq. 71} \quad \frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = \frac{[T_{ECS}] - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{[T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} \right) \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}}$$

Experimentally it has been determined that:

$$\text{Eq. 72} \quad \begin{aligned} [A] &= 5 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & K_M^{T_{ECS}} &= 2.2 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & K_{eq} &= 3.43 \\ K_A &= 4.3 \cdot 10^3 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & K_M^{T_{cyt}} &= 2.0 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & v_M^f &= 1.2 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{min} \cdot \text{cell}} \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the concentration of T_{ECS} can be regarded as constant, and it is

$$\text{Eq. 73} \quad [T_{ECS}] = 1.5 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

CODE 4. The diagram of the rate in function of $[T_{cyt}]$ is in Figure 12. It is plotted by the following code.

```
% file name = MM_reversible_1
% date of creation = 22/08/2019
clear all
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10) % molecules/cell
K_M_Tcyt = 2.2*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3) % molecules/cell
K_eq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8) % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6) % molecules/cell
T_ECS = 1.5*(10^9) % molecules/cell
% the array for T_cyt
T_cyt (1) = 10^5; % molecules/cell
T_cyt (101) = 10^10; % molecules/cell
d = ( T_cyt (101)-T_cyt (1) )/100; % molecules/cell
for i=2:101
    T_cyt (i) = T_cyt (i-1) + d;
endfor
% the array for the rate
for i=1:101
    rate_n = V_M_F *(1 - ( T_cyt(i)/( T_ECS*K_eq ) ) )*( T_ECS/K_M_TECS );
    rate_d = 1 + (A/K_A) + (T_ECS/K_M_TECS) + (T_cyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt);
    rate (i) = rate_n/rate_d;
endfor
% plot
semilogx(T_cyt(1:101), rate (1:101), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('Cytosolic L-typtophan (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('Transport inside the cell (molecules/min*cell)');
```


Figure 12. Michaelis-Menten equation for the transport of L-tryptophan across the cytosolic membrane of a serotonergic neuron of the midbrain. A case of competitive inhibition, reversible form. The x-axis is in logarithmic scale.

2.4.2 Product inhibition

In some cases, the inhibitor is the product itself. The Michaelis-Menten equation for this case can be derived from Eq. 63 by simply putting $I = P$ and $K_I = K_P$:

$$\text{Eq. 74} \quad v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{v_M[S]}{K_M \left(1 + \frac{[P]}{K_P}\right) + [S]}$$

2.4.3 Uncompetitive inhibition

DEF. 20. If the inhibitor binds to the enzyme only when the substrate is bound to the enzyme itself, then we call it an *uncompetitive inhibitor*. The inhibitor, in this case, do not binds to the active site of the enzyme: it binds either to another site that is made available only when the enzyme is linked to its substrate, or to the substrate itself.

Uncompetitive inhibition is rarely found among enzymatic reactions with only one substrate. An example is that of lithium which acts as an uncompetitive inhibitor for *Myo-inositol monophosphatase*. More commonly, uncompetitive inhibition happens when we have multiple substrates. For instance, in a reaction in which substrate S_1 has to bind to the enzyme before S_2 in order for the reaction to take place, S_2 behaves as an uncompetitive inhibitor with respect to S_1 .

2.4.3.1 Irreversible form

The equation of the general irreversible enzymatic reaction with uncompetitive inhibition is the following one.

In this case, the equilibrium for the reaction between ES and the inhibitor gives

Eq. 75
$$K'_i = \frac{[ES][I]}{[EIS]}$$

Figure 13. Michaelis-Menten equation for uncompetitive inhibition, irreversible form.

The conservation condition for the enzyme give and the steady assumption (Eq. 29) give

Eq. 76
$$[E_T] = [E] + [ES] + [EIS]$$

Eq. 77
$$[E] = K_M \frac{[ES]}{[S]}$$

Considering these three equations we have

$$[ES] = \frac{K'_i [EIS]}{[I]} = \frac{K'_i ([E_T] - [E] - [ES])}{[I]} = \frac{K'_i \left([E_T] - K_M \frac{[ES]}{[S]} - [ES] \right)}{[I]}$$

Rearranging this equation, we have

$$[ES] \frac{[I]}{K'_i} - [E_T] + K_M \frac{[ES]}{[S]} + [ES] = 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 78} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T]}{\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + \frac{K_M}{[S]} + 1} = \frac{[E_T][S]}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1\right)[S] + K_M}$$

But the rate of the reaction is given by $k_2[ES]$, thus we have

$$\text{Eq. 79} \quad v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_2[E_T][S]}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1\right)[S] + K_M} = \frac{v_M[S]}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1\right)[S] + K_M}$$

This is the Michaelis-Menten equation for uncompetitive inhibition, irreversible case. If we express $[S]$ as nK_M and $[I]$ as m times K_I' , we have the function

$$\text{Eq. 80} \quad \frac{v_0}{v_M} = \frac{n}{(m+1)n+1}$$

whose diagram is plotted in Figure 13.

2.4.3.2 Reversible form

The equation of the general irreversible enzymatic reaction with uncompetitive inhibition is the following one

The steady-state condition (Eq. 29) in this case gives

$$\text{Eq. 81} \quad [E] = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} [ES]$$

On the other hand, Eq. 75 and Eq. 76 still hold, hence we have

$$\begin{aligned} [ES] &= \frac{K_I' [EIS]}{[I]} = K_I' \frac{[E_T] - [E] - [ES]}{[I]} = K_I' \frac{[E_T] - \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} [ES] - [ES]}{[I]} \\ \text{Eq. 82} \quad [ES] &= \frac{[E_T]}{\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} + 1} = \frac{[E_T]}{\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + \frac{1}{\frac{K_M^S}{[S]} + \frac{K_M^P}{[P]}} + 1} = \frac{[E_T] \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right)}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right) + 1} \end{aligned}$$

The rate of the reaction is given by $k_2[ES] - k_{-2}[E][P]$. But $[E]$ is given by Eq. 81, hence we have

$$v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_2[ES] - k_{-2}[E][P] = \left(k_2 - k_{-2} \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} [P] \right) [ES] =$$

$$= \left(k_2 - \frac{k_{-2}[P]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \right) [ES] = \frac{\frac{k_2}{K_M^S} [S] + k_2 \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{k_{-2}}{k_2} \right) [P]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} [ES]$$

But $[ES]$ has been determined in Eq. 82, so we have

$$v_0 = \frac{\frac{k_2}{K_M^S} [S] + k_2 \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{k_{-2}}{k_2} \right) [P]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \frac{[E_T] \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right)}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right) + 1} = \frac{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{k_{-2}}{k_2} \right) [P]}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right) + 1} [E_T] k_2$$

Remembering Eq. 69, we have

$$\text{Eq. 83} \quad v_0 = \frac{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right) + 1} \frac{[E_T] k_2}{K_M^S} = \frac{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{\left(\frac{[I]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right) + 1} \frac{v_M}{K_M^S}$$

This is the Michaelis-Menten equation for uncompetitive inhibition, reversible case.

2.4.3.3 Substrate inhibition

A particular case of uncompetitive inhibition is the one in which the substrate itself is the inhibitor. It has been proposed, for instance, that Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase-1 (IDO-1) (which has the same function than IDO-2, see paragraph 2.2.1) is inhibited by L-tryptophan because it has a second binding site for its substrate, which is inactive. Moreover, when the enzyme is bound to the substrate through this second site, then it is made inactive. The general scheme for such a reaction is the following one:

where ES' is the complex made up by the enzyme and the substrate, when the latter binds to the inactive site. The Michaelis-Menten equation for this case can be obtained directly from Eq. 79:

$$\text{Eq. 84} \quad v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 [E_T] [S]}{\left(\frac{[S]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) [S] + K_M} = \frac{v_M [S]}{\left(\frac{[S]}{K_I'} + 1 \right) [S] + K_M}$$

2.4.3.4 Tryptophan metabolism (IDO-1)

IDO-1 catalyzes the same reaction as IDO-2, but it is expressed by a larger variety of cell types. As mentioned, it is inhibited by its substrate itself (L-tryptophan) which can bind to an inactive site and prevent the enzyme from binding the substrate in the active site. For a serotonergic neuron of the midbrain we have the following M-M equation and experimental data:

$$\text{Eq. 85} \quad v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_2[IDO_1][T_{cyt}]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1\right)[T_{cyt}] + K_M^T}$$

$$\text{Eq. 86} \quad k_2 = 84 \frac{\text{molecules L-Try}}{\text{min}\cdot\text{cell}} \frac{\text{molecules DO-1}}{\text{cell}} \quad [IDO_1] = 208 \frac{\text{molecules IDO-1}}{\text{cell}}$$

$$K_M^T = 3.4 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules L-Try}}{\text{cell}} \quad K_I^T = 2.5 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules L-Try}}{\text{cell}}$$

CODE 5. The diagram of the rate in function of $[T_{cyt}]$ is in Figure 14. It is plotted by the following code.

Figure 14. Michaelis-Menten equation for the conversion of L-tryptophan in N formylkynurenin. The x-axis is in logarithmic scale on the left, while it is in linear scale on the right.

```
% file name = MM_substrate_1
% date of creation = 25/08/2019
clear all

K_M_T = 3.4*(10^7) % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_T = 2.5*(10^8) % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84 % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208 % molecules IDO1/cell

% the array for T_cyt
T_cyt (1) = 10000000; % molecules/cell
T_cyt (101) = 1000000000; % molecules/cell
d = ( T_cyt (101)-T_cyt (1) )/100; % molecules/cell
for i=2:101
    T_cyt (i) = T_cyt (i-1) + d;
endfor

% the array for the rate
for i=1:101
    rate_n = k_2*IDO1*T_cyt(i);
    rate_d = ( ( 1 + (T_cyt(i)/K_I_T) ) * T_cyt(i) ) + K_M_T;
    rate (i) = rate_n/rate_d;
endfor

% plot
figure (1)
axis ([T_cyt(1) T_cyt(101) min(rate) max(rate)])
semilogx(T_cyt (1:101), rate (1:101), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
```

```

grid on
xlabel('Cytosolic L-typtophan (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate of conversion (molecules/min*cell)');
figure (2)
plot (T_cyt (1:101), rate (1:101), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('Cytosolic L-typtophan (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate of conversion (molecules/min*cell)');

```

2.4.4 Mixed inhibition

DEF. 21. When the inhibitor displays both the behaviors described in paragraphs 2.4.1 and 0 we have a case of *mixed inhibition* also called (with a misleading name), *non-competitive inhibition*. The name is misleading because there is competitive inhibition, by definition, as said.

2.4.4.1 Irreversible form

The equation of the general irreversible enzymatic reaction with mixed inhibition is the following one.

In this case, we have two equilibrium relationships:

$$\text{Eq. 87} \quad K_I = \frac{[E][I]}{[EI]}$$

$$\text{Eq. 88} \quad K'_I = \frac{[ES][I]}{[EIS]}$$

The conservation for the enzyme gives:

$$\text{Eq. 89} \quad [E_T] = [E] + [ES] + [EI] + [EIS]$$

Considering these three equations we have

$$[ES] = [E_T] - [E] - [EI] - [EIS] = [E_T] - [E] - \frac{[E][I]}{K_I} - \frac{[ES][I]}{K'_I}$$

$$\text{Eq. 90} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T] - [E] \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K'_I}}$$

We can still use the steady-state condition (Eq. 29) which gives

$$\text{Eq. 91} \quad [E] = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1} \frac{[ES]}{[S]} = K_M \frac{[ES]}{[S]}$$

So, we have

$$\text{Eq. 92} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T]}{\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) + \frac{K_M}{[S]}\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)}$$

But the rate of the reaction is given by $k_2[ES]$, thus we have

$$\text{Eq. 93} \quad v_0 = \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_2[E_T]}{\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) + \frac{K_M}{[S]}\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)} = \frac{v_M[S]}{[S]\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) + K_M\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)}$$

As can easily be seen, for $K_I \rightarrow \infty$ we have Eq. 79, while for $K_I' \rightarrow \infty$ we get Eq. 63, as expected. This is the Michaelis-Menten equation for Mixed inhibition, irreversible form.

2.4.4.2 Reversible form

The equation of the general reversible enzymatic reaction with uncompetitive inhibition is the following one.

In this case, the set of equations is:

$$\text{Eq. 94} \quad K_I = \frac{[E][I]}{[EI]}, \quad K_I' = \frac{[ES][I]}{[EIS]}$$

$$\text{Eq. 95} \quad [E_T] = [E] + [ES] + [EI] + [EIS]$$

$$\text{Eq. 96} \quad [E] = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1[S] + k_{-2}[P]} [ES] = \frac{[ES]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}}$$

Substituting the first two and the third one in the second one we get

$$\begin{aligned} [E_T] &= [E] + [ES] + \frac{[E][I]}{K_I} + \frac{[ES][I]}{K_I'} = [E] \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right) + [ES] \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) = \\ &= \frac{[ES]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right) + [ES] \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) = [ES] \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I}\right)}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} + \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 97} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T]}{\frac{\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right)}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} + \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right)} = \frac{[E_T] \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) + \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'}\right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}\right)}$$

The rate of the reaction is given by $k_2[ES] - k_{-2}[E][P]$, therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[P]}{dt} &= k_2[ES] - k_{-2} \frac{[ES]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} [P] = \left(k_2 - k_{-2} \frac{[P]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \right) [ES] = \\ &= k_2 \left[\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{k_{-2}}{k_2} \right) [P] \right] [ES] \end{aligned}$$

Remembering Eq. 69 we have

$$\frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_2}{K_M^S} \left([S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}} \right) [ES]$$

and substituting in this equation the expression found for $[ES]$ we conclude that

$$\text{Eq. 98} \quad \frac{d[P]}{dt} = v_0 = \frac{\left([S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}} \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right)}{\left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'} \right) + \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I'} \right) \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right)} \frac{k_2 [E_T]}{K_M^S}$$

As one might expect, for $K_I' \rightarrow \infty$ we get Eq. 70 and for $K_I \rightarrow \infty$ this relationship becomes Eq. 83.

3 Numerical methods

3.1 Cauchy problem

Let's consider the two following functions of n elements:

$$\text{Eq. 99} \quad \mathbf{x}(t) = [x_1(t) \quad x_2(t) \quad \dots \quad x_n(t)]^T$$

$$\text{Eq. 100} \quad \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}(t)) = [f_1(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \quad f_2(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \quad \dots \quad f_n(\mathbf{x}(t), t)]^T$$

We are interested in the following systems of ordinary² differential equations (ODEs) of the first order:

$$\text{Eq. 101} \quad \frac{d\mathbf{x}(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}(t)) \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \dot{x}_1(t) = f_1(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); t) \\ \dot{x}_2(t) = f_2(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); t) \\ \vdots \\ \dot{x}_n(t) = f_n(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); t) \end{cases}$$

with the *initial conditions*:

$$\text{Eq. 102} \quad \begin{cases} x_i(t_0) = x_{i0} \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{x}_0$$

As the reader can easily recognize, Eq. 28 and Eq. 43 are exactly examples of this category of systems. In our case, $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is a vector whose elements are the concentration of the enzyme, the concentration of the reactant, the concentration of the product and the concentration of the enzyme-substrate complex; \mathbf{x}_0 contains their respective concentrations for $t = t_0$. This system of equations and its initial condition are called *Cauchy problem*.

Now, does this system has a solution? If it has a solution, is it unique? The answer to these important questions is provided by the following theorem (called *theorem of existence and uniqueness*). There are several possible enunciations of this proposition, depending for instance on the domain I is defined in. Since we are interested only in values $t > t_0$, where t_0 is the point in time in which the chemical reaction starts, we can restrict ourselves to the following enunciation.

PROP. 2 (*theorem of existence and uniqueness*). Let $\mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x})$ be defined and continuous in $I = \{(t, \mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^n | t \in [t_0, t_0 + \beta], \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n\}$. If $\forall M > 0 \exists L > 0$ so that³

$$\text{Eq. 103} \quad |\mathbf{x}^{(1)}|, |\mathbf{x}^{(2)}| < M \Rightarrow |\mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})| \leq L|\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}|, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_0 + \beta]$$

then there is only one function $\mathbf{x}(t) \in C^1(I)$ such that both Eq. 101 and Eq. 102 are satisfied $\forall t \in [t_0, t_0 + \beta]$.

In the previous proposition, we have assumed that

$$\text{Eq. 104} \quad |\mathbf{x}| = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2}$$

² A differential equation is called *ordinary* when there are no partial derivatives. It is called of the first order when the derivatives with respect to that variable are all of the first order.

³ This condition means that \mathbf{f} is a Lipschitz function with respect to \mathbf{x} for $t \in [\alpha, \beta]$.

$$\text{Eq. 105} \quad |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| = \sqrt{[x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}]^2 + [x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}]^2 + \dots + [x_n^{(2)} - x_n^{(1)}]^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Eq. 106} \quad & |f(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - f(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})| = \\ & = \sqrt{[f_1(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - f_1(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})]^2 + [f_2(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - f_2(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})]^2 + \dots + [f_n(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - f_n(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})]^2} \end{aligned}$$

To further simplify this enunciation of the theorem of existence and uniqueness, consider the following proof.

PROP. 3 (*lemma*). If

$$\text{Eq. 107} \quad \exists L \in \mathbb{R} \left| \frac{\partial f(t, \mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i} \right| \leq L \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall (t, \mathbf{x}) \in I \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{array} \right.$$

then the hypothesis in Eq. 104 is also true.

Proof. To see that, let's assume that $n = 2$. Then Eq. 107 can be written as follows:

$$\exists L \in \mathbb{R} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left| \frac{\partial f(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right| = \sqrt{\left| \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\partial f_2(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right|^2} \leq L' \\ \left| \frac{\partial f(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_2} \right| = \sqrt{\left| \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_2} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\partial f_2(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_2} \right|^2} \leq L' \end{array} \right. \quad \forall (t, \mathbf{x}) \in I \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 108} \quad \exists L \in \mathbb{R} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left| \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right| \leq L' \\ \left| \frac{\partial f_2(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right| \leq L' \\ \left| \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_2} \right| \leq L' \\ \left| \frac{\partial f_2(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_2} \right| \leq L' \end{array} \right. \quad \forall (t, \mathbf{x}) \in I$$

From the definition of derivative, we can also write that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right| \leq L' \quad \forall (t, \mathbf{x}) \in I \\ \Rightarrow \exists M_1 : & \left| x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)} \right| \leq M_1 \Rightarrow \left| \frac{f_1(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2) - f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2)}{x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}} - \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right| \leq L' \\ \Rightarrow \exists M_1 : & \left| x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)} \right| \leq M_1 \Rightarrow \left| \frac{f_1(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2) - f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2)}{x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}} \right| \leq L' + \left| \frac{\partial f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2)}{\partial x_1} \right| \leq 2L' \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, we can proceed for the other three inequalities in Eq. 108 so that we find

$$\begin{cases} \exists M_1 : |x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \leq M_1 \Rightarrow |f_1(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2) - f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2)| \leq 2L' |x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \forall x_2 \in \mathbb{R} \\ \exists M'_1 : |x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \leq M'_1 \Rightarrow |f_2(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2) - f_2(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2)| \leq 2L' |x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \forall x_2 \in \mathbb{R} \\ \exists M_2 : |x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \leq M_2 \Rightarrow |f_1(t, x_1, x_2^{(2)}) - f_1(t, x_1, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L' |x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \forall x_1 \in \mathbb{R} \\ \exists M'_2 : |x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \leq M'_2 \Rightarrow |f_2(t, x_1, x_2^{(2)}) - f_2(t, x_1, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L' |x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \forall x_1 \in \mathbb{R} \end{cases}$$

and this must be true $\forall t \in [t_0, t_0 + \beta]$. Now, if $M' = \max\{M_1, M'_1, M_2, M'_2\}$, we can write, in particular, that

$$\exists M' : |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \leq M' \sqrt{2} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} |f_1(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2^{(2)}) - f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L' |x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \\ |f_2(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2^{(2)}) - f_2(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L' |x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \\ |f_1(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2^{(2)}) - f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L' |x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \\ |f_2(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2^{(2)}) - f_2(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L' |x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \end{cases}$$

Now, since $|x_1^{(2)} - x_1^{(1)}| \leq |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}|$ and also $|x_2^{(2)} - x_2^{(1)}| \leq |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}|$, we can write

$$\exists M' : |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \leq M' \sqrt{2} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} |f_1(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2^{(2)}) - f_1(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \\ |f_2(t, x_1^{(2)}, x_2^{(2)}) - f_2(t, x_1^{(1)}, x_2^{(1)})| \leq 2L |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \end{cases}$$

So we have found that

$$\exists M' : |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \leq M' \sqrt{2} \Rightarrow \sqrt{[f_1(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - f_1(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})]^2 + [f_2(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - f_2(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})]^2} \leq L |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}|$$

where I have introduced $L = 2\sqrt{2}L'$. Now consider that, by defining $M = M' \sqrt{2}/2$ we have

$$\begin{cases} |\mathbf{x}^{(1)}| \leq M \\ |\mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \leq M \end{cases} \Rightarrow |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \leq 2M = M' \sqrt{2}$$

So we have proved that if the hypothesis is true for $n = 2$, then

$$\exists M : |\mathbf{x}^{(1)}|, |\mathbf{x}^{(2)}| \leq M \Rightarrow |\mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}) - \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}^{(1)})| \leq L |\mathbf{x}^{(1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(2)}|$$

which is the thesis for $n = 2$ ■

Considering PROP. 3 we can now write another, simplified, enunciation of PROP. 2.

PROP. 4 (*theorem of existence and uniqueness*). Let $\mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x})$ be defined and continuous in $I = \{(t, \mathbf{x}) \in R \times R^n | t \in [t_0, t_0 + \beta], \mathbf{x} \in R^n\}$. If

$$\text{Eq. 109} \quad \exists L \in \mathbb{R} \left| \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i} \right| \leq L \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \forall (t, \mathbf{x}) \in I \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{array} \right.$$

then there is only one function $\mathbf{x}(t) \in C^1(I)$ such that both Eq. 101 and Eq. 102 are satisfied $\forall t \in [t_0, t_0 + \beta]$.

Now, if we consider the system in Eq. 43, we have

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} [S] \\ [E] \\ [ES] \\ [P] \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1[E][S] \\ k_{-1}[ES] \\ k_2[ES] \\ k_{-2}[E][P] \end{bmatrix}$$

hence, for the derivative with respect to $x_1 = [S]$ we have

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x})}{\partial [S]} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1[E] \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -k_1[E] \\ -k_1[E] \\ k_1[E] \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \left| \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x})}{\partial [S]} \right| = k_1 \sqrt{3} [E]$$

and it is obviously $\left| \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{x})}{\partial [S]} \right| \leq k_1 \sqrt{3} [E]_T$. Analogous relationships can be found for the other three derivatives. So, for our purposes, the hypotheses of PROP. 4 are verified and we can conclude that Eq. 43 has a unique solution.

3.2 The stoichiometric matrix for reversible and irreversible reactions

The system in Eq. 43 can also be written with the use of matrixes:

$$\text{Eq. 110} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d[S]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[E]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[ES]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1[E][S] \\ k_{-1}[ES] \\ k_2[ES] \\ k_{-2}[E][P] \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \frac{d\mathbf{x}(t)}{dt} = A \cdot \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}(t), t, \mathbf{k})$$

DEF. 22. The matrix that appears in Eq. 110 is called *stoichiometric* and it is the same for any reversible enzymatic reaction. The elements of the vector $\mathbf{x}(t)$ are the concentrations that we want to determine. The vector \mathbf{k} is given by the kinetic constants of the reaction. Now, if we name the rates of each of the four elementary reactions in an obvious way:

$$v_1 = k_1[E][S], v_{-1} = k_{-1}[ES], v_2 = k_2[ES], v_{-2} = k_{-2}[E][P]$$

then we also have the more compact expression

$$\text{Eq. 111} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d[S]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[E]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[ES]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_{-1} \\ v_2 \\ v_{-2} \end{bmatrix}$$

The same stoichiometric matrix can be used for an irreversible reaction, the only difference is that in this case $k_{-2} = 0$. The problem with Eq. 110 is that we need to know all the kinetic constants in order to perform the calculation, while what can be measured in studies is $k_2 = k_{cat}$, K_M^S , K_M^P and K_{eq} . It is possible to prove the following theorem.

PROP. 5. For a reversible reaction, it can be proved that

$$\text{Eq. 112} \quad \begin{cases} k_{-2} = k_2 \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_M^P K_{eq} K_M^S} \\ k_1 = k_2 \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_{eq} K_M^S} \\ k_{-1} = k_2 \frac{K_M^P}{K_{eq} K_M^S} \end{cases}$$

Proof. From Eq. 48 and Eq. 52 we have

$$\text{Eq. 113} \quad \begin{cases} K_M^S = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1}, K_M^P = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_{-2}}, K_{eq} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P}{k_{-1} K_M^S} = \frac{k_2 k_1}{k_{-1} k_{-2}} \Rightarrow \\ \begin{cases} k_1 = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{K_M^S} \\ k_{-2} = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{K_M^P} \\ k_{-1} = \frac{k_2 k_1}{K_{eq} k_{-2}} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

If we substitute the third in the other two equations we have

$$\text{Eq. 114} \quad \begin{cases} k_1 = \frac{\frac{k_2 k_1}{K_{eq} k_{-2}} + k_2}{K_M^S} \\ k_{-2} = \frac{\frac{k_2 k_1}{K_{eq} k_{-2}} + k_2}{K_M^P} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} k_1 K_M^S k_{-2} K_{eq} - k_1 k_2 = k_{-2} k_2 K_{eq} \\ k_{-2} K_M^P k_{-2} K_{eq} - k_1 k_2 = k_{-2} k_2 K_{eq} \end{cases}$$

By comparison, we have

$$\text{Eq. 115} \quad k_1 = k_{-2} \frac{K_M^P}{K_M^S}$$

If we substitute this expression in the first of Eq. 114 we have

$$\text{Eq. 116} \quad \begin{aligned} k_{-2}^2 K_M^P K_{eq} - k_{-2} k_2 \left(\frac{K_M^P}{K_M^S} + K_{eq} \right) &= 0 \Leftrightarrow k_{-2} \left[k_{-2} K_M^P K_{eq} - k_2 \left(\frac{K_M^P}{K_M^S} + K_{eq} \right) \right] = 0 \\ k_{-2} &= \frac{k_2 \left(\frac{K_M^P}{K_M^S} + K_{eq} \right)}{K_M^P K_{eq}} = k_2 \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_M^P K_{eq} K_M^S} \end{aligned}$$

If we substitute Eq. 116 in Eq. 115 we have

$$\text{Eq. 117} \quad k_1 = k_2 \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_{eq} K_M^{S^2}}$$

If we substitute Eq. 116 and Eq. 115 in a third of $K_M^S = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1}$, $K_M^P = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_{-2}}$, $K_{eq} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P}{k_{-1} K_M^S} = \frac{k_2 k_1}{k_{-1} k_{-2}} \Rightarrow$

Eq. 113 we have

$$\text{Eq. 118} \quad k_{-1} = \frac{k_2}{K_{eq} k_2 \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_M^P K_{eq} K_M^S}} k_2 \frac{K_M^P + K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_{eq} K_M^{S^2}} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P K_{eq} K_M^S}{K_{eq}} \frac{1}{K_{eq} K_M^{S^2}} = \frac{k_2 K_M^P}{K_{eq} K_M^S}$$

So, Eq. 116, Eq. 117, Eq. 118 give the thesis ■

For what concerns an irreversible reaction, k_1 and k_{-1} remain undetermined, because we only know that

$$\text{Eq. 119} \quad \begin{cases} k_1 = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{K_M} \\ k_{-2} = 0 \end{cases}$$

This means that the system of ODEs in Eq. 110 can't be integrated unless we find other data on the reaction.

3.3 Euler's method for reversible reactions

We know that the Cauchy problem defined by Eq. 110 plus the initial conditions for $[S]$, $[E]$, $[ES]$, $[P]$ has a unique solution (PROP. 4), and we have also found a semi-analytical solution for it in the case of irreversible enzymatic reactions (Eq. 171 and Eq. 172). We have also tried a numerical approach in paragraph 4.1.2, where the method by Newton for transcendental equations has been used to calculate $[S]$ in function of time. Now, I propose a more general method, that can be easily applied to all the other type of enzymatic reactions that are described in these notes: Euler's method. We can write

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(t, x(t)) \Rightarrow \frac{x(t + \Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t} \cong f(t, x(t)) \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 120} \quad x(t + \Delta t) \cong x(t) + f(t, x(t)) \Delta t$$

which means approximating $x(t + \Delta t)$ with the value that the tangent to $x(t)$ in t assumes in $t + \Delta t$. The smaller the value of Δt , the better the approximation. Similarly, we can approximate the system in Eq. 110 in a following way:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{[S]_{k+1} - [S]_k}{\Delta t} \\ \frac{[E]_{k+1} - [E]_k}{\Delta t} \\ \frac{[ES]_{k+1} - [ES]_k}{\Delta t} \\ \frac{[P]_{k+1} - [P]_k}{\Delta t} \end{bmatrix} \cong \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d[S]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[E]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[ES]}{dt} \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1[E]_k[S]_k \\ k_{-1}[ES]_k \\ k_2[ES]_k \\ k_{-2}[E]_k[P]_k \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 121} \quad \begin{bmatrix} [S]_{k+1} \\ [E]_{k+1} \\ [ES]_{k+1} \\ [P]_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [S]_k \\ [E]_k \\ [ES]_k \\ [P]_k \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1[E]_k[S]_k \\ k_{-1}[ES]_k \\ k_2[ES]_k \\ k_{-2}[E]_k[P]_k \end{bmatrix} \Delta t$$

This is the so-called *Euler's method*, the simplest way to solve numerically a system of first-order ODEs.

3.3.1 Pentose phosphate pathway

CODE 6. This is the application of Euler's method (Eq. 121) to the reaction in Eq. 53. It plots the diagrams in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Concentrations and rate, in function of time.

```
% file name = Euler_reversible
% date of creation = 14/08/2019
clear all
K_M_S = 5.97 %Michaelis constant (mM) for direct reaction
K_M_P = 7.70 %Michaelis constant (mM) for reverse reaction
E_T = 0.01 %total concentration of the enzyme
k2 = 4020
V_M_F = E_T*k2 %Maximal velocity for direct reaction (mM/s)
K_eq = 1.4
k_1 = k2*K_M_P/(K_M_S*K_eq)
V_M_R = E_T*k_1 %Maximal velocity for reverse reaction (mM/s)
k_2 = k2*(K_M_P+(K_eq*K_M_S))/(K_M_P*K_eq*K_M_S)
k1 = k2*(K_M_P+(K_eq*K_M_S))/(K_M_S*K_eq*K_M_S)
```

```

k_1 = k2*(K_M_P/(K_eq*K_M_S))
S(1)= 0.09 % initial substrate concentration (m M)
P(1)= 0.01 % initial product concentration (m M)
E(1)= E_T
ES(1) = 0
rate(1) = k2*ES(1)-k_2*E(1)*P(1)
t(1) = 0. % time zero
delta_t = 0.0001 % increase in time
% the stoichiometric matrix
A (1,:) = [-1, 1, 0, 0];
A (2,:) = [-1, 1, 1, -1];
A (3,:) = [1, -1, -1, 1];
A (4,:) = [0, 0, 1, -1];
% arrays for time, x(t), [S]
% the array for concentrations
i=1;
while ( abs( (P(i)/S(i) )-K_eq)>0.01 )
% the array for concentrations
C(1:4,1) = [S(i); E(i); ES(i); P(i)];
% array of the derivatives
D(1:4,1) = [k1*E(i)*S(i); k_1*ES(i); k2*ES(i); k_2*E(i)*P(i)];
%array of incree
B(1:4,1) = A*D(1:4,1);
% the new array for the concentrations
C(1:4,1) = C(1:4,1) + B(1:4,1)*delta_t;
S(i+1) = C(1,1);
E(i+1) = C(2,1);
ES(i+1) = C(3,1);
P(i+1) = C(4,1);
rate(i+1) = B(4,1);
t(i+1) = t(i) + delta_t;
i = i+1;
i_M = i;
endwhile
i_M
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:100:i_M), S(1:100:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:100:i_M), P(1:100:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:100:i_M), ES(1:100:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot (t(1:100:i_M), E(1:100:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 1)
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('Concentration (mM)');
legend('D-ribulose 5-phosphate (mM)', 'D-xylulose 5-phosphate (mM)', 'RPE-Ru5P', 'free RPE');
figure(2)
plot (t(1:100:i_M), rate(1:100:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('rate (mM/s)');

```

3.4 Runge-Kutta method

We have seen how in the method named after Euler, the function that is the solution of the Cauchy's problem is locally approximated with its tangent. Another way to solve numerically the same problem comes from the approximation of a function $x(t)$ with a line whose angular coefficient is an average of three approximations.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \cong \frac{x(t + \Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t} \\ \frac{dx\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{dt} \cong \frac{x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) - x(t)}{\frac{\Delta t}{2}} \\ \frac{dx(t + \Delta t)}{dt} \cong \frac{x(t + \Delta t) - x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{\frac{\Delta t}{2}} \end{array} \right. \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \Delta t \cong x(t + \Delta t) - x(t) \\ \frac{dx\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{dt} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \cong x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) - x(t) \\ \frac{dx(t + \Delta t)}{dt} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \cong x(t + \Delta t) - x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \end{array} \right.$$

In our case, $\dot{x}(t) = f(t, x(t))$, so we can write

$$\text{Eq. 122} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} f(t, x(t))\Delta t + x(t) \cong x(t + \Delta t) \\ f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right)\frac{\Delta t}{2} + x(t) \cong x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ f(t + \Delta t, x(t + \Delta t))\frac{\Delta t}{2} + x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \cong x(t + \Delta t) \end{array} \right.$$

Now, we approximate the angular coefficient of the tangent to $x(t)$ with an average value given by

$$\text{Eq. 123} \quad \frac{x(t+\Delta t)-x(t)}{\Delta t} \cong \frac{f(t,x(t))+4f\left(t+\frac{\Delta t}{2},x\left(t+\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right)+f(t+\Delta t,x(t+\Delta t))}{6}$$

where a higher weigh has been given to the slope at the midpoint. Now, considering the first equation in Eq. 122 we can write

$$\text{Eq. 124} \quad f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \frac{f(t,x(t))\Delta t}{2}\right)$$

On the other hand, considering the second equation in Eq. 122 we can also write

$$\text{Eq. 125} \quad f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right)\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)$$

Moreover, we have

$$\text{Eq. 126} \quad f(t + \Delta t, x(t + \Delta t)) = f\left(t + \Delta t, x(t) + f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right)\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\Delta t\right)$$

So, if we define $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4$ in the following way

$$\text{Eq. 127} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1 = f(t, x(t)) \\ \lambda_2 = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_1 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_3 = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_2 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_4 = f(t + \Delta t, x(t) + \lambda_3 \Delta t) \end{cases}$$

we can write Eq. 123 as follows

$$\text{Eq. 128} \quad \frac{x(t+\Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t} \cong \frac{\lambda_1 + 2f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_1 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) + 2f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_2 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) + \lambda_4}{6}$$

where we have used both the expressions found for $f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right)$. All that said, the *Classic Runge-Kutta method*, also known simply as the Runge-Kutta method, states that we can assume:

$$\text{Eq. 129} \quad x(t + \Delta t) = x(t) + \frac{\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2 + 2\lambda_3 + \lambda_4}{6} \Delta t$$

As the method named after Euler, this method approximates locally the function $x(t)$ with a line, but in this case, the angular coefficient of the line is an average of the following angular coefficients: λ_1 , which is the angular coefficient of the tangent to $x(t)$ in t ; λ_2 and λ_3 which are approximations of the angular coefficient of the tangent in $(t + \Delta t/2)$; λ_4 , which is an approximation of the tangent in $(t + \Delta t)$. Note that λ_2 is based on the first approximation, λ_3 on the second and λ_4 on the third. Using a symbology suitable for coding, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 130} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1^{(i)} = f(t_i, x_i) \\ \lambda_2^{(i)} = f\left(t_i + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_3^{(i)} = f\left(t_i + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_4^{(i)} = f\left(t_i + \Delta t, x_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t\right) \\ x_{i+1} = x_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t \end{cases}$$

The order in which the equations are written is also the order that the code must follow in their evaluation.

3.4.1 Reversible reactions

This holds for one differential equation, now we have to adapt this method to the four differential equations in Eq. 43. For the first equation we have:

$$\text{Eq. 131} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} = -k_1[E]_i[S]_i + k_{-1}[ES]_i \\ \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} = -k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} = -k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} = -k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) + k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ [S]_{i+1} = [S]_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t \end{cases}$$

For the second equation, we have

$$\text{Eq. 132} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} = -k_1[E]_i[S]_i + (k_{-1} + k_2)[ES]_i - k_{-2}[E]_i[P]_i \\ \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} = -k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + (k_{-1} + k_2) \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) - k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} = -k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + (k_{-1} + k_2) \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) - k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} = -k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) + (k_{-1} + k_2) \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) - k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ [E]_{i+1} = [E]_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t \end{cases}$$

For the third equation, we have

Eq. 133

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} = k_1[E]_i[S]_i - (k_{-1} + k_2)[ES]_i + k_{-2}[E]_i \\ \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} = k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) - (k_{-1} + k_2) \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} = k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) - (k_{-1} + k_2) \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} = k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) - (k_{-1} + k_2) \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) + k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ [ES]_{i+1} = [ES]_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t \end{cases}$$

For the fourth equation, we have

$$\text{Eq. 134} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} = k_2[ES]_i - k_{-2}[E]_i[P]_i \\ \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} = k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) - k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} = k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) - k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ \lambda_{4,4}^{(i)} = k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) - k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ [P]_{i+1} = [P]_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,4}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t \end{cases}$$

These 20 equations must be calculated in the following order. The first step is

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1[E]_i[S]_i \\ k_{-1}[ES]_i \\ k_2[ES]_i \\ k_{-2}[E]_i[P]_i \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \\
\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \\
\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \\ k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \\
\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{4,4}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \\
\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} [S]_{i+1} \\ [E]_{i+1} \\ [ES]_{i+1} \\ [P]_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} [S]_i \\ [E]_i \\ [ES]_i \\ [P]_i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,4}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta t}{6}
\end{aligned}$$

3.4.1.1 Pentose phosphate pathway

CODE 7. This is the application of the Runge-Kutta method to the reaction in Eq. 53. In the code, I employ two matrices. Matrix C is defined as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} k_1[E]_i[S]_i & k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_1 \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ k_{-1}[ES]_i & k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_{-1} \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ k_2[ES]_i & k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_2 \left([ES]_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \\ k_{-2}[E]_i[P]_i & k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) & k_{-2} \left([E]_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \Delta t \right) \end{bmatrix}$$

Matrix Λ has the following definition:

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} & \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} & \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} & \lambda_{1,4}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} & \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} & \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} & \lambda_{2,4}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} & \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} & \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} & \lambda_{3,4}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} & \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} & \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} & \lambda_{4,4}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix}$$

This code plots the two diagrams in Figure 16.

```
% file name = Runge_Kutta_reversible
% date of creation = 20/08/2019
clear all
K_M_S = 5.97 % Michaelis constant (mM) for direct reaction
K_M_P = 7.70 % Michaelis constant (mM) for reverse reaction
E_T = 0.01 % total concentration of the enzyme
k2 = 4020
V_M_F = E_T*k2 % Maximal velocity for direct reaction (mM/s)
K_eq = 1.4
k_1 = k2*K_M_P/(K_M_S*K_eq)
V_M_R = E_T*k_1 %Maximal velocity for reverse reaction (mM/s)
k_2 = k2*(K_M_P+(K_eq*K_M_S))/(K_M_P*K_eq*K_M_S)
k1 = k2*(K_M_P+(K_eq*K_M_S))/(K_M_S*K_eq*K_M_S)
k_1 = k2*(K_M_P/(K_eq*K_M_S))
i = 1
S(i)= 0.09 % initial substrate concentration (m M)
P(i)= 0.02 % initial product concentration (m M)
E(i)= E_T % initial free enzyme concentration (m M)
ES(i) = 0 % initial bound enzyme concentration (m M)
rate(i) = k2*ES(i)-k_2*E(i)*P(i); % initial speed
t(i) = 0. % time zero
d_t = 0.0001 % increase in time
% the stoichiometric matrix
A (1,:) = [-1, 1, 0, 0];
A (2,:) = [-1, 1, 1, -1];
A (3,:) = [1, -1, -1, 1];
A (4,:) = [0, 0, 1, -1];
while ( abs( (P(i)/S(i) )-K_eq)>0.01 )
% the array for concentrations
C(1:4,1) = [k1*E(i)*S(i); k_1*ES(i); k2*ES(i); k_2*E(i)*P(i)];
% array of the first level of lambda constants
lambda(1,1:4) = (A*C(1:4,1))';
C(1,2) = k1*( E(i)+(lambda(1,2)*(d_t/2)) )*( S(i)+(lambda(1,1)*(d_t/2)) );
C(2,2) = k_1*( ES(i)+(lambda(1,3)*(d_t/2)) );
C(3,2) = k2*( ES(i)+ (lambda(1,3)*(d_t/2)) );
C(4,2) = k_2*( E(i)+ (lambda(1,2)*(d_t/2)) )*( P(i)+(lambda(1,4)*(d_t/2)) );
% array of the second level of lambda constants
lambda(2,1:4) = (A*C(1:4,2))';
C(1,3) = k1*( E(i)+(lambda(2,2)*(d_t/2)) )*( S(i)+(lambda(2,1)*(d_t/2)) );
C(2,3) = k_1*( ES(i)+(lambda(2,3)*(d_t/2)) );
C(3,3) = k2*( ES(i)+(lambda(2,3)*(d_t/2)) );
C(4,3) = k_2*( E(i)+(lambda(2,2)*(d_t/2)) )*( P(i)+(lambda(2,4)*(d_t/2)) );
% array of the third level of lambda constants
lambda(3,1:4) = (A*C(1:4,3))';
C(1,4) = k1*( E(i)+(lambda(3,2)*d_t) )*( S(i)+(lambda(3,1)*d_t) );
```

```

C(2,4) = k_1*( ES(i)+(lambda(3,3)*d_t ));
C(3,4) = k2*( ES(i)+(lambda(3,3)*d_t ));
C(4,4) = k_2*( E(i)+(lambda(3,2)*d_t ))*( P(i)+(lambda(3,4)*d_t ) );
% array of the fourth level of lambda constants
lambda(4,1:4) = (A*C(1:4,4))';
% array of the concentrations for the following step
S(i+1) = S(i) + ( lambda(1,1)+2*lambda(2,1)+2*lambda(3,1)+lambda(4,1) )*(d_t/6);
E(i+1) = E(i) + ( lambda(1,2)+2*lambda(2,2)+2*lambda(3,2)+lambda(4,2) )*(d_t/6);
ES(i+1) = ES(i) + ( lambda(1,3)+2*lambda(2,3)+2*lambda(3,3)+lambda(4,3) )*(d_t/6);
P(i+1) = P(i) + ( lambda(1,4)+2*lambda(2,4)+2*lambda(3,4)+lambda(4,4) )*(d_t/6);
rate(i+1) = k2*ES(i+1)-k_2*E(i+1)*P(i+1);
t(i+1) = t(i) + d_t;
i = i+1;
i_M = i;
endwhile
i_M
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:100:i_M), S(1:100:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:100:i_M), P(1:100:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:100:i_M), ES(1:100:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot (t(1:100:i_M), E(1:100:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 1)
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('Concentration (mM)');
legend('D-ribulose 5-phosphate (mM)', 'D-xylulose 5-phosphate (mM)', 'RPE-Ru5P', 'free RPE');
figure(2)
plot (t(1:100:i_M), rate(1:100:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('rate (mM/s)');

```


Figure 16. Concentrations and rate, in function of time.

3.4.2 Irreversible reactions

We have already noted that the full system in Eq. 110 can't be solved in the case of an irreversible enzymatic reaction, and this is due to the fact that k_{-1} is usually not available as an experimental measure. But we can still solve the Michaelis-Menten equation in Eq. 39 with the Runge-Kutta method. Let's consider the Cauchy problem in Eq. 161; given Eq. 130 we have

$$\text{Eq. 135} \quad [S]_{i+1} = [S]_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t$$

$$\text{Eq. 136} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1^{(i)} = -k_{cat} \frac{[S]_i}{K_M + [S]_i} [E]_T \\ \lambda_2^{(i)} = -k_{cat} \frac{[S]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_M + [S]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}} [E]_T \\ \lambda_3^{(i)} = -k_{cat} \frac{[S]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_M + [S]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}} [E]_T \\ \lambda_4^{(i)} = -k_{cat} \frac{[S]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t}{K_M + [S]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t} [E]_T \end{cases}$$

We can couple this system with the last three equations in Eq. 171:

$$\text{Eq. 137} \quad \begin{cases} [P]_i = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [S]_i \\ [ES]_i = \frac{[S]_i}{K_M + [S]_i} [E]_T \\ [E]_i = \frac{K_M}{K_M + [S]_i} [E]_T \end{cases}$$

3.4.2.1 Tryptophan metabolism (IDO-2)

CODE 8. We will now use the Runge-Kutta method for the reaction in Eq. 40, using the same kinetic parameters used in paragraph 2.2.1 and the concentrations indicated in Eq. 173. The output of this code can be found in Figure 17.

```
% file name = Runge_Kutta_irreversible
% date of creation = 20/08/2019
clear all
k_cat = 0.103 % catalytic constant (1/s)
K_M = 6809.0 % Michaelis constant (micro M)
E_T = 8.0 % enzyme concentration (micro M)
v_M = k_cat * E_T % maximum rate
S(1) = 400. % initial substrate concentration (micro M)
E(1) = E_T
ES(1) = 0.
P(1) = 0. % initial product concentration (micro M)
t(1) = 0. % time zero
d_t = 0.1 % increase in time
% arrays
i = 1;
while (S(i) > 1)
    lambda(1) = -v_M * S(i) / (K_M + S(i));
    lambda(2) = -v_M * (S(i) + (lambda(1) * d_t / 2)) / (K_M + S(i) + (lambda(1) * d_t / 2));
    lambda(3) = -v_M * (S(i) + (lambda(2) * d_t / 2)) / (K_M + S(i) + (lambda(2) * d_t / 2));
```

```

lambda(4) = -v_M*( S(i) + ( lambda(3)*d_t ) )/(K_M + S(i) + ( lambda(3)*d_t ) );
S(i+1) = S(i)+ ( lambda(1) + 2*lambda(2) + 2*lambda(3) + lambda(4) )*d_t/6;
P(i+1) = P(1) + S(1) - S(i+1);
ES(i+1) = S(i+1)*E_T/( K_M + S(i+1) );
E(i+1) = K_M*E_T/( K_M + S(i+1) );
t(i+1) = t(i) + d_t;
i = i+1;
endwhile
i_M = i
% rate
for i=1:1:i_M
    v(i) = k_cat*ES(i);
endfor
% Michaelis-Menten equation
% rate
for i=1:1:i_M
    v_MM(i) = k_cat*S(i)*E_T/( K_M + S(i) );           % micro M/s
endfor
d = int32(i_M/1000);
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:d:i_M), S(1:d:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:d:i_M), P(1:d:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:d:i_M), ES(1:d:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:d:i_M), E(1:d:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('Concentration ({}\mu}M)');
legend('L-tryptophan', 'N-formylkynurenin', 'IDO2-LTry', 'free IDO-2');
figure(2)
plot (S(1:d:i_M), v(1:d:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan ({}\mu} M)');
ylabel('Rate ({}\mu}M/s)');
legend('Numerical solution');
figure(3)
plot (S(1:d:i_M), v_MM(1:d:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan ({}\mu} M)');
ylabel('Rate ({}\mu}M/s)');
legend('Michelis-Menten equation');
figure(4)
semilogx(S(1:d:i_M), v_MM(1:d:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan ({}\mu} M)');
ylabel('Rate ({}\mu}M/s)');
legend('Michelis-Menten equation');

```


Figure 17. The plot of the concentrations of S, P, ES and E for the transformation of L-tryptophan into N-formylkynurenine by IDO-2.

3.4.3 Reversible reactions with a competitive inhibitor

In order to describe the evolution in time of the reaction in paragraph 2.4.1.2, we can use the Michaelis-Menten equation in Eq. 70 combined with the relationship $[S] = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P]$. So, we have

$$\text{Eq. 138} \quad \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \frac{v_M}{K_M^S} = \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_{eq}}\right)[P]}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}\right)[P]} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S}$$

In order to find the other concentrations, we can use Eq. 67, Eq. 65 and Eq. 66:

Figure 18. Transport of extracellular L-Tryptophan (left) inside a serotonergic neuron of the midbrain. Cytosolic concentration on the right.

$$\text{Eq. 139} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [S] = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P] \\ [ES] = \frac{[E_T]}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \left(\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P} \right) \\ [E] = \frac{[ES]}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \\ [EI] = \frac{1}{\frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \frac{[ES][I]}{K_I} \end{array} \right.$$

Now, what is the expression of the Runge-Kutta method for the ODE in Eq. 138? We have to adjust Eq. 130 to this case. We have:

$$\text{Eq. 140} \quad [P]_{i+1} = [P]_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t$$

$$\text{Eq. 141} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_1^{(i)} = \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_{eq}}\right) [P]_i}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}\right) [P]_i} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} \\ \lambda_2^{(i)} = \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_{eq}}\right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}\right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} \\ \lambda_3^{(i)} = \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_{eq}}\right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}\right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} \\ \lambda_4^{(i)} = \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_{eq}}\right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t\right)}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}\right) \left([P]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t\right)} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} \end{array} \right.$$

3.4.3.1 Tryptophan transport (LAT1)

This is the case introduced in paragraph 2.4.1.3. In this case, we have

$$\text{Eq. 142} \quad [S] = [T_{ECS}], [P] = [T_{Cyt}], [I] = [A], K_I = K_A, K_M^S = K_M^{T_{ECS}}, K_M^P = K_M^{T_{Cyt}}$$

with the experimental data given in Eq. 72, Eq. 73. For the initial conditions we can set:

$$\text{Eq. 143} \quad [T_{ECS}]_0 = 1.5 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}, [T_{Cyt}]_0 = 10^5 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

Moreover, we have to calculate $[LAT1]_0$, since it is not given by the data. The problem here is that in order to do that we should have the value of k_2 (because $[LAT1]_0 = v_M^f/k_2$), but it can't be calculated from $K_M^{T_{ECS}}, K_M^{T_{Cyt}}, K_{eq}$. In fact, the system in Eq. 112 is a system of three equations in four unknowns (k_1, k_{-1}, k_2, k_{-2}). Then, in this case, we will run the simulation only for $[T_{ECS}]$ and $[T_{Cyt}]$. One point to be made here is what happens to the level of $[T_{ECS}]$: is it depleted or not?

CODE 9. In our first simulation, we will assume that $[T_{ECS}]$ can change because of the transport. In this case, we can use directly Eq. 129 and Eq. 130. The code is the following one and the diagrams for $[T_{ECS}]$ and $[T_{Cyt}]$ are in Figure 18.

```

% file name = Runge_Kutta_reversible_inhibition_competitive
% date of creation = 26/08/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M_S = 2.2*(10^10) % molecules/cell
K_M_P = 2.2*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_I = 4.3*(10^3) % molecules/cell
K_eq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*60*(10^8) % molecules/(hour*cell)
I = 5*(10^6) % molecules/cell
% initial conditions
i = 1
P(i)= 10^9 % molecules/cell
S(i)= 1.5*(10^9) % molecules/cell
t(i) = 0. % time zero
num = ( P(1) + S(1) - ( 1 + (1/K_eq) ) *P(i) ) *V_M_F;
den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + ( ( P(1) + S(1) ) /K_M_S ) + ( (1/K_M_P) - (1/K_M_S) ) *P(i) ) *K_M_S;
rate (i) = num/den;
d_t = 1. % increase in time
% arrays
i = 1;
while ( abs( rate(i) ) > 0.1 )
    num = ( P(1) + S(1) - ( 1 + (1/K_eq) ) *P(i) ) *V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + ( ( P(1) + S(1) ) /K_M_S ) + ( (1/K_M_P) - (1/K_M_S) ) *P(i) ) *K_M_S;
    lambda(1) = num/den;
    num = ( P(1) + S(1) - ( 1 + (1/K_eq) ) * ( P(i) + lambda(1)*d_t/2 ) ) *V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + ( ( P(1) + S(1) ) /K_M_S ) + ( (1/K_M_P) - (1/K_M_S) ) * \
    ( P(i) + lambda(1)*d_t/2 ) ) *K_M_S;
    lambda(2) = num/den;
    num = ( P(1) + S(1) - ( 1 + (1/K_eq) ) * ( P(i) + lambda(2)*d_t/2 ) ) *V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + ( ( P(1) + S(1) ) /K_M_S ) + ( (1/K_M_P) - (1/K_M_S) ) * \
    ( P(i) + lambda(2)*d_t/2 ) ) *K_M_S;
    lambda(3) = num/den;
    num = ( P(1) + S(1) - ( 1 + (1/K_eq) ) * ( P(i) + lambda(3)*d_t ) ) *V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + ( ( P(1) + S(1) ) /K_M_S ) + ( (1/K_M_P) - (1/K_M_S) ) * \
    ( P(i) + lambda(3)*d_t ) ) *K_M_S;
    lambda(4) = num/den;
    P(i+1) = P(i) + ( lambda(1) + 2*lambda(2) + 2*lambda(3) + lambda(4) ) *d_t/6;
    S(i+1) = P(1) + S(1) - P(i+1);
    rate (i+1) = lambda (1);
    t(i+1) = t(i) + d_t;
    i = i+1;
endwhile
i_M = i
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:i_M), S(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (hours)');
ylabel('L-tryptophan in extracellular space (molecules/cell)');
figure(2)
plot (t(1:i_M), P(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (hours)');
ylabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');

```


Figure 19. The transport rate of extracellular L-Tryptophan (right) inside a serotonergic neuron of the midbrain. The cytosolic concentration of L-Tryptophan is on the left.

CODE 10. If we assume now that $[T_{ECS}]$ is constant, then we have to integrate Eq. 70 where we regard $[S]$ as a constant. So, the Runge-Kutta method in this case becomes:

$$\text{Eq. 144} \quad [P]_{i+1} = [P]_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t$$

$$\lambda_1^{(i)} = \frac{[S]_0 - \frac{[P]_i}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]_i}{K_M^P}} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S}$$

$$\lambda_2^{(i)} = \frac{[S]_0 - \frac{([P]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2})}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M^S} + \frac{([P]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2})}{K_M^P}} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S}$$

$$\lambda_3^{(i)} = \frac{[S]_0 - \frac{([P]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2})}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M^S} + \frac{([P]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2})}{K_M^P}} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S}$$

$$\lambda_4^{(i)} = \frac{[S]_0 - \frac{([P]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t)}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M^S} + \frac{([P]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t)}{K_M^P}} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S}$$

The following code gives the diagrams in Figure 19, where both the concentration of L-tryptophan in cytosol and transport rate into the cytosol in function of time are reported.

```
% file name = Runge_Kutta_reversible_inhibition_competitive_2
% date of creation = 26/08/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M_S = 2.2*(10^10) % molecules/cell
K_M_P = 2.2*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_I = 4.3*(10^3) % molecules/cell
K_eq = 3.43
```

```

V_M_F = 1.2*60*(10^8) % molecules/(hour*cell)
I = 5*(10^6) % molecules/cell
S = 1.5*(10^9) % molecules/cell
% initial conditions
i = 1
P(i)= 10^9 % molecules/cell
t(i) = 0. % time zero
num = ( S - (P(i)/K_eq) )*V_M_F;
den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + (S/K_M_S) + (P(i)/K_M_P) )*K_M_S;
rate (i) = num/den;
d_t = 1. % increase in time
% arrays
i = 1;
while ( abs( rate(i) )>0.1 )
    num = ( S - (P(i)/K_eq) )*V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + (S/K_M_S) + (P(i)/K_M_P) )*K_M_S;
    lambda(1) = num/den;
    num = ( S - ( ( P(i) + (lambda(1)*d_t/2) )/K_eq ) )*V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + (S/K_M_S) + ( ( P(i) + (lambda(1)*d_t/2) )/K_M_P) )*K_M_S;
    lambda(2) = num/den;
    num = ( S - ( ( P(i) + (lambda(2)*d_t/2) )/K_eq ) )*V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + (S/K_M_S) + ( ( P(i) + (lambda(2)*d_t/2) )/K_M_P) )*K_M_S;
    lambda(3) = num/den;
    num = ( S - ( ( P(i) + (lambda(3)*d_t) )/K_eq ) )*V_M_F;
    den = ( 1 + (I/K_I) + (S/K_M_S) + ( ( P(i) + (lambda(3)*d_t) )/K_M_P) )*K_M_S;
    lambda(4) = num/den;
    P(i+1) = P(i) + ( lambda(1) + 2*lambda(2) + 2*lambda(3) + lambda(4) )*d_t/6;
    S(i+1) = P(1) + S(1) - P(i+1);
    rate (i+1) = lambda (1);
    t(i+1) = t(i) + d_t;
    i = i+1;
endwhile
i_M = i
% plots
figure (1)
plot (t(1:i_M), P(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (hours)');
ylabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
figure (2)
plot (t(1:i_M), rate(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
ylabel('transport into cytosol (molecules/cell*hour)');
xlabel('time (hours)');

```

3.4.4 Irreversible reactions with substrate inhibition

We consider here the case discussed in paragraph 2.4.3.3 in which the substrate is an uncompetitive inhibitor that binds the complex EI. Eq. 84 becomes

$$\text{Eq. 145} \quad \frac{d[S]}{dt} = - \frac{k_2[E_T][S]}{\left(\frac{[S]}{K_I} + 1\right)[S] + K_M} = - \frac{v_M[S]}{\left(\frac{[S]}{K_I} + 1\right)[S] + K_M}$$

Runge-Kutta method (Eq. 130) for Eq. 84 is as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 146} \quad [S]_{i+1} = [S]_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t$$

$$\lambda_1^{(i)} = -\frac{v_M [S]_i}{\left(\frac{[S]_i}{K_I'} + 1\right) [S]_i + K_M}$$

$$\lambda_2^{(i)} = -\frac{v_M \left([S]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{\left(\frac{[S]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_I'} + 1\right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) + K_M}$$

$$\lambda_3^{(i)} = -\frac{v_M \left([S]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{\left(\frac{[S]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_I'} + 1\right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) + K_M}$$

$$\lambda_4^{(i)} = -\frac{v_M \left([S]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t\right)}{\left(\frac{[S]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t}{K_I'} + 1\right) \left([S]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t\right) + K_M}$$

We can then derive the other concentrations considering Eq. 75, Eq. 77, Eq. 78:

$$\text{Eq. 147} \quad [ES] = \frac{[E_T][S]}{\left(\frac{[S]}{K_I'} + 1\right) [S] + K_M}, \quad [ES_2] = \frac{[ES][S]}{K_I'}, \quad [E] = K_M \frac{[ES]}{[S]}$$

$$\text{Eq. 148} \quad [P]_i = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [S]_i$$

Figure 20. *L*-Tryptophan (left) is converted into *N* formylkynurenine (right) by *IDO1*.

3.4.4.1 Tryptophan metabolism (IDO-1)

CODE 11. Let's now integrate the MM equation for the case in paragraph 2.4.3.4 with the experimental data in Eq. 86. Moreover, we consider the following initial concentrations:

$$\text{Eq. 149} \quad \begin{cases} [P]_0 = 10^5 \frac{\text{molecules } N\text{-formylkynurenine}}{\text{cell}} \\ [S]_0 = 9 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{molecules } L\text{-tryptophan}}{\text{cell}} \end{cases}$$

Diagrams by the following code are collected in Figure 20.

```

% file name = Runge_Kutta_irreversible_substrate_inhibition
% date of creation = 26/08/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M = 3.4*(10^7) % molecules L-T/cell
K_I = 2.5*(10^8) % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84 % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208 % molecules IDO1/cell
V_M = k_2*IDO1
% initial conditions
i = 1
P(i)= 10^5 % molecules/cell
S(i)= 9*(10^6) % molecules/cell
t(i) = 0. % time zero
num = S(i)*V_M;
den = K_M + ( 1+( S(i)/K_I ) )*S(i) ;
rate (i) = -1*num/den;
d_t = 1. % increase in time
% arrays
while ( abs( rate(i) )>1 )
    num = S(i)*V_M;
    den = K_M + ( 1+( S(i)/K_I ) )*S(i);
    lambda(1) = -1*num/den;
    num = ( S(i)+ (lambda(1)*d_t/2) )*V_M;
    den = K_M + ( 1+( ( S(i)+ (lambda(1)*d_t/2) )/K_I ) )*( S(i)+ (lambda(1)*d_t/2) );
    lambda(2) = -1*num/den;
    num = ( S(i)+ (lambda(2)*d_t/2) )*V_M;
    den = K_M + ( 1+( ( S(i)+ (lambda(2)*d_t/2) )/K_I ) )*( S(i)+ (lambda(2)*d_t/2) );
    lambda(3) = -1*num/den;
    num = ( S(i)+ (lambda(3)*d_t) )*V_M;
    den = K_M + ( 1+( ( S(i)+ (lambda(3)*d_t) )/K_I ) )*( S(i)+ (lambda(3)*d_t) );
    lambda(4) = -1*num/den;
    S(i+1) = S(i)+ ( lambda(1) + 2*lambda(2) + 2*lambda(3) + lambda(4) )*d_t/6;
    P(i+1) = P(1) + S(1) - S(i+1);
    rate (i+1) = lambda (1);
    t(i+1) = t(i) + d_t;
    i = i+1;
endwhile
i_M = i
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:i_M), S(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (hours)');
ylabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
figure(2)
plot (t(1:i_M), P(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (hours)');
ylabel('N-formylkynurenine in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
figure(3)
plot (S(1:i_M), rate(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate of conversion (molecules/cell)');

```

3.4.5 Tryptophan metabolism, IDO1 and LAT1

We will now study the first example of a simple metabolic pathway made up by LAT1 and IDO1. We have the following two ODEs, respectively:

$$\text{Eq. 150} \quad \frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{[T_{ECS}]K_{eq}}\right) \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}}$$

$$\text{Eq. 151} \quad \frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = - \frac{k_2[IDO1][T_{cyt}]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^{Trp}} + 1\right)[T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp}}$$

3.4.5.1 Michaelis-Menten-like equation

The first one represents the flux of L-tryptophan inside the cell and it is considered positive when the amino acid enters the cell. The second one is the rate of conversion of L-tryptophan into N-formylkynurenine: it is negative when there is the conversion of the substrate into the product. Thus, the change of the concentration of L-tryptophan in the cytosol with respect of time is

$$\text{Eq. 152} \quad \frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{[T_{ECS}]K_{eq}}\right) \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}} - \frac{k_2[IDO1][T_{cyt}]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^{Trp}} + 1\right)[T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp}}$$

Figure 21. Michaelis-Menten-like diagram for the LAT1-IDO1 system. The detail on the right for the lowest values of L-tryptophan concentration where there is the first state of equilibrium.

CODE 12. Eq. 152 is a Michaelis-Menten-like equation for this two-step reaction; its diagram is plotted by the following code and is represented in Figure 21 and Figure 22.

Figure 22. Michaelis-Menten-like diagram for the LAT1-IDO1 system. Detail of the second state of equilibrium.

Figure 23. Michaelis-Menten-like diagram for the LAT1-IDO1 system with a logarithmic scale for the x-axis.

More conveniently, we can plot the same diagram in a semi-logarithmic scale (Figure 23) so to have all the three steady state in the same diagram.

```
% file name = Metabolic_trap_MM
% date of creation = 27/08/2019
clear all
% experiential parameters
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10)           % molecules/cell
K_M_Tcyt = 2.2*(10^9)           % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3)                % molecules/cell
Keq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8)              % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6)                    % molecules/cell
```

```

TECS = 1.5*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_M_Trp = 3.4*(10^7) % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8) % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84 % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208 % molecules IDO1/cell
n = 10001 % nodes
n_2 = 100
n_3 = 1000
Tcyt(1)= 10^6; % molecules/cell
Tcyt(n) = 5*10^9; % molecules/cell
d_Tcyt = (Tcyt(n)-Tcyt(1))/(n-1);
% we build the array for Tcyt
for i=2:1:n
    Tcyt(i) = Tcyt(i-1) + d_Tcyt;
endfor
% we build the array for rate
for i=1:1:n
    num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - (Tcyt(i)/(TECS*Keq)) ) * TECS / K_M_TECS;
    den_1 = ( 1 + ( A / K_A ) + ( TECS / K_M_TECS ) + ( Tcyt(i) / K_M_Tcyt ) );
    num_2 = k_2 * IDO1 * Tcyt(i);
    den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1 + ( Tcyt(i) / K_I_Trp ) ) * Tcyt(i);
    rate_1 (i) = num_1 / den_1;
    rate_2 (i) = num_2 / den_2;
    rate (i) = (num_1 / den_1) - (num_2 / den_2);
    if (abs(rate(i)) < 50)
        i, Tcyt(i), rate (i)
    endif
endfor
figure (1)
plot (Tcyt(1:100:n), rate(1:100:n), 'k', 'Linewidth', 2);
hold on
plot (Tcyt(1:100:n), rate_1(1:100:n), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2);
hold on
plot (Tcyt(1:100:n), rate_2(1:100:n), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate (molecules/cell)');
legend ('total rate', 'flux of L-Tryp. into cytosol', 'rate of conversion by IDO1')
figure (2)
plot (Tcyt(1:n_2), rate(1:n_2), 'k', 'Linewidth', 2);
hold on
plot (Tcyt(1:n_2), rate_1(1:n_2), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2);
hold on
plot (Tcyt(1:n_2), rate_2(1:n_2), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate (molecules/cell)');
legend ('total rate', 'flux of L-Tryp. into cytosol', 'rate of conversion by IDO1')
figure (3)
plot (Tcyt(n_2:n_3), rate(n_2:n_3), 'k', 'Linewidth', 2);
hold on
plot (Tcyt(n_2:n_3), rate_1(n_2:n_3), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2);
hold on
plot (Tcyt(n_2:n_3), rate_2(n_2:n_3), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate (molecules/cell)');

```

3.4.5.2 Equilibrium states

As you can see from Figure 21, we have three states of equilibrium (the concentrations of L-Tryp in which the rate is naught):

$$\text{Eq. 153} \quad \begin{cases} \text{equilibrium state A: } [T_{cyt}] \sim 2.5 \cdot 10^7 \leftarrow \text{stable} \\ \text{equilibrium state B: } [T_{cyt}] \sim 4.0 \cdot 10^8 \leftarrow \text{unstable} \\ \text{equilibrium state C: } [T_{cyt}] \sim 4.5 \cdot 10^9 \leftarrow \text{stable} \end{cases}$$

Equilibrium state A is stable because if we deplete the concentration of L-tryptophan in the cytosol, the rate is positive (Figure 21, right), so $[T_{cyt}]$ increases again. On the other hand, if we increase $[T_{cyt}]$, then the rate is negative, so the system comes back to the equilibrium state. This is true for state C too. State B is unstable, because if we decrease $[T_{cyt}]$, then it decreases further, while if we increase it, it increases further; in both cases, the system moves away from its equilibrium, either towards state A or towards state C. Thus, the phase space (DEF. 24) for this system is the following one:

Equilibrium states for the LAT1-IDO1 system are the solutions of the equation $\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = 0$. We try now to calculate them analytically. We have:

$$\begin{aligned} v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{[T_{ECS}]K_{eq}} \right) \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^{Trp}} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp} \right) &= k_2 [IDO1] [T_{cyt}] \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \left(1 - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{[T_{ECS}]K_{eq}} \right) \left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^{Trp}} + [T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp} \right) &= \frac{k_2 K_M^{T_{ECS}} [IDO1]}{v_M^f [T_{ECS}]} [T_{cyt}] \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow -\frac{[T_{cyt}]^3}{K_I^{Trp} [T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} + \left(\frac{1}{K_I^{Trp}} - \frac{1}{[T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} \right) [T_{cyt}]^2 - \left(\frac{K_M^{Trp}}{[T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp} &= \\ = \frac{k_2 K_M^{T_{ECS}} [IDO1]}{v_M^f [T_{ECS}]} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \right) [T_{cyt}] + \frac{k_2 K_M^{T_{ECS}} [IDO1]}{v_M^f [T_{ECS}] K_M^{T_{cyt}}} [T_{cyt}]^2 &\Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow -\frac{[T_{cyt}]^3}{K_I^{Trp} [T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} + \left(\frac{1}{K_I^{Trp}} - \frac{1}{[T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} - \frac{k_2 K_M^{T_{ECS}} [IDO1]}{v_M^f [T_{ECS}] K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right) [T_{cyt}]^2 - & \\ - \left(\frac{K_M^{Trp}}{[T_{ECS}] K_{eq}} + 1 + \frac{k_2 K_M^{T_{ECS}} [IDO1]}{v_M^f [T_{ECS}]} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \right) \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

3.4.5.3 Numerical method

The Runge-Kutta method for this equation is the following one:

$$\text{Eq. 154} \quad [T_{\text{cyt}}]_{i+1} = [T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t$$

$$\lambda_1^{(i)} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i}{[T_{\text{ECS}}] K_{\text{eq}}} \right) \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}} + \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i}{K_M^{T_{\text{cyt}}}}} - \frac{k_2 [IDO1] [T_{\text{cyt}}]_i}{\left(\frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_{i+1}}{K_I^{T_{\text{Trp}}}} \right) [T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + K_M^{T_{\text{Trp}}}}$$

$$\lambda_2^{(i)} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{[T_{\text{ECS}}] K_{\text{eq}}} \right) \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}} + \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_M^{T_{\text{cyt}}}}} - \frac{k_2 [IDO1] \left([T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right)}{\left(\frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_I^{T_{\text{Trp}}}} + 1 \right) \left([T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + K_M^{T_{\text{Trp}}}}$$

$$\lambda_3^{(i)} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{[T_{\text{ECS}}] K_{\text{eq}}} \right) \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}} + \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_M^{T_{\text{cyt}}}}} - \frac{k_2 [IDO1] \left([T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right)}{\left(\frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}}{K_I^{T_{\text{Trp}}}} + 1 \right) \left([T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \right) + K_M^{T_{\text{Trp}}}}$$

$$\lambda_4^{(i)} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t}{[T_{\text{ECS}}] K_{\text{eq}}} \right) \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{\text{ECS}}]}{K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}}} + \frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t}{K_M^{T_{\text{cyt}}}}} - \frac{k_2 [IDO1] \left([T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t \right)}{\left(\frac{[T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t}{K_I^{T_{\text{Trp}}}} + 1 \right) \left([T_{\text{cyt}}]_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t \right) + K_M^{T_{\text{Trp}}}}$$

We use the following experimental measures:

$$\text{Eq. 155} \quad [A] = 5 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \quad K_M^{T_{\text{ECS}}} = 2.2 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \quad K_{\text{eq}} = 3.43$$

$$K_A = 4.3 \cdot 10^3 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \quad K_M^{T_{\text{cyt}}} = 2.2 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \quad v_M^f = 1.2 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{min} \cdot \text{cell}}$$

$$\text{Eq. 156} \quad [T_{\text{ECS}}]_0 = 1.5 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}, \quad [T_{\text{cyt}}]_0 = ?$$

$$\text{Eq. 157} \quad k_2 = 84 \frac{\text{molecules} \cdot \text{Try}}{\text{min} \cdot \text{cell} \cdot \frac{\text{molecules} \cdot \text{DO}-1}{\text{cell}}} \quad [IDO_1] = 208 \frac{\text{molecules} \cdot \text{DO}-1}{\text{cell}}$$

$$K_M^{T_{\text{Trp}}} = 3.4 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules} \cdot \text{Try}}{\text{cell}} \quad K_I^{T_{\text{Trp}}} = 2.5 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules} \cdot \text{Try}}{\text{cell}}$$

CODE 13. The following lines implement the numerical method above. The evolution in time of this system depends on the initial value of $[T_{\text{cyt}}]$. We will run several cases in the following paragraphs.

```
% file name = Metabolic_trap
% date of creation = 27/08/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10) % molecules/cell
```

```

K_M_Tcyt = 2.2*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3) % molecules/cell
Keq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8) % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6) % molecules/cell
TECS = 1.5*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_M_Trp = 3.4*(10^7) % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8) % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84 % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208 % molecules IDO1/cell
% initial conditions
i = 1
Tcyt(i)= 10^6 % molecules/cell
t(i) = 0. % time zero
num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - (Tcyt(i)/(TECS*Keq)) ) *TECS/K_M_TECS;
den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS/K_M_TECS ) + ( Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt ) );
num_2 = k_2*IDO1*Tcyt(i);
den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( Tcyt(i)/K_I_Trp ) ) *Tcyt(i);
rate (i) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);
d_t = 1. % increase in time
% arrays
while ( abs( rate(i) )>1 )
    num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - (Tcyt(i)/(TECS*Keq)) ) *TECS/K_M_TECS;
    den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS/K_M_TECS ) + ( Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt ) );
    num_2 = k_2*IDO1*Tcyt(i);
    den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( Tcyt(i)/K_I_Trp ) ) *Tcyt(i);
    lambda(1) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);

    num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - ( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(1)*d_t/2))/(TECS*Keq)) ) *TECS/K_M_TECS;
    den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS/K_M_TECS ) + ( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(1)*d_t/2))/K_M_Tcyt ) );
    num_2 = k_2*IDO1*(Tcyt(i)+(lambda(1)*d_t/2));
    den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(1)*d_t/2))/K_I_Trp ) ) *(Tcyt(i)+(lambda(1)*d_t/2));
    lambda(2) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);

    num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - ( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(2)*d_t/2))/(TECS*Keq)) ) *TECS/K_M_TECS;
    den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS/K_M_TECS ) + ( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(2)*d_t/2))/K_M_Tcyt ) );
    num_2 = k_2*IDO1*(Tcyt(i)+(lambda(2)*d_t/2));
    den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(2)*d_t/2))/K_I_Trp ) ) *(Tcyt(i)+(lambda(2)*d_t/2));
    lambda(3) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);

    num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - ( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(3)*d_t)/(TECS*Keq)) ) *TECS/K_M_TECS;
    den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS/K_M_TECS ) + ( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(3)*d_t)/K_M_Tcyt ) );
    num_2 = k_2*IDO1*(Tcyt(i)+(lambda(3)*d_t));
    den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( (Tcyt(i)+(lambda(3)*d_t)/K_I_Trp ) ) *(Tcyt(i)+(lambda(3)*d_t));
    lambda(4) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);

    Tcyt(i+1) = Tcyt(i)+ ( lambda(1) + 2*lambda(2) + 2*lambda(3) + lambda(4) ) *d_t/6;
    rate (i+1) = lambda (1);
    t(i+1) = t(i) + d_t;
    i = i+1;
endwhile
i_M = i
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:i_M), Tcyt(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('time (hours)');

```

```

ylabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
figure(2)
plot (Tcyt(1:i_M), rate(1:i_M), 'k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan in cytosol (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('rate (molecules/cell)');

```

3.4.5.4 Evolution in time towards state A

If we start with a concentration of L-tryptophan in cytosol below the value in state A, we would expect an evolution towards state A. If we set

$$\text{Eq. 158} \quad [T_{Cyt}]_0 = 10^5 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

we have the diagram in Figure 24 and you can see that the prediction is in fact correct. If we start with a concentration of cytosolic L-Tryptophan that is between state A and state B, we should move again towards state A. Let's consider the initial concentration:

$$\text{Eq. 159} \quad [T_{Cyt}]_0 = 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

Then we have again an evolution towards state A (Figure 25).

Figure 24. Evolution towards state A from lower values of cytosolic L-tryptophan.

Figure 25. Evolution towards state A from higher values of cytosolic L-tryptophan.

3.4.5.5 Evolution in time towards state C

Let's consider

$$\text{Eq. 160} \quad [T_{\text{Cyt}}]_0 = 8 \cdot 10^5 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}},$$

4 Semi-analytical solutions

4.1 Irreversible reactions

Since $\frac{d[P]}{dt} = -\frac{d[S]}{dt}$, the equation for the irreversible enzymatic reaction (Eq. 39) can be written

$$\text{Eq. 161} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{d[S]}{dt} = -k_{cat} \frac{[S]}{K_M + [S]} [E]_T \\ [S](t=0) = [S]_0 \end{cases}$$

This equation can be integrated by separation of variables:

$$\frac{K_M + [S]}{[S]} d[S] = -k_{cat} [E]_T dt \Rightarrow \int_{[S]_0}^{[S]} \frac{K_M + y}{y} dy = -k_{cat} [E]_T \int_{t_0=0}^t d\tau$$

For the integral in the first term of the equation on the right we have

$$K_M \int_{[S]_0}^{[S]} \frac{dy}{y} + \int_{[S]_0}^{[S]} dy = K_M \ln \frac{[S]}{[S]_0} + [S] - [S]_0$$

So we have found the solution to the Cauchy problem in Eq. 161:

$$\text{Eq. 162} \quad [S] = [S]_0 - K_M \ln \frac{[S]}{[S]_0} - v_M t$$

Now, this is a transcendental equation in $[S]$ and this can be solved numerically, with Newton's method (see paragraph 4.1.2). But it would be useful to have an analytical expression for $[S]$ because it would allow us to completely solve the system in Eq. 28 in an analytical way. For that purpose, let's write Eq. 162 in another way:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[S]}{K_M} &= \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} - \ln[S] + \ln[S]_0 - \frac{v_M t}{K_M} \Leftrightarrow \frac{[S]}{K_M} = \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} - \ln[S] + \ln K_M + \ln[S]_0 - \ln K_M - \frac{v_M t}{K_M} \Leftrightarrow \\ &\Leftrightarrow \frac{[S]}{K_M} + \ln \frac{[S]}{K_M} = \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} + \ln \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} - \frac{v_M t}{K_M} \Leftrightarrow \frac{[S]}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]}{K_M}} = \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0 - t}{K_M}} \end{aligned}$$

Let's consider now the following substitution:

$$x(t) = \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0 - t}{K_M}} \Leftrightarrow t = [S]_0 - K_M \ln \left(\frac{K_M}{[S]_0} x(t) \right)$$

Then with the following notation

$$\text{Eq. 163} \quad \begin{cases} W(x) = \frac{[S]}{K_M} \\ x(t) = \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0 - t}{K_M}} \end{cases}$$

we can write Eq. 163 in the following form:

$$\text{Eq. 164} \quad W(x)e^{W(x)} = x$$

The function $W(x)$ that solves this functional equation is called *Lambert function* or also *Omega function* and there are several approximate expressions for it. A simple one is an approximation by Winitzki (which gives an error less than 10^{-2}):

$$\text{Eq. 165} \quad W(x) \cong \ln(1+x) \left\{ 1 - \frac{\ln[1+\ln(1+x)]}{2+\ln(1+x)} \right\}, \quad \forall x > 0$$

So we have found:

$$\text{Eq. 166} \quad [S] = K_{MW} \left(\frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0-t}{K_M}} \right)$$

And using Winitzki's approximation we have:

$$\text{Eq. 167} \quad [S] \cong K_M \ln \left(1 + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0-t}{K_M}} \right) \left\{ 1 - \frac{\ln \left[1 + \ln \left(1 + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0-t}{K_M}} \right) \right]}{2 + \ln \left(1 + \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{\frac{[S]_0-t}{K_M}} \right)} \right\}$$

For what concerns $[P]$, we recognize that

$$\frac{d[P]}{dt} = -\frac{d[S]}{dt} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} [P] = -[S] + C \\ [P]_0 = -[S]_0 + C \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} [P] = -[S] + C \\ [P]_0 + [S]_0 = C \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Eq. 168} \quad [P] = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [S]$$

Then, from the fourth equation in Eq. 28 we have

$$\text{Eq. 169} \quad [ES] = \frac{1}{k_2} \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{k_{cat}}{k_2} \frac{[S]}{K_M + [S]} [E]_T = \frac{[S]}{K_M + [S]} [E]_T$$

where we have considered that $k_{cat} = k_2$. We can then easily calculate $[E]$:

$$\text{Eq. 170} \quad [E] = [E]_T - [ES] = \frac{K_M}{K_M + [S]} [E]_T$$

So, we can conclude that the semi-analytical solution of the system of ODEs associated with the general irreversible enzymatic reaction (Eq. 28) is:

$$\text{Eq. 171} \quad \begin{cases} [S] = K_M \ln(1+x(t)) \left\{ 1 - \frac{\ln[1+\ln(1+x(t))]}{2+\ln(1+x(t))} \right\} \\ [P] = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [S] \\ [ES] = \frac{[S]}{K_M + [S]} [E]_T \\ [E] = \frac{K_M}{K_M + [S]} [E]_T \end{cases}$$

assuming that

$$\text{Eq. 172} \quad x(t) = \frac{[S]_0}{K_M} e^{-\frac{[S]_0 t}{K_M}}$$

4.1.1 Tryptophan metabolism (IDO-2)

We will now use the semi-analytical solution in Eq. 171 for the reaction in Eq. 40, using the same kinetic parameters used in paragraph 2.2.1 and the concentrations indicated below:

$$\text{Eq. 173} \quad \begin{aligned} k_{cat} &= 0.103 \mu M s^{-1}, & [S]_0 &= 400 \mu M, \\ K_M &= 6809.0 \mu M, & [P]_0 &= 0, \\ & & [E]_0 &= 8 \mu M \end{aligned}$$

In order to plot the four concentrations, we should know the total time required for the substrate to be completely consumed. A way to solve the problem is to use the *while statement* that evaluates $[S]$ for increasing values of time until the substrate reaches a concentration below a certain cutoff. The concentrations are collected in Figure 26: as you can see, at the beginning all the enzyme is bound to the substrate (saturation), and as the time passes by and the substrate is consumed, the concentration of the free enzyme increases. We can also calculate the rate of the reaction, using the equation $\frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_{cat}[ES]$ and we can compare it with the plot of the Michaelis-Menten equation (see Figure 27). The two diagrams are basically identical for our reaction, despite the remarkable observation that the steady-state assumption made for the derivation of the Michaelis-Menten equation (Eq. 29) has not been used in the semi-analytical solution. This further indicates that the steady-state hypothesis is a good simplification.

Figure 26. Plot of the concentrations of S , P , ES and E for the transformation of L -tryptophan into N -formylkynurenine by $IDO-2$.

CODE 14. This code plots $[S]$, $[P]$, $[ES]$, $[E]$ in function of time the reaction in Eq. 40 and can be used for any irreversible enzymatic reaction (the type in Eq. 27). It uses the semi-analytical solution in Eq. 171. This code also plots the rate of the reaction, which can be obtained once it has registered the array for $[ES]$, using the relationship $\frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_{cat}[ES]$ and it compares that curve with the plot of the Michaelis-Menten equation.

```

% file name = analytical_irreversible
% date of creation = 9/08/2019
clear all
k_cat = 0.103 % catalitic constant (1/s)
K_M = 6.809 % Michaelis constant (micro M)
E_T = 5. % enzyme concentration (micro M)
S(1)= 40. % initial substrate concentration (micro M)
P(1)= 0. % initial product concentration (mico M)
t(1) = 0. % time zero
delta_t = 0.1 % increase in time
% arrays for time, x(t), [S]
i = 1;
while (S(i)>=0.1)
    i = i + 1;
    t(i) = t(i-1) + delta_t;
    x(i) = ( S(1)/K_M ) * exp( ( S(1)-t(i) ) / K_M );
    S(i) = K_M * log( 1.+x(i) ) * ( 1. - ( ( log( 1. + log(1.+x(i)) ) ) / ( 2 + log(1.+x(i)) ) ) );
    t_M = t(i);
    i_M = i;
endwhile
i_M
t_M
% arrays for [P], [ES], [E]
for i=1:i_M
    P(i) = P(1)+S(1)-S(i);
    ES(i) = S(i)*E_T/( K_M + S(i) );
    E(i) = K_M*E_T/( K_M + S(i) );
endfor
% rate
for i=1:i_M
    v(i) = k_cat*ES(i);
endfor
% Michaelis-Menten equation
% rate
for i=1:i_M
    v_MM(i) = k_cat*S(i)*E_T/( K_M + S(i) ); % micro M/s
endfor
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:i_M), S(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:i_M), P(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:i_M), ES(1:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot (t(1:i_M), E(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 1)
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('Concentration ( {\mu}M)');
legend('L-tryptophan', 'N-formylkynurenin', 'IDO2-LTry', 'free IDO-2');
figure(2)
plot (S(1:i_M), v(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan ( {\mu} M)');
ylabel('Rate ( {\mu}M/s)');
legend('Semi-analytical solution');
figure(3)

```

```

plot(S(1:i_M), v_MM(1:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan ( $\mu$  M)');
ylabel('Rate ( $\mu$ M/s)');
legend('Michelis-Menten equation');

```


Figure 27. The plot of the derivative of *N*-formylkynurenin concentration with respect to time, in function of [L-tryptophan]. On the left the curve obtained with the semi-analytical solution; on the right, the curve of the Michaelis-Menten equation.

4.1.2 Newton and Lambert

The transcendental equation in Eq. 162 is amenable of solution through the classic Newton's method. We have instead searched for an analytical expression of its solution, and we have found it thanks to the approximation of the Lambert function, as the reader might remember. Now, we will try the numerical solution and we will compare it with the semi-analytical one. In order to do so let's take a quick look at Newton's method.

We want to find the solution of the equation $f(x) = 0$ in $x \in [a, b]$ and let's assume that $f'(x) \neq 0$ for each value $x \in [a, b]$. The equation of the tangent to the plot of f in $(x_k, f(x_k))$ can be written:

$$\text{Eq. 174} \quad \frac{y - f(x_k)}{x_{k+1} - x_k} = f'(x_k)$$

Its intersection with the x -axis can be found putting $y = 0$:

$$\text{Eq. 175} \quad x_{k+1} = x_k - \frac{f(x_k)}{f'(x_k)}$$

If we now repeat this algorithm from the point $(x_{k+1}, f(x_{k+1}))$ we obtain the tangent $t_{\{k+1\}}$ that encounters the x -axis in x_{k+2} (Figure 28). It is possible to prove that the series $\{x_k\}$ gives an approximation of the solution of $f(x) = 0$ in $x \in [a, b]$.

Figure 28. Representation of Newton's method.

CODE 15. In the case of Eq. 162, we want to find the value of $[S]$ that solve the equation

$$[S] - [S]_0 + K_M \ln \frac{[S]}{[S]_0} + v_{Mt} = 0$$

for a given value of t . So, in our case we have that x is given by $[S]$ while $f([S])$ is given by

$$f([S]) = [S] - [S]_0 + K_M \ln \frac{[S]}{[S]_0} + v_{Mt}$$

Thus, for the derivative we have

$$\frac{df([S])}{d[S]} = 1 + \frac{K_M}{[S]}$$

All that said, the recursive expression in Eq. 175 can be written, in our case, as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 176} \quad [S]_{k+1} = [S]_k - \frac{f([S]_k)}{f'([S]_k)} = [S]_k - \frac{[S]_k - [S]_0 + K_M \ln \frac{[S]_k}{[S]_0} + v_{Mt}}{1 + \frac{K_M}{[S]_k}}$$

There is a possible source of confusion here: the value $[S]_k$ is not the concentration of the substrate for a time t . It is the k^{th} iterate obtained during the calculation of Newton's algorithm for a time t . So, to avoid confusion and to allow the reader to go through the lines of the following code, we will use the following notation:

$$\text{Eq. 177} \quad [S]_{k+1}^N = [S]_k^N - \frac{f_k}{f'_k} = [S]_k^N - \frac{[S]_k^N - [S]_0 + K_M \ln \frac{[S]_k^N}{[S]_0} + v_{Mt_i}}{1 + \frac{K_M}{[S]_k^N}}$$

where $[S]_k^N$ is the k^{th} iterate obtained during the calculation of Newton's algorithm for a time t_i . At the end of the loop, we obtain $[S]_i$, which is the value of $[S]$ at time t_i . To make it even clearer, I have represented the flowchart in Figure 30. As you can notice, there are two while cycles, one externally, that ends when the substrate is small enough; the other one is nested inside the external one: it is the cycle where Newton's method is applied and it ends when the value of f_k is small enough. The diagrams plotted by this code are in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Concentrations (left) and rate (right) for the for the transformation of L-tryptophan into N-formylkynurenine by IDO-2.

```

% file name = newton_irreversible
% date of creation = 11/08/2019
clear all
k_cat = 0.103                % catalytic constant (1/s)
K_M = 6.809                 % Michaelis constant (micro M)
E_T = 5.                   % enzyme concentration (micro M)
v_M = k_cat*E_T            % maximum rate
S(1)= 40.                  % initial substrate concentration (micro M)
P(1)= 0.                   % initial product concentration (mico M)
t(1) = 0.                  % time zero
delta_t = 0.1              % increase in time
% arrays for time, x(t), [S]
i = 1;
while (S(i)>=0.1)
    S_N (1) = S (i);
    f(1) = S_N (1) - S(1) + ( K_M*log(S_N (1)/S(1)) ) + v_M*t(i);
    f_p(1) = 1 + ( K_M/S_N (1) );
    S_N (2) = S_N (1) - f(1)/f_p(1);
    k = 2;
    while ( abs( f(k-1) ) >= 0.001 )
        f(k) = S_N (k) - S(1) + ( K_M*log(S_N (k)/S(1)) ) + v_M*t(i);
        f_p(k) = 1 + ( K_M/S_N (k) );
        S_N (k+1) = S_N (k) - f(k)/f_p(k);
        k = k+1;
    endwhile
    S(i+1) = S_N (k);
    i = i + 1;
    t(i) = t(i-1) + delta_t;
    t_M = t(i);
    i_M = i;

```

```

P(i) = P(1)+S(1)-S(i);
ES(i) = S(i)*E_T/( K_M + S(i) );
E(i) = K_M*E_T/( K_M + S(i) );
endwhile
i_M
t_M
% rate
for i=1:i_M
    v(i) = k_cat*ES(i);
endfor
% Michaelis-Menten equation
% rate
for i=1:i_M
    v_MM(i) = k_cat*S(i)*E_T/( K_M + S(i) );    % micro M/s
endfor
% plots
figure(1)
plot (t(1:i_M), S(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:i_M), P(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (t(1:i_M), ES(1:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot (t(1:i_M), E(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 1)
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('Concentration (μM)');
legend('L-tryptophan', 'N-formylkynurenin', 'IDO2-LTry', 'free IDO-2');
figure(2)
plot (S(1:i_M), v(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan (μM)');
ylabel('Rate (μM/s)');
legend('Numerical solution');
figure(3)
plot (S(1:i_M), v_MM(1:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid on
xlabel('L-tryptophan (μM)');
ylabel('Rate (μM/s)');
legend('Michelis-Menten equation');

```


Figure 30. The flowchart for the solution of the irreversible enzymatic reaction with the use of with Newton's method.

4.2 Reversible reactions

If we take into account Eq. 168, the equation for the reversible enzymatic reaction (Eq. 50) can be written

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S] - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]}{1 + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \Rightarrow \frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P]) - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]}{1 + \frac{([P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P])}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}} \Rightarrow \\ [S] = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P] \end{cases}$$

Eq. 178

$$\frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) [P]}{1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S} \right) [P]}$$

This equation can be integrated by separation of variables, and you can follow pretty much the same method we used in paragraph 4.1:

$$\frac{1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S} \right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) [P]} d[P] = dt \Rightarrow$$

Eq. 179

$$\int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S} \right) y}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) y} dy = \int_{t_0=0}^t dt$$

The integral in the first member of the equation can be split into two integrals. For the first one we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} \right) \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{dy}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) y} = \\ & = - \frac{1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{d \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) y \right)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) y} = \\ & = - \frac{1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \ln \left(\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S]_0 - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]_0} \right) \end{aligned}$$

For the second one we have:

$$\left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S} \right) \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{y}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right) y} dy =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -\frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) y - \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) y} dy = \\
&= -\frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \left\{ \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} dy - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)\right) \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{dy}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) y} \right\} = \\
&= -\frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \left\{ [P] - [P]_0 + \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{d \left[\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) y \right]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) y} \right\} = \\
&= -\frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \left\{ [P] - [P]_0 + \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \ln \left[\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) [P]_0} \right] \right\} = \\
&= -\frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \left\{ [P] - [P]_0 + \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \ln \left[\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S]_0 - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]_0} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

In conclusion, we have found that Eq. 161 can be written

$$\begin{aligned}
&-\frac{1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \ln \left[\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S]_0 - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]_0} \right] - \frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \{[P] - [P]_0\} - \\
&-\frac{\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S}}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \left\{ \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \ln \left[\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S]_0 - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]_0} \right] \right\} = t - t_0 \Leftrightarrow \\
\text{Eq. 180} \quad &\left(1 + \frac{[P]_0 + [S]_0}{K_M^S} + \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0)}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}} \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S} \right) \right) \ln \left[\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}\right) [P]}{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} [S]_0 - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} [P]_0} \right] + \\
&+ \left(\frac{1}{K_M^P} - \frac{1}{K_M^S} \right) \{[P] - [P]_0\} = -(t - t_0) \left(\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S} + \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The same equation can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Eq. 181} \quad & \ln \left[\frac{v_M^f K_M^P ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - (v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S) [P]}{v_M^f K_M^P [S]_0 - v_M^r K_M^S [P]_0} \right]^{K_M^P \left(K_M^S + [P]_0 + [S]_0 + v_M^f \frac{([P]_0 + [S]_0)(K_M^S - K_M^P)}{v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S} \right)} + \\
& + (K_M^S - K_M^P) \{ [P] - [P]_0 \} = -(t - t_0) (v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S)
\end{aligned}$$

4.2.1 Newton's method

We can't use the Lambert function in the case of Eq. 181, but we can still solve the equation with Newton's method introduced in paragraph 4.1.2. In this case, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
f([P]) = \ln \left[\frac{v_M^f K_M^P ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - (v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S) [P]}{v_M^f K_M^P [S]_0 - v_M^r K_M^S [P]_0} \right]^{K_M^P \left(K_M^S + [P]_0 + [S]_0 + v_M^f \frac{([P]_0 + [S]_0)(K_M^S - K_M^P)}{v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S} \right)} + \\
+ (K_M^S - K_M^P) \{ [P] - [P]_0 \} + t (v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S)
\end{aligned}$$

where we have considered $t_0 = 0$. Thus, for the derivative we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{df([P])}{d[P]} = \\
- \frac{(v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S) (v_M^f K_M^P [S]_0 - v_M^r K_M^S [P]_0) K_M^P \left(K_M^S + [P]_0 + [S]_0 + v_M^f \frac{([P]_0 + [S]_0)(K_M^S - K_M^P)}{v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S} \right) + \\
+ (K_M^S - K_M^P)}{v_M^f K_M^P ([P]_0 + [S]_0) - [P] (v_M^f K_M^P + v_M^r K_M^S)}
\end{aligned}$$

As in paragraph 4.1.2 we have:

$$\text{Eq. 182} \quad [P]_{k+1}^N = [P]_k^N - \frac{f_k}{f'_k}$$

where $[P]_k^N$ is the k^{th} iterate obtained during the calculation of Newton's algorithm for a time t_i . At the end of the loop, we obtain $[P]_i$, which is the value of $[P]$ at time t_i . We have also assumed that $f_k = f([P]_k^N)$ and $f'_k = \left. \frac{df([P])}{d[P]} \right|_{[P]=[P]_k^N}$. The flowchart is similar to the one in Figure 30, but the exit condition for the external loop, in this case, is given by the state of equilibrium. So, we can ask to exit from the loop when $\left| \frac{[P]_i}{[S]_i} - \frac{[P]_{eq}}{[S]_{eq}} \right| \leq 0.01$, where $\frac{[P]_{eq}}{[S]_{eq}} = K_{eq}$ for Eq. 17. Once we have $[P]_i$, considering Eq. 168, we obtain

$$\text{Eq. 183} \quad [S]_i = [P]_0 + [S]_0 - [P]_i$$

If we consider now the first and the fourth equations of Eq. 43 we have

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{d[P]}{dt} = -k_1[E][S] + k_{-1}[ES] \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_2[ES] - k_{-2}[E][P] \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{k_1[E][S] - \frac{d[P]}{dt}}{k_{-1}} = [ES] \\ \frac{\frac{d[P]}{dt} + k_{-2}[E][P]}{k_2} = [ES] \end{cases} \Rightarrow$$

$$\begin{cases} [E] = \frac{\frac{d[P]}{dt}(k_{-1} + k_2)}{k_1 k_2 [S] - k_{-1} k_{-2} [P]} \\ [ES] = \frac{\frac{d[P]}{dt} + k_{-2}[E][P]}{k_2} \end{cases}$$

Remembering now the Michaelis-Menten equation itself, we have

Eq. 184

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d[P]_i}{dt} = \frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^S}[S]_i - \frac{v_M^r}{K_M^P}[P]_i}{1 + \frac{[S]_i}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]_i}{K_M^P}} \\ [E]_i = \frac{\frac{d[P]_i}{dt}(k_{-1} + k_2)}{k_1 k_2 [S]_i - k_{-1} k_{-2} [P]_i} \\ [ES]_i = \frac{\frac{d[P]_i}{dt} + k_{-2}[E]_i[P]_i}{k_2} \end{cases}$$

where k_1, k_{-1}, k_{-2} are given by Eq. 112. One might also use Eq. 45 and substitute the last two equations with the following ones

Eq. 185

$$\begin{cases} [ES]_i = \frac{\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1 [S]_i + k_{-2} [P]_i} + 1}{[E]_T} \\ [E]_i = [E]_T - [ES]_i \end{cases}$$

In CODE 16 both the methods are present, and you can chose one or the other using the symbol % ahead of the line that you don't want the computer to read.

Figure 31. Concentrations and rate, in function of time.

4.2.2 Pentose phosphate pathway

CODE 16. We can use the recursive method in Eq. 182 and Eq. 184 to find the evolution in time for the concentrations in Eq. 53. With the settings in Eq. 54 and assuming $[Ru5P]_0 = 0.09$ mM, $[X5P]_0 = 0.01$ mM, $[RPE]_T = 0.01$ we have the concentrations and the rate in Figure 31.

```
% file name = newton_reversible
% date of creation = 14/08/2019
clear all
K_M_S = 5.97 %Michaelis constant (mM) for direct reaction
K_M_P = 7.70 %Michaelis constant (mM) for reverse reaction
E_T = 0.01 %total concentration of the enzyme
k2 = 4020
V_M_F = E_T*k2 %Maximal velocity for direct reaction (mM/s)
K_eq = 1.4
k_1 = k2*K_M_P/(K_M_S*K_eq)
V_M_R = E_T*k_1 %Maximal velocity for reverse reaction (mM/s)
k_2 = k2*(K_M_P+(K_eq*K_M_S))/(K_M_P*K_eq*K_M_S)
k1 = k2*(K_M_P+(K_eq*K_M_S))/(K_M_S*K_eq*K_M_S)
k_1 = k2*(K_M_P/(K_eq*K_M_S))
S(1)= 0.09 % initial substrate concentration (m M)
P(1)= 0.01 % initial product concentration (m M)
E(1)= E_T
ES(1) = 0
t(1) = 0. % time zero
delta_t = 0.1 % increase in time
% arrays for time, x(t), [S]
i = 1;
while ( abs((P(i)/S(i))-K_eq)>=0.01 )
    P_N (1) = P(i);
    f_E(1) = K_M_P*(K_M_S + P(1) + S(1) + ( V_M_F*( P(1) + S(1) )*\
    ( K_M_S - K_M_P )/((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S)) ) );
    f_1(1)=((V_M_F*K_M_P*(P(1)+S(1)))-((V_M_F*K_M_P)+\
    (V_M_R*K_M_S))*P_N(1)))/((V_M_F*K_M_P*S(1))-(V_M_R*K_M_S*P(1)) );
    f(1) = f_E(1)*log(f_1(1))+(K_M_S-K_M_P)*(P_N(1) - P(1))+((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S))*t(i);
    f_p(1) = (-1)*f_E(1)*(1/f_1(1))*((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S))+( K_M_S - K_M_P );
    P_N(2) = P_N (1) - f(1)/f_p(1);
    k = 2;
    while ( abs(P_N(k)-P_N(k-1)) >= 0.001 )
        f_E(k) = K_M_P*(K_M_S + P(1) + S(1) + ( V_M_F*( P(1) + S(1) )*\
        ( K_M_S - K_M_P )/((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S)) ) );
        f_1(k) = ( (V_M_F*K_M_P*(P(1)+S(1))) - (((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S))*\
        P_N(k)) )/((V_M_F*K_M_P*S(1)) - (V_M_R*K_M_S*P(1)) );
        f(k) = f_E(k)*log(f_1(k))+(K_M_S-K_M_P)*(P_N(k) - P(1))+((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S))*t(i);
        f_p(k) = (-1)*f_E(k)*(1/f_1(k))*((V_M_F*K_M_P)+(V_M_R*K_M_S))+( K_M_S - K_M_P );
        P_N (k+1) = P_N (k) - f(k)/f_p(k);
        k = k+1;
    endwhile
    P(i+1) = P_N (k);
    i = i + 1;
    t(i) = t(i-1) + delta_t;
    t_M = t(i);
    i_M = i;
    S(i) = P(1)+S(1)-P(i);
    rate(i) = (((V_M_F/K_M_S)*S(i))-((V_M_R/K_M_P)*P(i)))/(1 + (S(i)/K_M_S) + (P(i)/K_M_P));
    E(i) = rate(i)*(k_1 + k2)/( (k1*k2*S(i)) - (k_1*k_2*P(i)) );
    ES(i) = ( rate(i) + k_2*E(i)*P(i) )/k2;
    %ES(i) = E_T/( 1 + ( (k_1 + k2)/( (k1*S(i)) + (k_2*P(i)) ) ) );
    %E(i) = E_T - ES(i);
endwhile
i_M
% plots
```

```

figure(1)
plot(t(1:i_M), S(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot(t(1:i_M), P(1:i_M), ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot(t(1:i_M), ES(1:i_M), '--k', 'Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot(t(1:i_M), E(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 1)
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('Concentration (mM)');
legend('D-ribose 5-phosphate (mM)', 'D-xylulose 5-phosphate (mM)', 'RPE-Ru5P', 'free RPE');
figure(2)
plot(t(2:i_M), rate(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('time (s)');
ylabel('rate (mM/s)');
figure(3)
plot(P(1:i_M), rate(1:i_M), '-k', 'Linewidth', 2);
grid on
xlabel('D-xylulose 5-phosphate (mM)');
ylabel('rate (mM/s)');

```

4.3 Competitive inhibition, reversible form

Let's consider Eq. 70 and let's assume that $[S]$ is a constant. We can separate the variables:

$$\frac{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} + \frac{[P]}{K_M^P}}{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}} d[P] = \frac{v_M}{K_M^S} dt$$

The integration of the first member leads to two integrals:

$$\text{Eq. 186} \quad \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S}}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} dx + \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{\frac{x}{K_M^P}}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} dx = \int_{t_0}^t \frac{v_M}{K_M^S} d\tau$$

The first one gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S}}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} dx &= \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S}\right) \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{dx}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} = \\ &= -K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S}\right) \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{d\left([S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}\right)}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} = -K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S}\right) \ln \frac{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{[S] - \frac{[P]_0}{K_{eq}}} \end{aligned}$$

where we have assumed that

$$\text{Eq. 187} \quad [P] < [S]K_{eq}$$

For the second integral of the first member we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{K_M^P} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{x}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} dx = \frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{x}{[S]K_{eq} - x} dx = -\frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{[S]K_{eq} - x - [S]K_{eq}}{[S]K_{eq} - x} dx = \\
& = -\frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} dx + \frac{[S]K_{eq}^2}{K_M^P} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{dx}{[S]K_{eq} - x} = -\frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} ([P] - [P]_0) - \frac{[S]K_{eq}^2}{K_M^P} \int_{[P]_0}^{[P]} \frac{d([S]K_{eq} - x)}{[S]K_{eq} - x} = \\
& = -\frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} ([P] - [P]_0) - \frac{[S]K_{eq}^2}{K_M^P} \ln \frac{[S]K_{eq} - [P]}{[S]K_{eq} - [P]_0}
\end{aligned}$$

always assuming the condition in Eq. 187. We have found that Eq. 186 can be written

$$\begin{aligned}
& -K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} \right) \ln \frac{[S] - \frac{[P]}{K_{eq}}}{[S] - \frac{[P]_0}{K_{eq}}} - \frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} ([P] - [P]_0) - \frac{[S]K_{eq}^2}{K_M^P} \ln \frac{[S]K_{eq} - [P]}{[S]K_{eq} - [P]_0} = \frac{v_M}{K_M^S} (t - t_0) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \frac{\frac{x}{K_{eq}}}{[S] - \frac{x}{K_{eq}}} \left[K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_I} + \frac{[S]}{K_M^S} \right) + \frac{[S]K_{eq}^2}{K_M^P} \right] \ln \frac{[S]K_{eq} - [P]}{[S]K_{eq} - [P]_0} + \frac{K_{eq}}{K_M^P} ([P] - [P]_0) = -\frac{v_M}{K_M^S} (t - t_0)
\end{aligned}$$

5 Bifurcation in enzymatic reactions

5.1 Tryptophan transport (LAT1)

In order to study the bifurcation of the system in Eq. 71, let's consider the derivative of Eq. 71 with respect to $[T_{cyt}]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = -\frac{\frac{v_M^f}{K_{eq}K_M^{T_{ECS}}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}} - \frac{\left([T_{ECS}] - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_{eq}} \right) \frac{1}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}}{\left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right)^2} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} = \\
& = -\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \left(\frac{1}{K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right)} + \frac{[T_{ECS}] - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_{eq}}}{K_M^{T_{cyt}} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right)^2} \right) \Rightarrow \\
& \text{Eq. 188} \quad \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = -\frac{v_M^f}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \frac{K_M^{T_{cyt}} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \right) + K_{eq}[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}} K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right)^2}
\end{aligned}$$

Bifurcation is possible only for those values of the parameters in which this derivative is nought. We have

$$\frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = 0 \Leftrightarrow K_M^{T_{cyt}} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \right) + K_{eq}[T_{ECS}] = 0$$

This condition never happens, and it means that this system doesn't have bifurcations. The equilibrium states are given by the condition $\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = 0$ which gives:

$$\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{[T_{ECS}] - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_{eq}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}} \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} = 0 \Leftrightarrow [T_{ECS}]K_{eq} = [T_{cyt}]$$

In the case of the experimental data in Eq. 72 and Eq. 73 we have the equilibrium

$$\text{Eq. 189} \quad [T_{cyt}] = [T_{ECS}]K_{eq} = 1.5 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} 3.43 = 5.145 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

which is the one represented in Figure 12. This state is stable because for $[T_{cyt}] < [T_{ECS}]K_{eq}$ we have $\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} > 0$ and for $[T_{cyt}] > [T_{ECS}]K_{eq}$ we have $\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} < 0$.

5.2 Tryptophan metabolism (IDO1)

In order to study the bifurcation of the system in Eq. 85, let's consider its derivative with respect to $[T_{cyt}]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} &= \frac{\partial \left(-\frac{k_2[IDO_1][T_{cyt}]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = \\ &= -\frac{k_2[IDO_1]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T} + \frac{k_2[IDO_1][T_{cyt}]}{\left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^T} + [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = \\ &= -\frac{k_2[IDO_1]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T} + \frac{k_2[IDO_1][T_{cyt}]}{\left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2} \left(2 \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) = \\ &= k_2[IDO_1] \left(-\frac{\frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^T} + [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T}{\left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2} + \frac{2 \frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^T} + [T_{cyt}]}{\left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 190} \quad \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = k_2 [IDO_1] \left(\frac{\frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^T} - K_M^T}{\left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2} \right)$$

This derivative is nought when $[T_{cyt}] = \sqrt{K_I^T K_M^T}$. This state can potentially lead to bifurcation. But for that to be true it has also to be a state of equilibrium. But the state of equilibrium for this system is reached for $[T_{cyt}] \rightarrow \infty$. So, there is no bifurcation for $[T_{cyt}] = \sqrt{K_I^T K_M^T}$.

5.3 Tryptophan metabolism (LAT1-IDO1 system)

5.3.1 Bifurcation with respect to extracellular L-tryptophan

5.3.1.1 Necessary condition

In the case of the LAT1-IDO1 system we have

$$\text{Eq. 191} \quad \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = \frac{k_2 [IDO_1] \left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^T} - K_M^T \right)}{\left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2} - \frac{v_M^f K_M^{T_{cyt}} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \right) + K_{eq} [T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}} K_M^{T_{cyt}} K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right)^2}$$

Figure 32. This surface is the function in Eq. 152. Axes are in log scale.

CODE 17. If we consider as bifurcation parameter the concentration $[T_{ECS}]$ we can plot Eq. 191 as a function of $[T_{ECS}]$ and $[T_{cyt}]$ with the following code. In order to simplify the writing of Eq. 191 within the code, I have defined the following functions:

$$\begin{aligned} num_1 &= k_2[IDO_1] \left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]^2}{K_I^T} - K_M^T \right) \\ den_1 &= \left(\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^T} + 1 \right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^T \right)^2 \\ num_2 &= K_M^{T_{cyt}} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \right) + K_{eq}[T_{ECS}] \\ den_2 &= K_M^{T_{cyt}} K_{eq} \left(1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}} \right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

So, we have

$$\text{Eq. 192} \quad \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = \frac{num_1}{den_1} - \frac{v_M^f}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} \frac{num_2}{den_2}$$

The plot of this function can be found in Figure 32 and, as you can see, there are two curves in which the second derivative is zero. These states are those in which bifurcations are possible. These states are almost independent from the concentration of extracellular Tryptophan and require a concentration of cytosolic Tryptophan of about 10^8 and $10^{9.1} = 1.26 \cdot 10^9$. The diagram has been plotted by the following code.

```
% file name = Metabolic_trap_bifurcation_TECS_necessary_condition
% date of creation = 31/08/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10) % molecules/cell
K_M_Tcyt = 2.2*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3) % molecules/cell
Keq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8) % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6) % molecules/cell
K_M_Trp = 3.4*(10^7) % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8) % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84 % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208 % molecules IDO1/cell
n = 100 % nodes
Tcyt(1) = 10^7.9; % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(1) = log10(Tcyt(1));
Tcyt(n) = 10^10; % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(n) = log10(Tcyt(n));
d_LogTcyt = (log10(Tcyt(n))-log10(Tcyt(1)))/(n-1);
TECS(1) = 10^5; % molecules/cell
```

```

LogTECS(1) = log10(TECS(1));
TECS(n) = 10^10; % molecules/cell
LogTECS(n) = log10(TECS(n));
d_LogTECS = (log10(TECS(n))-log10(TECS(1)))/(n-1);
% we build the array for Tcyt
for i=2:1:n-1
    LogTcyt(i) = LogTcyt(i-1) + d_LogTcyt;
    Tcyt(i) = 10^LogTcyt(i);
endfor
for j=2:1:n-1
    LogTECS(j) = LogTECS(j-1) + d_LogTECS;
    TECS(j) = 10^LogTECS(j);
endfor
for i=1:n
    for j=1:n
        num_1 = k_2*(IDO1)* ( ((Tcyt(i))^2)/(K_I_Trp)) - K_M_Trp );
        den_1 = ( (((Tcyt(i))/(K_I_Trp))+1)*Tcyt(i) + K_M_Trp )^2;
        num_2 = K_M_Tcyt*(1+ (A/K_A) + (TECS(j)/K_M_TECS) ) +Keq*TECS(j);
        den_2 = K_M_Tcyt*Keq*( 1+ (A/K_A) + (TECS(j)/K_M_TECS) + (Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt) )^2;
        d_d_Tcyt(i,j) = ( num_1/den_1 ) - (V_M_F/K_M_TECS)*( num_2/den_2 );
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(LogTECS(1:5:n), LogTcyt (1:5:n), d_d_Tcyt(1:5:n,1:5:n));
hold on
mesh(LogTECS(1:5:n), LogTcyt(1:5:n), plane_xy(1:5:n,1:5:n));
grid on
xlabel('{log_{10}}(extracellular L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('{log_{10}}(extracellular L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');

```


Figure 33. This surface is the rate in function of cytosolic L-Tryptophan and extracellular L-Tryptophan. Equilibrium states are highlighted: state A and state C are stable equilibria while state B is an unstable one. Axes are in logarithmic scale.

5.3.1.2 Steady states

CODE 18. In order to find possible values of $[T_{ECS}]$ in which the necessary condition for bifurcation is satisfied we also have to search for the steady states of the system. These states are those in which Eq. 152 is zero. They are represented by the intersection of the surface $z = \frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt}$ and plane xy (Figure 33). The following code plot the rate in function of $[T_{cyt}]$ and of the bifurcation parameter $[T_{ECS}]$. Using the same labels introduced in Eq. 153, we have that states A and C are steady states, while B is a state of unstable equilibrium. Two bifurcations are present in agreement with what seen before. The lines of code used to plot this diagram are reported below.

```
% file name = Metabolic_trap_bifurcation_TECS_rate
% date of creation = 27/08/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10)           % molecules/cell
K_M_Tcyt = 2.2*(10^9)           % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3)                % molecules/cell
Keq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8)              % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6)                    % molecules/cell
TECS = 1.5*(10^9)               % molecules/cell
K_M_Trp = 3.4*(10^7)            % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8)            % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84                        % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208                      % molecules IDO1/cell
n = 200                          % nodes
Tcyt(1)= 10^7;                  % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(1) = log10(Tcyt(1));
Tcyt(n) = 10^10;                % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(n) = log10(Tcyt(n));
d_LogTcyt = (log10(Tcyt(n))-log10(Tcyt(1)))/(n-1);
TECS(1) = 10^8;                 % molecules/cell
LogTECS(1) = log10(TECS(1));
TECS(n) = 10^9.7;               % molecules/cell
LogTECS(n) = log10(TECS(n));
d_LogTECS = (log10(TECS(n))-log10(TECS(1)))/(n-1);
% we build the array for Tcyt
for i=2:1:n-1
    LogTcyt(i) = LogTcyt(i-1) + d_LogTcyt;
    Tcyt(i) = 10^LogTcyt(i);
endfor
for j=2:1:n-1
    LogTECS(j) = LogTECS(j-1) + d_LogTECS;
    TECS(j) = 10^LogTECS(j);
endfor
% we build the array for rate and for the bifurcation diagram
for i=1:1:n
    for j=1:1:n
        num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - (Tcyt(i)/(TECS(j)*Keq)) ) * TECS(j)/K_M_TECS;
        den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS(j)/K_M_TECS ) + ( Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt ) );
        num_2 = k_2*IDO1*Tcyt(i);
        den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( Tcyt(i)/K_I_Trp ) ) * Tcyt(i);
        rate (i,j) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
```

```

endfor
LogTECS = log10(TECS);
LogTcyt = log10(Tcyt);
figure (1)
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(LogTECS(1:5:n), LogTcyt (1:5:n), rate(1:5:n,1:5:n));
hold on
mesh(LogTECS(1:5:n), LogTcyt(1:5:n), plane_xy(1:5:n,1:5:n));
xlabel('{log_{10}}(extracellular L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('{log_{10}}(cytosolic L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');
zlabel ('rate (molecules/(min*cell))');
figure (2)
grid on
for i=1:1:n
for j=1:1:n
if ( abs(rate (i,j))<10 )
plot3(LogTECS(j), LogTcyt(i), 0, "@k.", "markersize", 15)
hold on
endif
endif
endif
xlabel('{log_{10}}(extracellular L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('{log_{10}}(cytosolic L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');

```

5.3.1.3 Points of bifurcation

CODE 19. The following code search for those states in which both the conditions PROP. 6 are satisfied. A way to search for these points is to find the nodes in which there is a change in the sign of both the rate dT_{cyt}/dt and the second derivative in Eq. 191. Using this code, we find the following two points of bifurcation:

$$\text{Eq. 193} \quad \begin{cases} \text{point AB: } [T_{cyt}] = 9.65 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}, [T_{ECS}] = 2.17 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \\ \text{point BC: } [T_{cyt}] = 1.54 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}, [T_{ECS}] = 9.73 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \end{cases}$$

```

% file name = Metabolic_trap_bifurcation_states_TECS_bis
% date of creation = 13/09/2019
clear all
% experiential parameters
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10) % molecules/cell
K_M_Tcyt = 2*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3) % molecules/cell
Keq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8) % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6) % molecules/cell
TECS = 1.5*(10^9) % molecules/cell
K_M_Trp = 3.4*(10^7) % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8) % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84 % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208 % molecules IDO1/cell
n = 400 % nodes
Tcyt(1)= 10^7; % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(1) = log10(Tcyt(1));
Tcyt(n) = 10^10; % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(n) = log10(Tcyt(n));
d_LogTcyt = (log10(Tcyt(n))-log10(Tcyt(1)))/(n-1);

```

```

TECS(1) = 10^8; % molecules/cell
LogTECS(1) = log10(TECS(1));
TECS(n) = 10^9.7; % molecules/cell
LogTECS(n) = log10(TECS(n));
d_LogTECS = (log10(TECS(n))-log10(TECS(1)))/(n-1);
% we build the array for Tcyt
for i=2:1:n-1
    LogTcyt(i) = LogTcyt(i-1) + d_LogTcyt;
    Tcyt(i) = 10^LogTcyt(i);
endfor
for j=2:1:n-1
    LogTECS(j) = LogTECS(j-1) + d_LogTECS;
    TECS(j) = 10^LogTECS(j);
endfor
% we build the array for rate
for i=1:1:n
    for j=1:1:n
        num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - (Tcyt(i)/(TECS(j)*Keq)) )*TECS(j)/K_M_TECS;
        den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS(j)/K_M_TECS ) + ( Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt ) );
        num_2 = k_2*IDO1*Tcyt(i);
        den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( Tcyt(i)/K_I_Trp ) )*Tcyt(i);
        rate (i,j) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);
    endfor
endfor
% we build the array for the second derivative
for i=1:n
    for j=1:n
        num_1 = k_2*(IDO1)* ( ((Tcyt(i))^2)/(K_I_Trp) ) - K_M_Trp );
        den_1 = ( (((Tcyt(i))/(K_I_Trp))+1)*Tcyt(i) + K_M_Trp )^2;
        num_2 = K_M_Tcyt*(1+ (A/K_A) + (TECS(j)/K_M_TECS) ) +Keq*TECS(j);
        den_2 = K_M_Tcyt*Keq*( 1+ (A/K_A) + (TECS(j)/K_M_TECS) + (Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt) )^2;
        d_d_Tcyt(i,j) = ( num_1/den_1 ) - (V_M_F/K_M_TECS)*( num_2/den_2 );
    endfor
endfor
% we search for the first bifurcation point
for j=2:n
    for i =2:n
        if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
            if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
                i_1 = i;
                j_1 = j;
            endif
            if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
                i_1 = i;
                j_1 = j;
            endif
            if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
                i_1 = i;
                j_1 = j;
            endif
            if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
                i_1 = i;
                j_1 = j;
            endif
        endif
        if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
            if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )

```

```

    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
endif
endfor
endfor
% we search for the second bifurcation point
for j=2:n
for i =2:n

```

```

if ( j != j_1 )
  if ( i != i_1 )
    if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
    endif
    if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
    endif
    if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
      if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
        i_2 = i;
        j_2 = j;
      endif
    endif
    if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )

```


5.3.1.4 Bifurcation diagram

CODE 20. Now we are interested in a two-dimensional bifurcation diagram. In order to obtain it, we must collect the points in which the rate intercepts the plane xy . We use the change in sign of the rate, as we move along the $[T_{Cyt}]$ axis. The diagram is in Figure 34.

```

% file name = Metabolic_trap_bifurcation_diagram_TECS_bis
% date of creation = 5/09/2019
clear all
% experiental parameters
K_M_TECS = 2.2*(10^10)           % molecules/cell
K_M_Tcyt = 2.*(10^9)            % molecules/cell
K_A = 4.3*(10^3)                % molecules/cell
Keq = 3.43
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8)              % molecules/(min*cell)
A = 5*(10^6)                    % molecules/cell
K_M_Trp = 3.4*(10^7)            % molecules L-T/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8)            % molecules L-T/cell
k_2 = 84                        % molecules L-T/min*molecules IDO1
IDO1 = 208                      % molecules IDO1/cell
n = 400
Tcyt(1) = 10^7;                 % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(1) = log10(Tcyt(1));
Tcyt(n) = 10^10;                % molecules/cell
LogTcyt(n) = log10(Tcyt(n));
d_LogTcyt = (log10(Tcyt(n))-log10(Tcyt(1)))/(n-1);
TECS(1) = 10^8;                 % molecules/cell
LogTECS(1) = log10(TECS(1));
TECS(n) = 10^9.7;               % molecules/cell
LogTECS(n) = log10(TECS(n));
d_LogTECS = (log10(TECS(n))-log10(TECS(1)))/(n-1);
% we build the array for Tcyt
for i=2:1:n-1
    LogTcyt(i) = LogTcyt(i-1) + d_LogTcyt;
    Tcyt(i) = 10^LogTcyt(i);
endfor
% we build the array for TECS
for j=2:1:n-1
    LogTECS(j) = LogTECS(j-1) + d_LogTECS;
    TECS(j) = 10^LogTECS(j);
endfor
% we build the array for rate
for i=1:1:n
    for j=1:1:n
        num_1 = V_M_F*( 1 - (Tcyt(i)/(TECS(j)*Keq)) ) * TECS(j)/K_M_TECS;
        den_1 = ( 1 + ( A/K_A ) + ( TECS(j)/K_M_TECS ) + ( Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt ) );
        num_2 = k_2*IDO1*Tcyt(i);
        den_2 = K_M_Trp + ( 1+( Tcyt(i)/K_I_Trp ) ) * Tcyt(i);
        rate (i,j) = (num_1/den_1) - (num_2/den_2);
    endfor
endfor
% we build the array for the second derivative
for i=1:n
    for j=1:n
        num_1 = k_2*(IDO1)* ( ((Tcyt(i))^2)/(K_I_Trp) ) - K_M_Trp );
        den_1 = ( (((Tcyt(i))/(K_I_Trp))+1)*Tcyt(i) + K_M_Trp )^2;
    endfor
endfor

```

```

num_2 = K_M_Tcyt*(1+ (A/K_A) + (TECS(j)/K_M_TECS) ) +Keq*TECS(j);
den_2 = K_M_Tcyt*Keq*( 1+ (A/K_A) + (TECS(j)/K_M_TECS) + (Tcyt(i)/K_M_Tcyt) )^2;
d_d_Tcyt(i,j) = ( num_1/den_1 ) - (V_M_F/K_M_TECS)*( num_2/den_2 );
plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
endfor
endfor
% we search for the first bifurcation point
for j=2:n
for i=2:n
if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
i_1 = i;
j_1 = j;
endif

```

```

endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_1 = i;
    j_1 = j;
endif
endif
endif
endfor
endfor
% we search for the second bifurcation point
for j=2:n
for i =2:n
if ( j != j_1 )
if ( i != i_1 )
if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i-1,j)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif

```

```

endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) < sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
if ( sign(rate (i,j-1)) > sign(rate (i,j)) )
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i-1,j))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))<sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
if ( sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j-1))>sign(d_d_Tcyt(i,j)) )
    i_2 = i;
    j_2 = j;
endif
endif
endif
endif
endif
% we search for the points of the bifurcation diagram for state A
k = 1
for j=1:n
    for i =1:i_1
        if ( sign(rate (i+1,j)) < sign(rate(i,j)) )
            state_A (k) = Tcyt(i);
            bif_par_A (k) = TECS(j);

```

```

        k = k + 1;
    endif
endfor
endfor
state_A (k) = Tcyt(i_1);
bif_par_A (k) = TECS(j_1);
% we search for the points of the bifurcation diagram for state B
state_B (1) = Tcyt(i_2);
bif_par_B (1) = TECS(j_2);
k = 2
for j=1:n
    for i =i_1:i_2
        if ( sign(rate (i+1,j)) > sign(rate(i,j)) )
            state_B (k) = Tcyt(i);
            bif_par_B (k) = TECS(j);
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
state_B (k) = Tcyt(i_1);
bif_par_B (k) = TECS(j_1);
% we search for the points of the bifurcation diagram for state C
state_C (1) = Tcyt(i_2);
bif_par_C (1) = TECS(j_2);
k = 2
for j=1:n
    for i =i_2:n
        if ( sign(rate (i,j)) < sign(rate(i-1,j)) )
            state_C (k) = Tcyt(i);
            bif_par_C (k) = TECS(j);
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
Log_bif_par_A = log10(bif_par_A);
Log_state_A = log10(state_A);
Log_bif_par_B = log10(bif_par_B);
Log_state_B = log10(state_B);
Log_bif_par_C = log10(bif_par_C);
Log_state_C = log10(state_C);
% plotting of the bifurcation diagram
plot (Log_bif_par_A, Log_state_A, '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (Log_bif_par_B, Log_state_B, ':k', 'Linewidth', 2)
hold on
plot (Log_bif_par_C, Log_state_C, '-k', 'Linewidth', 2)
grid minor
xlabel('{log_{10}}(extracellular L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');
ylabel('{log_{10}}(cytosolic L-tryptophan) (molecules/cell)');

```

5.3.2 Notes about units of measurements

The reader might have recognized that the units of measurements in Eq. 155, Eq. 156, and Eq. 157 are not the usual ones. We have used the number of molecules for cell instead of the concentration expressed in moles/L (M). Moreover, *cell* stands for intracellular volume when we are dealing with metabolites and parameters related to cytosol, while it stands for extracellular volume when we are

dealing with metabolites and parameters related to the extracellular space. In what follows I convert all these parameters in moles/L. To do that we have to calculate both the cellular volume and the extracellular one. Let's assume that

$$\text{Eq. 194} \quad K_M^{TECS} = 21.4 \mu M = 21.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{N_A}{L} \text{ molecules}$$

where

$$\text{Eq. 195} \quad N_A = 6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}$$

is the Avogadro number. Now we can calculate the average extracellular volume (ECV):

$$\begin{aligned} 2.2 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{\text{molecules}}{ECV} &= 21.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \frac{N_A}{L} \text{ molecules} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{2.2 \cdot 10^{10}}{ECV} &= 21.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \frac{N_A}{L} \Rightarrow ECV = \frac{2.2 \cdot 10^{10}}{21.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} L \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 196} \quad ECV = \frac{2.2}{21.4 \cdot 6.02214076} \cdot 10^{-7} L = 1.7071 \cdot 10^{-9} L$$

Let's now assume that

$$\text{Eq. 197} \quad K_M^{Trp} = 15 \mu M = 15 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \frac{N_A}{L} \text{ molecules}$$

Now we can calculate the average cellular volume:

$$\begin{aligned} 3.4 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV} &= 15 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \frac{N_A}{L} \text{ molecules} \\ \Rightarrow CV &= 3.4 \cdot 10^7 \frac{L}{15 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot N_A} \Rightarrow CV = \frac{3.4 \cdot 10^7}{15 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} L \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 198} \quad CV = \frac{3.4}{15 \cdot 6.02214076} \cdot 10^{-10} L = 3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12} L$$

Now we have to convert all the other parameters in Eq. 155, Eq. 156, and Eq. 157. For $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} K_M^{T_{cyt}} &= 2.0 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV} = \frac{2.0 \cdot 10^9}{3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12}} \frac{\text{molecules}}{L} = \frac{2.0}{3.7639} \cdot 10^{21} \frac{\text{molecules}}{L} = \\ &= \frac{2.0}{3.7639} \cdot \frac{10^{21}}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules}}{L} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 199} \quad K_M^{T_{cyt}} = 8.8235 \cdot 10^{-4} M$$

The concentration of the amino acids regarded as inhibitors is considered in both the cellular volume and in the extracellular one. So, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
[A] &= 5 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV + ECV} = \frac{5 \cdot 10^6}{3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12} + 1.7071 \cdot 10^{-9}} \frac{\text{molecules}}{L} = \\
&= \frac{5 \cdot 10^{15}}{3.7639 \cdot 10^{-3} + 1.7071} \cdot \frac{1}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules}}{L} = \frac{5}{10.30306 \cdot 10^8} \frac{\text{moles}}{L}
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. 200 $[A] = 4.8529 \cdot 10^{-9} \mu M$

The same algorithm applies to K_A . So, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
K_A &= 4.3 \cdot 10^3 \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV + ECV} = \frac{4.3 \cdot 10^3}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules}}{1.7109 \cdot 10^{-9} L} = \\
&= \frac{4.3 \cdot 10^{-11}}{6.02214076 \cdot 1.7109} \frac{\text{moles}}{L}
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. 201 $K_A = 4.1735 \cdot 10^{-6} \mu M$

For $[T_{ECS}]_0$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}
[T_{ECS}]_0 &= 1.5 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{ECV} = \frac{1.5 \cdot 10^9}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules}}{1.7071 \cdot 10^{-9} L} = \\
&= \frac{1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}}{6.02214076 \cdot 1.7071} \frac{\text{moles}}{L}
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. 202 $[T_{ECS}]_0 = 1.4591 \mu M$

For K_{eq} we can use Eq. 52 and we have

$$K_{eq} = \frac{[T_{cyt}]_{eq}}{[T_{ECS}]_{eq}} = \frac{\frac{[T_{cyt}]_{eq}}{N_A \cdot CV}}{\frac{[T_{ECS}]_{eq}}{N_A \cdot ECV}} = \frac{[T_{cyt}]_{eq}}{[T_{ECS}]_{eq}} \frac{ECV}{CV} = 3.43 \frac{ECV}{CV} = 3.43 \frac{1.7071 \cdot 10^{-9} L}{3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12} L}$$

Eq. 203 $K_{eq} = 1.5557 \cdot 10^3$

For v_M^f , since the first member of Eq. 152 is $\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt}$, then it has to be expressed with respect to CV and not ECV. So, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
v_M^f &= 1.2 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{min} \cdot CV} = \frac{1.2 \cdot 10^8}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules}}{\text{min} \cdot 3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12} L} = \\
&= \frac{1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}}{6.02214076 \cdot 3.7639} \frac{\text{moles}}{\text{min} \cdot L}
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. 204 $v_M^f = 5.2941 \cdot 10^{-5} \frac{M}{\text{min}}$

All the parameters relative to the reaction catalyzed by IDO1 refer to CV. So, we have

$$[IDO_1] = 208 \frac{\text{molecules } DO1}{\text{cell}} = \frac{208}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules } DO1}{CV} =$$

$$= \frac{208}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{\text{moles}}{3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12} L}$$

Eq. 205 $[IDO_1] = 9.1764 \cdot 10^{-11} M$

Eq. 206 $K_I^{Trp} = \frac{2.5 \cdot 10^8}{6.02214076 \cdot 10^{23}} \frac{N_A \cdot \text{molecules molecules}}{CV} = 1.1029 \cdot 10^{-4} M$

Eq. 207 $k_2 = 84 \frac{1}{\text{min}}$

CODE 21. The following lines of code make the calculations mentioned above. And if we use these new values in CODE 20, we obtain the bifurcation diagram in Figure 35.

```
% file name = cellular volume
% date of creation = 14/09/2019
clear all
% parameters
N_A = 6.02214076*10^23;           % Avogadro number
K_M_TECF = 2.2*10^10;           % molecules / extracellular volume
K_M_TECF_2 = 21.4*N_A*10^(-6);  % molecules/L
K_M_Trp = 3.4*10^7;            % molecules/ intracellular volume
K_M_Trp_2 = 15*N_A*10^(-6);    % molecules/L
K_A = 4.3*10^3;                % molecules/(cellular + extracellular volume)
A = 5*10^6;                    % molecules/(cellular + extracellular volume)
TECS = 1.5*10^9;               % molecules/extracellular volume
K_eq = 3.43;
V_M_F = 1.2*(10^8);            % molecules/(min*cell)
IDO1 = 208;                     % molecules IDO1/cell
K_I_Trp = 2.5*(10^8)           % molecules L-T/cell
% volumes
ECV = K_M_TECF/K_M_TECF_2      % extracellular volume (L)
CV = K_M_Trp/K_M_Trp_2        % cellular volume (L)
% other parameters
K_A_2 = K_A/( N_A*(CV+ECV) )   % moles/L
A_2 = A/( N_A*(CV+ECV) )       % moles/L
TECS_2 = TECS/( N_A*ECV )      % moles/L
K_eq_2 = K_eq*ECV/CV           % moles/L
V_M_F_2 = V_M_F/( N_A*CV )     % moles/(min*L)
IDO1_2 = IDO1/( N_A*CV )       % moles/L
K_I_Trp_2 = K_I_Trp/( N_A*CV ) % moles/L
K_M_Tcyt = 2.*(10^9)/( N_A*CV ) % moles/L
```

One way to check for the presence of mistakes in this case would be to see if the two bifurcation points that we get in Figure 35 are the same in Eq. 193. For the first point of bifurcation we have:

$$[T_{cyt}] = 4.26 \cdot 10^{-5} \frac{\text{moles}}{L} = 4.26 \cdot 10^{-5} N_{ACV} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} = 9.65 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

$$[T_{ECS}] = 2.12 \cdot 10^{-5} \frac{\text{moles}}{L} = 2.12 \cdot 10^{-5} N_{AECV} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} = 2.17 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

Figure 35. Bifurcation diagram with respect to the concentration of extracellular *L*-tryptophan with all the parameters expressed as moles/L. The vertical line is the population of states with a concentration of extracellular *L*-tryptophan of $1.4591 \mu\text{M}$. Both the axes are in log-scale.

Figure 36. Bifurcation diagram with respect to the concentration of extracellular *L*-tryptophan for a symmetric LATI. Units of measurements are expressed in moles/L in the diagram on the left, while they are expressed in molecules/cell in the diagram on the right.

For the second point of bifurcation we have

$$[T_{cyt}] = 6.80 \cdot 10^{-4} \frac{\text{moles}}{L} = 6.80 \cdot 10^{-4} N_{ACV} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} = 1.54 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

$$[T_{ECS}] = 9.47 \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{\text{moles}}{L} = 9.47 \cdot 10^{-7} N_{AECV} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} = 9.73 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}$$

So, we get the same points of bifurcation that we found in Eq. 193.

5.3.3 Symmetrical transporter

If we consider Eq. 194 and Eq. 199 we realize that LAT1 has an asymmetrical behavior, since it has a greater affinity for the uptake of L-tryptophan than it has for the efflux of the same amino acid ($K_M^{T_{cyt}} \sim 40K_M^{T_{ECS}}$). What happens then, if we remove this asymmetry? One way to see that is to plot the bifurcation diagram for $K_M^{T_{cyt}} = K_M^{T_{ECS}} = 21.4 \mu M$ after we have made all the conversions mentioned in the previous paragraph. We get the bifurcation diagram on the left of Another way to see what happens when LAT1 has a symmetric behavior, would be to express $K_M^{T_{ECS}}$ with the same units of measurements $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$ is expressed in. We can then set $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$ with this value in CODE 20. We have:

$$K_M^{T_{ECS}} = 2.2 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{\text{molecules}}{ECV} = 2.2 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{CV}{ECV} \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV} = 4.8507 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV}$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_M^{T_{cyt}} &= 2.0 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{CV} = 2.0 \cdot 10^9 \frac{ECV}{CV} \frac{\text{molecules}}{ECV} = \\ &= 2.0 \cdot 10^9 \frac{1.7071 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ molecules}}{3.7639 \cdot 10^{-12} ECV} = 9.071 \cdot 10^{11} \frac{\text{molecules}}{ECV} \end{aligned}$$

5.3.4 Bifurcation with respect to $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$

5.3.4.1 Necessary condition and steady states

If we plot Eq. 191 in function of $[T_{cyt}]$ and of $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$, we get the two diagrams in Figure 37 (I have split the $[T_{cyt}]$ axis into two parts because otherwise the surface on the right would have been completely flattened on plane xy).

Figure 37. The second derivative in Eq. 191 encounters plane xy in two complex curves. These curves contain the possible bifurcation points with respect to $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$, if any.

As for the steady state points, they are given by the interception of the rate $\frac{dT_{cyt}}{dt}$ (in function of $[T_{cyt}]$ and of $K_M^{T_{cyt}}$) and the plane xy . The population of steady states is

6 Introduction to bifurcation theory

6.1 Bifurcation in one dimension

DEF. 23. Given the differential equation

$$\text{Eq. 208} \quad \frac{dy(t)}{dt} = f(y(t), \mu)$$

where μ is a parameter of f that can assume a given range of values, we say that there is a *bifurcation* for $\mu = \mu_c$ if the states of equilibrium change in number and/or position and/or stability when $\mu = \mu_c$. We assume that Eq. 208 satisfies the hypotheses of PROP. 2.

DEF. 24. We call *phase space* of a system a space in which all the possible states of the system itself are represented. The number of dimensions of a phase space is given by the minimum number of independent coordinates required for the system to be described.

DEF. 25. A *bifurcation diagram* is a collection of the states reached asymptotically by a system (*equilibria*), in function of a parameter of the system itself, called *bifurcation parameter*. In such a diagram, dotted lines represent unstable equilibrium states, while stable equilibrium states are represented with solid lines.

DEF. 26. If a system can settle into multiple different steady-states, depending on external conditions or perturbations, we say that it is bistable. The LAT1-IDO1 system in par. 5.3 represents an example of bistability. Bistability can emerge only for certain values of the parameters of the system, as you can see in Figure 34, for instance, where it is present only when extracellular tryptophane is included within a range of values.

6.1.1 Necessary condition for bifurcation

PROP. 6 (*necessary condition*). Let's consider Eq. 208. If we assume that

$$\text{Eq. 209} \quad f(y_c, \mu_c) = 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 210} \quad \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} \neq 0$$

then it is not possible to have a bifurcation for $\mu = \mu_c$. In other words, $\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} = 0$ is a necessary condition for having a bifurcation in $\mu = \mu_c$.

Proof. According to Dini's theorem on implicit functions, it is possible to find a neighborhood $I \in \mathbb{R}^2$ of the point (y_c, μ_c) in which $f(y, \mu) = 0$ and a unique value of y can be associated with each value of μ . Moreover, we know that $y = \varphi(\mu)$ has a derivative given by

$$\text{Eq. 211} \quad \varphi'(\mu) = -\frac{\frac{\partial f}{\partial \mu}(\varphi(\mu), \mu)}{\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(\varphi(\mu), \mu)}$$

So we have a unique state of equilibrium for any $(y, \mu) \in I$ and no bifurcation is present ■

6.1.2 Examples

Let's consider the differential equation

$$\text{Eq. 212} \quad \dot{y} = \mu - y^2$$

If we assume that $\mu > 0$, this system has two points of equilibrium: $y = \pm\sqrt{\mu}$. The nature of these two states can be decided considering the sign of \dot{y} . For $y > \sqrt{\mu}$ we have $\dot{y} < 0$ and for $-\sqrt{\mu} < y < \sqrt{\mu}$ we have $\dot{y} > 0$: thus, the state $y = \sqrt{\mu}$ is stable. Reasoning with the same method, we can conclude that the state $y = -\sqrt{\mu}$ is unstable. The phase space, in this case, can be represented as follows (it includes both the case $\mu > 0$ and the case $\mu = 0$).

When $\mu = 0$ we have only one state of equilibrium, which is a saddle-node (see PROP. 7). So, it is a state of unstable equilibrium. When $\mu < 0$, no equilibrium state is present.

Figure 38. Bifurcation diagram for the system in Eq. 212. The dotted line represents unstable equilibrium states, the solid one collects all the stable equilibrium states.

In the case of the system in Eq. 212 we have

$$f(y, \mu) = \mu - y^2 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial f(y, \mu)}{\partial y} = -2y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} f(0,0) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial f(0,0)}{\partial y} = 0 \end{cases}$$

So, the necessary condition for having a bifurcation in $(y = 0, \mu = 0)$ is fulfilled. Note also that for the other two states of equilibrium ($y = -\sqrt{\mu}$ and $y = \sqrt{\mu}$) we have $\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \neq 0$ and this means that bifurcations are not possible for $\mu \neq 0$. The bifurcation diagram with respect to the only parameter of the system, is the one in Figure 38. It can also be noted that Figure 38 is the interception between the surface $z = f(y, \mu)$ and the plane xy , as can be seen in Figure 39.

Figure 39. Equilibrium states for the system in Eq. 212 are given by the interception between the surface $z = f(y, \mu)$ and the plane xy .

Let's consider now the system:

Eq. 213 $\dot{y} = \mu y - y^2$

Figure 40. Bifurcation diagram for the system in Eq. 213. The dotted line represents unstable equilibrium states, the solid one collects all the stable equilibrium states.

The extremes are $y = 0$ and $y = \mu$: with the same method used above, we can draw the following phase state, which holds for $\mu \geq 0$.

Hence, for $\mu > 0$ we have that $y = \mu$ is a state of stable equilibrium, while $y = 0$ is a state of unstable equilibrium. Moreover, when $\mu = 0$, the only state of equilibrium is $y = \mu$, which is a state of unstable equilibrium. For $\mu < 0$ the phase state is as follows:

We have a state of unstable equilibrium for $y = \mu$ and a state of stable equilibrium for $y = 0$. Thus, the bifurcation diagram can be represented as in Figure 40. Note also that

$$f(y, \mu) = \mu y - y^2 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial f(y, \mu)}{\partial y} = \mu - 2y \Rightarrow \begin{cases} f(0,0) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial f(0,0)}{\partial y} = 0 \end{cases}$$

So, the necessary condition for the bifurcation is satisfied in $(0,0)$, but not elsewhere. In fact, we can still have $\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = 0$ for $y = \frac{\mu}{2}$, but $f\left(y = \frac{\mu}{2}, \mu\right) \neq 0$, so there no equilibrium state.

6.1.3 Saddle-node bifurcation

PROP. 7 (*saddle-node bifurcation*). Let's consider Eq. 208. If we assume that

Eq. 214 $f(y_c, \mu_c) = 0$

Eq. 215 $\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} = a \neq 0$

Eq. 216 $\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} = 0$

Eq. 217 $\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y} = 2b \neq 0$

then we have that it exists a neighborhood of μ_c in \mathbb{R} such that the following table holds.

Proof. If we consider the expansion of f with its Taylor series centered in y_c, μ_c , we have

$$f(y, \mu) = f(y_c, \mu_c) + \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} (\mu - \mu_c) + \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} (y - y_c) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y} (y - y_c)^2 + 2 \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} (\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) \right) + \dots$$

where we have considered that $\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} = \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y \partial \mu}$ (Schwartz's theorem). If we now substitute Eq. 214, Eq. 215, Eq. 216, and Eq. 217 in this expression we get

$$f(y, \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 + b(y - y_c)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} (\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) + \sigma(\rho^2)$$

whit $\rho = \sqrt{(\mu - \mu_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2}$. The remainder is such that $\lim_{\rho \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sigma(\rho^2)}{\rho^2} = 0$. We can arrange the expansion of f in the following way:

$$f(y, \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c) \left[1 + \frac{1}{2a} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c) \right] + b(y - y_c)^2 \left[1 + 2 \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)}{b(y - y_c)} \right] + \sigma(\rho^2)$$

		$\mu < \mu_c$	$\mu > \mu_c$
$ab < 0$	$a > 0$ $b < 0$	No equilibria	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ stable
			$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ unstable
	$a < 0$ $b > 0$		$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ unstable
			$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ stable
$ab > 0$	$a > 0$ $b > 0$	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ unstable	No equilibria
		$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ stable	
	$a < 0$ $b < 0$	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ stable	
		$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu)$ unstable	

Table 1. The complete study of stability for the equilibria of the system in Eq. 208 for whit the hypotheses of PROP. 7 holds.

Equilibria are given by the condition

$$(y - y_c)^2 = -\frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c) \frac{\left[1 + \frac{1}{2a} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c) \right]}{\left[1 + 2 \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)}{b(y - y_c)} \right]} - \frac{\sigma((\mu - \mu_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2)}{b \left[1 + 2 \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)}{b(y - y_c)} \right]}$$

For $\mu - \mu_c \rightarrow 0$ we have

$$(y - y_c)^2 \rightarrow -\frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c) - \frac{\sigma((y - y_c)^2)}{b}$$

For $y - y_c \rightarrow 0$ we have

$$(y - y_c)^2 \rightarrow -\frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$$

We can then say that the states of equilibrium of the system in Eq. 208 in a neighborhood of y_c, μ_c , when the hypotheses of this proposition holds, are given by the roots of the equation

$$\text{Eq. 218} \quad (y - y_c)^2 = -\frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c) \Leftrightarrow (y - y_c)^2 = -2 \frac{\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu}}{\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y}} (\mu - \mu_c)$$

And we get

$$\text{Eq. 219} \quad y = y_c \pm \sqrt{-\frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)} \Leftrightarrow y = y_c \pm \sqrt{-2 \frac{\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu}}{\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y}} (\mu - \mu_c)}$$

We have real roots only in the following two cases:

$$\text{Eq. 220} \quad ab < 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y} < 0 \quad \text{AND} \quad \mu - \mu_c > 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 221} \quad ab > 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y} > 0 \quad \text{AND} \quad \mu - \mu_c < 0$$

Another way to see this problem is by considering the intersection between $z = f(y, \mu)$ and the plane $y\mu$ as a conic, and by classifying it through the study of its associated matrix. We have

$$\text{Eq. 222} \quad a\mu + by^2 - 2by_c y + (by_c^2 - a\mu_c) = 0 \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} by_c^2 - a\mu_c & \frac{a}{2} & -by_c \\ \frac{a}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -by_c & 0 & b \end{pmatrix}$$

We have

$$\det A = \begin{vmatrix} by_c^2 - a\mu_c & \frac{a}{2} & -by_c \\ \frac{a}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -by_c & 0 & b \end{vmatrix} = b \begin{vmatrix} by_c^2 - a\mu_c & \frac{a}{2} \\ \frac{a}{2} & 0 \end{vmatrix} = -\frac{ba^2}{4} \Rightarrow r(A) = 3$$

$$\det A_{23,23} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

This means that the intersection of $f(y, \mu)$ with the plane $y\mu$ is always a parable. Its axis of symmetry is given by the equation:

$$\sqrt{b} \frac{\partial f(y, \mu)}{\partial y} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{b}(2by - 2by_c) = 0 \Leftrightarrow y = y_c$$

The intersection between the axis of symmetry and the parable itself is then μ_c, y_c . The orientation of the parable depends on whether $\mu > \mu_c$ (in this case it is included in the semi plane $\mu > \mu_c$) or $\mu < \mu_c$ (in this case it is included in the semi plane $\mu < \mu_c$). We have still to prove that those two pair of equilibrium states have opposite stabilities. Let's take a point within the plane included by the parable and one outside it, both points of the axis of symmetry, for instance. As you can see from Eq. 259, the stability of the two equilibria depends only on the sign of a and of $\mu - \mu_c$, but it is always true that the two equilibria have opposite stability. An example for each of the four cases is plotted in Figure 41. This completely proves the proposition ■

$$\text{Eq. 223} \quad \begin{cases} f(y_c, 2\mu_c) = 2a\mu_c \\ f\left(y_c, \frac{\mu_c}{2}\right) = -\frac{a}{2}\mu_c \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \mu > \mu_c \Rightarrow \begin{cases} a > 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{stable} \\ y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{unstable} \end{cases} \\ a < 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{unstable} \\ y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{stable} \end{cases} \end{cases} \\ \mu < \mu_c \Rightarrow \begin{cases} a > 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{unstable} \\ y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{stable} \end{cases} \\ a < 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{stable} \\ y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}(\mu_c - \mu) \leftarrow \text{unstable} \end{cases} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

DEF. 27. When the hypothesis of PROP. 7 holds for the system in Eq. 208, we say that a *saddle-node bifurcation* occurs at $\mu = \mu_c$.

CODE 22. This code plot the diagram for the saddle-node bifurcation like the ones in Figure 41.

```
% file name = saddle_node_1
% date of creation = 25/05/2021
clear all
% parameters
mu_c = -2
y_c = 2
a = -3
b = 2
% plotting of the surface y'(y,mu)
i = 1
j = 1
mu(i) = mu_c;
if (a*b < 0)
    mu(100) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
else
    mu(100) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
```

```

endif
y(j) = y_c-sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(100)));
y(100)= y_c+sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(100)));
d_mu = (mu(100)-mu(1))/101
d_y = (y(100)-y(1))/101
for i=2:100
    mu(i) = mu(i-1) + d_mu;
endfor
for j=2:100
    y(j) = y(j-1) + d_y;
endfor
for i=1:1:100
    for j =1:1:100
        f(i,j) = a*mu(i) + b*(y(j)^2) - 2*b*y_c*y(j)+(b*y_c^2 - a*mu_c);
        plane_xy(i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(y(1:5:100), mu(1:5:100), f(1:5:100,1:5:100));
hold on
mesh(y(1:5:100), mu(1:5:100), plane_xy(1:5:100,1:5:100));
hold on
xlabel('y');
ylabel('\mu');
mu_c_str = num2str(mu_c);
y_c_str = num2str(y_c);
a_str = num2str(a);
b_str = num2str(b);
legenda = strjoin({'\mu_c = ',mu_c_str,','y_c = ',y_c_str','a = ', a_str,'b = ', b_str });
legend(legenda)
% plotting of the states of equilibrium
k = 1;
h = 1;
for i=1:1:100
    for j =1:1:100-1
        if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
            stable(k) = y(j);
            mu_s(k) = mu(i);
            z_s(k) = 0.;
            k = k+1;
        elseif ( sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)) )
            unstable(h) = y(j);
            mu_us(h) = mu(i);
            z_us(h) = 0.;
            h = h+1;
        end
    endfor
endfor
plot3( stable, mu_s, z_s, '-b','linewidth', 8);
hold on
plot3( unstable, mu_us, z_us, '-r','linewidth', 8);

```

In PROP. 7 we have considered, in the neighborhood of y_c, μ_c , the following ODE:

$$\text{Eq. 224} \quad \dot{y}(t) = a(\mu - \mu_c) + b(y - y_c)^2$$

Now, this ODE can be solved analytically by separation of the variables. Let's consider the substitution $y - y_c = \eta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\eta(t)}{dt} = a(\mu - \mu_c) + b\eta^2 &\Leftrightarrow \frac{d\eta}{a(\mu - \mu_c) + b\eta^2} = dt \Leftrightarrow \int_{t_0}^t \frac{d\eta}{a(\mu - \mu_c) + b\eta^2} = t - t_0 \Leftrightarrow \\ &\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} \int_{t_0}^t \frac{d\eta}{1 + \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\eta^2} = t - t_0 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 41. Equilibria for the system in PROP. 7 for 4 different examples. In this case, a red line indicates unstable equilibrium, while a blue line indicates stable equilibrium.

We must now distinguish four cases. For $ab < 0$ and $\mu < \mu_c$ we have $\frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} > 0$. In this case we can consider the substitution $x = \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}}\eta$ and we have

$$\frac{1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{b}} \int_{t_0}^t \frac{dx}{1 + x^2} = t - t_0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{ab(\mu - \mu_c)}} \tan^{-1}(x) \Big|_{t_0}^t = t - t_0 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow \frac{\tan^{-1}\left(\sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu-\mu_c)}}(y-y_c)\right)\Big|_{t_0}^t}{\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}} = t-t_0 &\Leftrightarrow \tan^{-1}\left(\sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu-\mu_c)}}(y(t)-y_c)\right) = \\ &= \tan^{-1}\left(\sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu-\mu_c)}}(y(t_0)-y_c)\right) + (t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have found

$$\text{Eq. 225} \quad \begin{cases} y(t) = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu-\mu_c)}{b}} \tan[C + (t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}] \\ C = \tan^{-1}\left(\sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu-\mu_c)}}(y(t_0)-y_c)\right) \end{cases}$$

This same solution holds also for $ab > 0$ and $\mu > \mu_c$. This solution do not have a limit for $t \rightarrow \infty$, in agreement with Table 1. Let's verify that this solution does in fact solve Eq. 224. As a first step, let's calculate the derivative of $y(t)$:

$$\text{Eq. 226} \quad \begin{cases} \dot{y}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu-\mu_c)}{b}} \frac{\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}}{\cos^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}]} \\ C = \tan^{-1}\left(\sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu-\mu_c)}}(y(t_0)-y_c)\right) \end{cases}$$

If we substitute now $\dot{y}(t), y(t)$ in Eq. 224, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\sqrt{\frac{a(\mu-\mu_c)}{b}} \frac{\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}}{\cos^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}]} = a(\mu-\mu_c) + \\ &\quad + a(\mu-\mu_c) \left(\tan[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}]\right)^2 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow &\frac{1}{\cos^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}]} = 1 + \frac{\sin^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}]}{\cos^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}]} \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow &1 = \cos^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}] + \sin^2[C+(t-t_0)\sqrt{ab(\mu-\mu_c)}] \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we can confirm the goodness of our solution. For the other two cases we have $\frac{b}{a(\mu-\mu_c)} < 0$,

then we consider the substitution $x = \eta \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c-\mu)}}$ and we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} \int \frac{d\eta}{1 - \frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)} \eta^2} = t + C \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \int \frac{dx}{1 - x^2} = a(\mu - \mu_c)t + C \Leftrightarrow \\
& \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \int \frac{dx}{1 - x^2} = -a(\mu_c - \mu)t + C \Leftrightarrow \int \frac{dx}{1 - x^2} = -t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C \Leftrightarrow \\
& \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \tanh^{-1} \left((y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right) = -t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C_1 \leftarrow (y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \in]-1,1[\\ \coth^{-1} \left((y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right) = -t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C_2 \leftarrow (y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \in \mathbb{R} -]-1,1[\end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

Then we have found the solutions

$$\begin{cases} (y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} = \tanh \left(-t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C_1 \right) \leftarrow (y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \in]-1,1[\\ (y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} = \coth \left(-t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C_2 \right) \leftarrow (y(t) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \in \mathbb{R} -]-1,1[\end{cases}$$

But tanh and coth are odd functions, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \tanh \left(-t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C_1 \right) = -\tanh \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1 \right) \\
& \coth \left(-t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} + C_2 \right) = -\coth \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2 \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Remember also that

$$D \left[\tanh \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1 \right) \right] = \frac{\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)}}{\cosh^2 \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1 \right)}, \quad D \left[\coth \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2 \right) \right] = -\frac{\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)}}{\sinh^2 \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2 \right)}$$

Then we have found the solutions

$$\text{Eq. 227} \quad \begin{cases} y_1(t) = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \tanh \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1 \right) \\ \dot{y}_1(t) = -\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\cosh^2 \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1 \right)} \\ C_1 = \tanh^{-1} \left((y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right) + t_0 \sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} \\ y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} < y_1(t) < y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Eq. 228} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} y_2(t) = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \coth(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2) \\ \dot{y}_2(t) = \frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2)} \\ C_2 = \coth^{-1}\left((y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}}\right) + t_0\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} \\ y_2(t) < y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}, \quad y_2(t) > y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \end{array} \right.$$

As for C_1 , I have considered the following passages:

$$\begin{aligned} y(t_0) - y_c &= -\sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \tanh(t_0\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow -(y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} &= \tanh(t_0\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \tanh^{-1}\left(- (y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}}\right) - t_0\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} &= -C_1 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \tanh^{-1}\left((y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}}\right) + t_0\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} &= C_1 \end{aligned}$$

where we have considered that \tanh^{-1} is a odd function too. For C_2 we have analogous passages, since also \coth^{-1} is a odd function, and we find

$$\coth^{-1}\left((y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}}\right) + t_0\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} = C_2$$

Asymptotically we have

$$y_1(t) \rightarrow y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}, \quad y_2(t) \rightarrow y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}$$

So, it seems we have missed some of the solutions, during the integration. I can't say where the problem has been, but to prove the goodness of our integration, let's see if solution in Eq. 227 does in fact solve Eq. 224:

$$-\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1)} = a(\mu - \mu_c) + b \frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b} \left(\tanh(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1) \right)^2 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow -\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1)} = -a(\mu_c - \mu) + a(\mu_c - \mu) \frac{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1)}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1)} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow -1 = -\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1) + \sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1)$$

By remembering that $\cosh^2 x - \sinh^2 x = 1$, we conclude that $y_1(t)$ is in fact a solution of Eq. 224. Let's now test $y_2(t)$:

$$\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2)} = a(\mu - \mu_c) + a(\mu_c - \mu) \left(\coth(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2) \right)^2 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2)} = -1 + \frac{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2)}{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2)} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 1 = -\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2) + \cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2)$$

Then, $y_2(t)$ is a solution of Eq. 224, too. But we still miss two solutions, so let's try the following ones:

$$\text{Eq. 229} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} y_3(t) = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \tanh(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3) \\ \dot{y}_3(t) = \frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3)} \\ C_3 = -\tanh^{-1} \left((y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right) + t_0 \sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} \\ y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} < y_3(t) < y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \end{array} \right.$$

$$\text{Eq. 230} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} y_4(t) = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \coth(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_4) \\ \dot{y}_4(t) = -\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_4)} \\ C_4 = -\coth^{-1} \left((y(t_0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right) + t_0 \sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} \\ y_4(t) < y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}, \quad y_4(t) > y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \end{array} \right.$$

Does solution $y_3(t)$ solve Eq. 224? We have:

$$\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3)} = a(\mu - \mu_c) + a(\mu_c - \mu) \left(\tanh(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3) \right)^2 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3)} = -1 + \frac{\sinh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3)}{\cosh^2(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3)}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow -1 = \cosh^2 \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_3 \right) - \sinh^2 \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2 \right)$$

$ab(\mu_c - \mu) > 0$	$y_1(t) > y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}$ $y_1(t) < y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}$	$y_1(t) = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \tanh \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_1 \right)$ $C_1 = \tanh^{-1} \left((y(0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right)$	$y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}$
	$y_2(t) < y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}$ $y_2(t) > y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}}$	$y_2(t) = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu_c - \mu)}{b}} \coth \left(t\sqrt{ab(\mu_c - \mu)} - C_2 \right)$ $C_2 = \coth^{-1} \left((y(0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu_c - \mu)}} \right)$	
$ab(\mu_c - \mu) < 0$	$y(t) = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{b}} \tan \left[t\sqrt{ab(\mu - \mu_c)} + C \right]$ $C = \tan^{-1} \left((y(0) - y_c) \sqrt{\frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}} \right)$		No limit

Table 2. Solutions for the ODE in Eq. 224. We have considered $t_0 = 0$.

Figure 42. Evolution in time of the solution of Eq. 224 towards its asymptotic value, for different values of μ and for a particular initial condition and a particular set of parameters a, b .

The answer is no. Does solution $y_4(t)$ solve Eq. 224? In this case too the answer is no. So we remain with the problem that some solutions are missing. In Figure 42 there is a family of solutions for a particular set of parameters a, b , for a particular initial condition and for several values of μ . This diagram was plotted by the following code.

CODE 23. This code plots a family of solutions and the bifurcation diagram for Eq. 224 (Figure 42).

```

% file name = saddle_node_2
% date of creation = 27/05/2021
clear all
% parameters
mu_c = 2
y_c = 4
a = 3
b = -2
y_0 = 4.2
% calculating y'(y,mu)
n = 100;
i = 1
j = 1
mu (1) = mu_c;
temp = 1;
if (a*b < 0 )
    mu (n) = mu_c + temp*abs(mu_c);
    mu2(1) = 2*mu_c - mu(n);
    mu2(n) = mu_c;
else
    mu (n) = mu_c - temp*abs(mu_c);
    mu2(1) = mu_c;
    mu2(n) = 2*mu_c - mu(n);
endif
y (j) = y_c-sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n)));
y(n)= y_c+sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n)));
d_mu = (mu(n)-mu(1))/(n+1)
d_y = (y(n)-y(1))/(n+1)
for i=2:n
    mu(i) = mu(i-1) + d_mu;
    mu2(i) = mu2(i-1) + d_mu;
endfor
for j=2:n
    y(j) = y(j-1) + d_y;
endfor
for i=1:1:n
    for j =1:1:n
        f(i,j) = a*mu(i) + b*(y(j)^2) - 2*b*y_c*y(j)+(b*y_c^2 - a*mu_c);
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
% calculating and plotting the solutions of the ODE
delta_t = 0.0001;
m = 5*10^3;
t(1) = 0.;
for i=2:1:m
    t(i) = t(i-1) + delta_t;
endfor
for i=2:1:n
    sol(i,1) = y_0;

```

```

radical = sqrt( a*(mu_c - mu(i))/b );
radical2 = sqrt( a*b*(mu_c - mu(i)) );
if ( and( y_0 > y_c - radical, y_0 < y_c + radical ) )
    C_1 = atanh( ((y_0-y_c)/radical) );
    for k = 2:1:m
        sol(i,k) = y_c - radical*tanh( t(k)*radical2 - C_1 );
        mu_sol(i,k) = mu(i);
    endfor
else
    C_2 = acoth( ((y_0-y_c)/radical) );
    for k = 2:1:m
        sol(i,k) = y_c - radical*coth( t(k)*radical2 - C_2 );
        mu_sol(i,k) = mu(i);
    endfor
endif
endfor
for i=2:10:n
    plot3( sol(i,2:50:m), mu_sol(i,2:50:m), t(2:50:m), '-k','linewidth', 3);
    hold on
endfor
% there is another solution
for i=2:1:n
    sol2(i,1) = y_0;
    radical = sqrt( a*(mu2(i) - mu_c)/b )
    radical2 = sqrt( a*b*(mu2(i) - mu_c) );
    C = atan( (y_0-y_c)/radical )
    for k = 2:1:m
        sol2(i,k) = y_c + radical*tan( t(k)*radical2 + C );
        mu_sol2(i,k) = mu2(i);
    endfor
endfor
for i=2:10:n
    plot3( sol2(i,2:50:m), mu_sol2(i,2:50:m), t(2:50:m), '-k','linewidth', 3);
    hold on
endfor
% plotting of the states of equilibrium
k = 1;
h = 1;
for i=1:1:100
    for j = 1:1:100-1
        if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
            stable(k) = y(j);
            mu_s (k) = mu(i);
            z_s(k) = t(m);
            k = k+1;
        elseif ( sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)) )
            unstable(h) = y(j);
            mu_us (h) = mu(i);
            z_us(h) = t(m);
            h = h+1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
plot3( stable, mu_s, z_s, '-b','linewidth', 8);
hold on
plot3( unstable, mu_us, z_us, '-r','linewidth', 8);
grid on

```

```

xlabel('y');
ylabel('{\mu}');
mu_c_str = num2str(mu_c);
y_c_str = num2str(y_c);
a_str = num2str(a);
b_str = num2str(b);
y_0_str = num2str(y_0);
titolo = strjoin({'dy/dt = a(\mu-\mu_c) + b(y-y_c)^2, ', '{\mu_c} = '...
, mu_c_str, ', {y_c} = ', y_c_str, ', a = ', a_str, ', b = ', b_str, ', {y_0} = ', y_0_str });
title (titolo)

```

6.1.4 Pitchfork bifurcation

PROP. 8 (*Pitchfork bifurcation*). Let's consider Eq. 208. If we assume that

$$\text{Eq. 231} \quad f(y_c, \mu_c) = 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 232} \quad f(y_c - y, \mu) = -f(y_c + y, \mu)$$

$$\text{Eq. 233} \quad \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} = 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 234} \quad \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y^3} = 6b \neq 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 235} \quad \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y \partial \mu} = a \neq 0$$

then we have that it exists a neighborhood of μ_c in \mathbb{R} such that the following table holds.

Proof. If we consider the expansion of f with its Taylor series centered in y_c, μ_c , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
f(y, \mu) &= f(y_c, \mu_c) + \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} (\mu - \mu_c) + \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} (y - y_c) + \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y} (y - y_c)^2 + 2 \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} (\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) \right) + \\
&+ \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^3 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^3 + \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^3 y} (y - y_c)^3 + \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu \partial y} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 (y - y_c) \right) + \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial^2 y} (\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c)^2 \right) + \dots
\end{aligned}$$

where we have considered that $\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} = \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y \partial \mu}$ (Schwartz's theorem). If we now substitute the hypotheses in this expression, we have

$$f(y, \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) + b(y - y_c)^3 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 + \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^3 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^3 + \right.$$

$$+ \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu \partial y} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 (y - y_c) + \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial^2 y} (\mu - \mu_c) (y - y_c)^2 \Big) + \sigma(\rho^3)$$

whit $\rho = \sqrt{(\mu - \mu_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2}$. We can arrange the expansion of f in the following way:

Figure 43. Equilibria for the system in PROP. 8 for 4 different examples. In this case, a red line indicates unstable equilibrium, while a blue line indicates stable equilibrium.

$$f(y, \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)}{a(y - y_c)} \right] +$$

$$+ b(y - y_c)^3 \left[1 + \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)^2}{2b(y - y_c)^3} + \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^3 \mu} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)^3}{6b(y - y_c)^3} + \right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^3 \mu} \frac{(\mu - \mu_c)^2}{6b(y - y_c)^2} + \frac{\partial^3 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial^2 y} \frac{\mu - \mu_c}{6b(y - y_c)} \right] + \sigma(\rho^3)$$

As μ tends to μ_c , the addends in square brackets lose their importance with respect to the unity. Then we can write:

$$f(y, \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) + b(y - y_c)^3 + \sigma((y - y_c)^3)$$

Now, for $y \rightarrow y_c$, the function $\sigma((y - y_c)^3)$ has less weight than the other addends and we omit it. Thus, we have now the system

Eq. 236 $\frac{dy(t)}{dt} = f(y(t), \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) + b(y - y_c)^3$

We can now consider the intersection of $z = f(y, \mu)$ with the plane $z = 0$:

$$f(y(t), \mu) = 0 \Leftrightarrow a(\mu - \mu_c) + b(y - y_c)^2 = 0 \quad \text{OR} \quad (y - y_c) = 0$$

		$\mu < \mu_c$		$\mu > \mu_c$	
$ab < 0$	$a > 0$ $b < 0$	$y = y_c$	stable	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$	stable
				$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$	
				$y = y_c$	unstable
	$a < 0$ $b > 0$	$y = y_c$	unstable	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$	unstable
				$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$	
				$y = y_c$	stable
$ab > 0$	$a > 0$ $b > 0$	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$	unstable	$y = y_c$	unstable
		$y = y_c - \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$			
		$y = y_c$	stable		
	$a < 0$ $b < 0$	$y = y_c + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}(\mu_c - \mu)}$	stable	$y = y_c$	unstable
			$y = y_c$		

Table 3. The complete study of stability for the equilibria of the system in Eq. 208 for which the hypotheses of PROP. 8 holds.

We have the equilibria represented by the line of equation $y = y_c$. We have then the equilibria represented by the parable $a(\mu - \mu_c) + b(y - y_c)^2 = 0$ which is the one in Eq. 222. To discover the stability of equilibria, one can follow the same method used in the previous proposition. I have compiled Table 3 using the plots (Figure 43) made by the following code ■

CODE 24. This code plots the diagram for the pitchfork bifurcation like the ones in Figure 43.

```

% file name = Pitchfork_bifurcation_1
% date of creation = 26/05/2021
clear all
% parameters
mu_c = -2
y_c = 2
a = -1
b = -3
% plotting of the surface y'(y,mu)
n = 200;
if (a*b < 0 )
    mu (n) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
else
    mu (n) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
endif
y (1) = y_c-sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n)));
y(n)= y_c+sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n)));
d_mu = (mu(n)-mu(1))/( n+1 )
d_y = (y(n)-y(1))/( n+1 )
for i=2:n
    mu(i) = mu(i-1) + d_mu;
endfor
for j=2:n
    y(j) = y(j-1) + d_y;
endfor
for i=1:1:n
    for j =1:1:n
        f(i,j) = ( a*mu(i) + b*(y(j)^2) - 2*b*y_c*y(j) + (b*y_c^2 - a*mu_c) )*( y(j) - y_c );
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(y(1:5:n), mu(1:5:n), f(1:5:n,1:5:n));
hold on
mesh(y(1:5:n), mu(1:5:n), plane_xy(1:5:n,1:5:n));
hold on
xlabel('y');
ylabel('{\mu}');
mu_c_str = num2str(mu_c);
y_c_str = num2str(y_c);
a_str = num2str(a);
b_str = num2str(b);
legenda = strjoin({'{\mu_c} = ',mu_c_str,','y_c} = ',y_c_str,'a = ', a_str,'b = ', b_str } );
legend (legenda)
% plotting of the states of equilibrium
k = 1;
h = 1;
p = 1;
q = 1;
check_s2 = 0;
check_us2 = 0;
for i=1:1:n
    for j =1:1:n-1
        if (y(j)<y_c+d_y)
            if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )

```

```

stable(k) = y(j);
mu_s(k) = mu(i);
z_s(k) = 0.;
k = k+1;
elseif ( sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)) )
unstable(h) = y(j);
mu_us(h) = mu(i);
z_us(h) = 0.;
h = h+1;
endif
endif
if (y(j) > y_c+d_y)
if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
stable2(p) = y(j);
mu_s2(p) = mu(i);
z_s2(p) = 0.;
p = p+1;
check_s2 = 1;
elseif (sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)))
unstable2(q) = y(j);
mu_us2(q) = mu(i);
z_us2(q) = 0.;
q = q+1;
check_us2 = 1;
endif
endif
endif
endfor
endfor
plot3( stable, mu_s, z_s, '-b','linewidth', 8);
hold on
plot3( unstable, mu_us, z_us, '-:r','linewidth', 8);
hold on
if (check_s2 == 1)
hold on
plot3( stable2, mu_s2, z_s2, '-b','linewidth', 8);
endif
if (check_us2 == 1)
hold on
plot3( unstable2, mu_us2, z_us2, '-:r','linewidth', 8);
endif

```

The differential equation in Eq. 236 is a Bernoulli's equation and can be solved analytically, as shown in what follows.

PROP. 9 (*Bernoulli's equation*). Let's consider the following ODE:

$$\text{Eq. 237} \quad \dot{\eta}(t) = a(t)\eta(t) + b(t)\eta^\alpha(t)$$

It can be transformed into the following linear differential equation of the first order

$$\text{Eq. 238} \quad \dot{z}(t) = a(t)z(t)(1 - \alpha) + b(t)(1 - \alpha)$$

with $z(t) = \eta^{1-\alpha}(t)$ and for $\eta(t) \neq 0$. The general integral is

$$\text{Eq. 239} \quad \eta^{1-\alpha}(t) = z(t) = e^{(1-\alpha)F(t)} \left[\eta^{1-\alpha}(t_0) + (1 - \alpha) \int_{t_0}^t (b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)F(s)}) ds \right]$$

where $F(t) = \int a(\tau)d\tau$.

Proof. By derivation of $z(t)$ with respect to t we have

$$\dot{z}(t) = (1 - \alpha) \frac{\dot{\eta}(t)}{\eta^\alpha(t)} \Rightarrow \dot{\eta}(t) = \frac{\dot{z}(t)\eta^\alpha(t)}{1 - \alpha}$$

We also have $z(t)\eta^\alpha(t) = \eta(t)$ and the ODE becomes

$$\frac{\dot{z}(t)\eta^\alpha(t)}{1 - \alpha} = a(t)z(t)\eta^\alpha(t) + b(t)\eta^\alpha(t)$$

It can be simplified into Eq. 238 when $\eta(t) \neq 0$. Let's consider now the homogeneous ODE associated to Eq. 238: we can solve it by separation of the variables. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}(t) = a(t)(1 - \alpha)z(t) &\Rightarrow \frac{dz}{z} = a(t)(1 - \alpha)dt \Rightarrow \ln|z| = (1 - \alpha) \int a(t)dt \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow z = \pm e^{(1-\alpha) \int a(\tau)d\tau} = \pm e^{(1-\alpha) [\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau + C]} \end{aligned}$$

Then we have that the general integral of $\dot{z}(t) = a(t)z(t)(1 - \alpha)$ is

$$\text{Eq. 240} \quad z(t) = C e^{(1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau}$$

As for the non-homogenous ODE, if we consider a solution with the structure $\zeta(t) = \psi(t)z(t)$ where $z(t)$ is one of the solutions of the homogeneous ODE, then we have $\dot{\zeta}(t) = \dot{\psi}(t)z(t) + \psi(t)\dot{z}(t)$. If we now substitute this in Eq. 238 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\psi}(t)z(t) + \psi(t)\dot{z}(t) &= a(t)\psi(t)z(t)(1 - \alpha) + b(t)(1 - \alpha) \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \dot{\psi}(t)z(t) + \psi(t)\dot{z}(t) &= a(t)\psi(t)z(t)(1 - \alpha) + b(t)(1 - \alpha) \end{aligned}$$

If we now consider, in particular, a solution such that $\psi(t_0) = 0$, we have that it exists a neighborhood of $(t = t_0, z = 0)$ where $\psi(t) = 0$. In this neighborhood we have

$$\dot{\psi}(t) = \frac{b(t)(1 - \alpha)}{z(t)} = \frac{b(t)(1 - \alpha)}{C e^{(1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau}} \Rightarrow \psi(t) = \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{C} \int \frac{b(t)}{e^{(1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau}} dt$$

If we consider, in particular, the case $C = 1$, we have $\psi(t) = (1 - \alpha) \int b(t) e^{-(1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} dt$, then a particular solution of Eq. 238 is

$$\text{Eq. 241} \quad \zeta(t) = e^{(1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} (1 - \alpha) \int_{t_0}^t b(s) e^{-(1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt$$

To verify this last proposition let's consider that by deriving $\zeta(t)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\dot{\zeta}(t)}{(1-\alpha)} &= (1-\alpha)a(t)e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt + \\ &+ e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} b(t)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} = \\ &= (1-\alpha)a(t)e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt + b(t) \end{aligned}$$

Now, by substitution of $\dot{\zeta}(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ in Eq. 238, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (1-\alpha)^2 a(t)e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt + (1-\alpha)b(t) &= \\ = (1-\alpha)^2 a(t)e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt + (1-\alpha)b(t) \end{aligned}$$

Then we can state that the general integral of Eq. 238 can be written

$$\begin{aligned} z(t) &= C e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} + \zeta(t) = C e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} + \\ &+ e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} (1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt = \\ &= e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} \left[C + (1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt \right] \end{aligned}$$

If we then consider that $C = z(t_0)$ (as it is easy to verify) and if we put $\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau = F(s)$, we have proven this proposition ■

We note now that the differential equation in Eq. 237 becomes Eq. 236 if we consider the following changes in Eq. 236: $\alpha \rightarrow 3$, $b(t) \rightarrow b$, $a(t) = a(\mu - \mu_c)$, $\eta(t) = (y - y_c)$. In other words:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\eta}(t) &= a(t)\eta(t) + b(t)\eta^\alpha(t) & \alpha &= 3 \\ & & b(t) &= b \\ & & \rightarrow & \\ a(t) &= a(\mu - \mu_c) & \dot{y}(t) &= a(\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) + b(y - y_c)^3 \\ \eta(t) &= (y - y_c) \end{aligned}$$

This means that the general integral of Eq. 236 can be obtained by performing the same substitutions in Eq. 239. We have

$$\begin{aligned} e^{(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^t a(\tau)d\tau} \left[C + (1-\alpha) \int_{t_0}^t b(s)e^{-(1-\alpha)\int_{t_0}^s a(\tau)d\tau} dt \right] \\ (y(t) - y_c)^{1-3} = e^{(1-3)F(t)} \left[(y(t_0) - y_c)^{1-3} + (1-3) \int_{t_0}^t (be^{-(1-3)F(s)}) ds \right] \end{aligned}$$

with $F(t) = \int_{t_0}^t a(\mu - \mu_c)d\tau = a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 (y(t) - y_c)^{-2} &= e^{-2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \left[(y(t_0) - y_c)^{-2} - 2b \int_{t_0}^t e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(s - t_0)} ds \right] = \\
 &= e^{-2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \left[(y(t_0) - y_c)^{-2} - \frac{2b}{2a(\mu - \mu_c)} \int_{t_0}^t e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(s - t_0)} d(2a(\mu - \mu_c)(s - t_0)) \right] = \\
 &= e^{-2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \left[(y(t_0) - y_c)^{-2} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} (e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) \right] \Rightarrow \\
 \text{Eq. 242} \quad &\begin{cases} y(t) = y_c + \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}}} \leftarrow y(t_0) > y_c \\ y(t) = y_c - \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}}} \leftarrow y(t_0) < y_c \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

The derivative is then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{y}(t) &= \pm \left[\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \left(-2ab(\mu - \mu_c) \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)}{2 \left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right] = \\
 &= \pm \left[\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} + \frac{be^{3a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right] = \\
 &= \pm \left[a(\mu - \mu_c) + \frac{be^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}} \right] \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \\
 &= \pm \left[\frac{\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - be^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} + b + be^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}} \right] \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \Rightarrow \\
 \text{Eq. 243} \quad &\dot{y}(t) = \pm \left[\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} + b \right] \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can verify now that that Eq. 242 is a solution of Eq. 236 by substituting $y(t)$ in it:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \pm \left[\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} + b \right] \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \\
& = a(\mu - \mu_c) \frac{\pm e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}}} + b \left(\frac{\pm e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}}} \right)^3 \Leftrightarrow \\
& \Leftrightarrow \left[\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} + b \right] \frac{1}{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}} = \\
& = a(\mu - \mu_c) + b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \frac{e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}} \Leftrightarrow \\
& \Leftrightarrow \frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} + b = \frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{(y(t_0) - y_c)^2} - b \left[e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1 \right] + b e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \Leftrightarrow \\
& \Leftrightarrow b = -b e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} + b + b e^{2a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \Leftrightarrow b - b = 0
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 44. Evolution in time of the solution of Eq. 236 towards its asymptotic value, for different values of μ and for two particular initial conditions and a set of parameters a, b .

Let's now see how the study of the solution can lead to what we saw in Table 3. For $\mu > \mu_c, a > 0, b < 0$ we have that the solution has the following asymptotic behavior:

$$y(t) = y_c \pm \frac{e^{a(\mu-\mu_c)(t-t_0)}}{e^{a(\mu-\mu_c)(t-t_0)}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{(y(t_0)-y_c)^2 e^{2a(\mu-\mu_c)(t-t_0)}} - b \frac{1 - \frac{1}{e^{2a(\mu-\mu_c)(t-t_0)}}}{a(\mu-\mu_c)}}}} \rightarrow y_c \pm \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}} (\mu_c - \mu)$$

So we get correctly two of the asymptotic equilibria for this case, but we don't get the third one: $y(t) = y_c$. Why? It is because in PROP. 9 we made the substitution $z(t) = \eta^{1-\alpha}(t)$ which implied $\eta(t) \neq 0$ or, in the present case, $y(t) \neq y_c$. So, the integral in Eq. 243 do not includes solutions that tends to y_c asymptotically and I don't know how to find these solutions, at present. In Figure 44 there is a family of solutions for a particular set of parameters a, b , for a particular initial condition and for several values of μ . As you can see, in this case the solution reach asymptotically states of stable equilibrium. This diagram was plotted by the following code.

CODE 25. This code plots a family of solutions and the bifurcation diagram for Eq. 236 (Figure 44).

```
% file name = Pitchfork_bifurcation_2
% date of creation = 27/05/2021
clear all
% parameters
mu_c = -2
y_c = 2
a = -1
b = -3
y_0 = 4
% calculating y'(y,mu)
n = 100;
if (a*b < 0 )
    mu (n) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
else
    mu (n) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
endif
y(1) = y_c-sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n)));
y(n)= y_c+sqrt((a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n)));
d_mu = (mu(n)-mu(1))/( n+1 )
d_y = (y(n)-y(1))/( n+1 )
for i=2:n
    mu(i) = mu(i-1) + d_mu;
endfor
for j=2:n
    y(j) = y(j-1) + d_y;
endfor
for i=1:1:n
    for j=1:1:n
        f(i,j) = ( a*mu(i) + b*(y(j)^2) - 2*b*y_c*y(j) + (b*y_c^2 - a*mu_c) )*( y(j) - y_c );
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
% calculating and plotting the solution of the ODE
delta_t = 0.001;
m = 10^3;
t(1) = 0.;
for i=2:1:m
    t(i) = t(i-1) + delta_t;
```

```

endfor
for i=1:1:n
    for k = 2:1:m
        expo = a*(mu(i) - mu_c)*t(k);
        e1 = e^expo;
        e2 = e^(2*expo);
        eta_0 = y_0 - y_c;
        sol(i,k) = y_c + ( e1/sqrt( (1/eta_0)^2 - ( b*(e2 - 1)/( a*(mu(i) - mu_c) ) ) ) );
        mu_sol(i,k) = mu(i);
        sol2(i,k) = y_c - ( e1/sqrt( (1/eta_0)^2 - ( b*(e2 - 1)/( a*(mu(i) - mu_c) ) ) ) );
    endforendfor
for i=1:5:n
    plot3( sol(i,2:50:m), mu_sol(i,2:50:m), t(2:50:m), '-k','linewidth', 3);
    hold on
endfor
% plotting of the states of equilibrium
k = 1;
h = 1;
p = 1;
q = 1;
check_s2 = 0;
check_us2 = 0;
for i=1:1:n
    for j =1:1:n-1
        if (y(j)<y_c+d_y)
            if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
                stable(k) = y(j);
                mu_s (k) = mu(i);
                z_s(k) = t(m);
                k = k+1;
            elseif ( sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)) )
                unstable(h) = y(j);
                mu_us (h) = mu(i);
                z_us(h) = t(m);
                h = h+1;
            endif
        endif
        if (y(j) > y_c+d_y)
            if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
                stable2(p) = y(j);
                mu_s2 (p) = mu(i);
                z_s2(p) = t(m);
                p = p+1;
                check_s2 = 1;
            elseif (sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)))
                unstable2(q) = y(j);
                mu_us2 (q) = mu(i);
                z_us2(q) = t(m);
                q = q+1;
                check_us2 = 1;
            endif
        endif
    endfor
endfor
plot3( stable, mu_s, z_s, '-b','linewidth', 6);
hold on
plot3( unstable, mu_us, z_us, '-r','linewidth', 6);

```

```

if (check_s2 == 1)
    hold on
    plot3( stable2, mu_s2, z_s2, '-b','linewidth', 6);
endif
if (check_us2 == 1)
    hold on
    plot3( unstable2, mu_us2, z_us2, '-r','linewidth', 6);
endif
grid on
xlabel('y');
ylabel('{\mu}');
zlabel('time');
mu_c_str = num2str(mu_c);
y_c_str = num2str(y_c);
a_str = num2str(a);
b_str = num2str(b);
y_0_str = num2str(y_0);
titolo = strjoin({'dy/dt = a(\mu-\mu_c)(y-y_c) + b(y-y_c)^3', '\mu_c = '...
, mu_c_str, '{y_c} = ', y_c_str, ', a = ', a_str, ', b = ', b_str, '{y_0} = ', y_0_str});
title (titolo)

```


Figure 45. Equilibria for the system in Eq. 244 for 4 different examples. In this case, a red line indicates unstable equilibrium, while a blue line indicates stable equilibrium.

6.1.5 Transcritical bifurcation

In PROP. 9 we have seen how the system that approximate the behaviour of Eq. 208 in a neighborhood of μ_c, y_c is a Bernoulli's equation with $\alpha = 3$. Now we will see how a system that can be approximated in μ_c, y_c by a Bernoulli's equation with $\alpha = 2$ does bifurcate. In this case we have the system

$$\text{Eq. 244} \quad y(\dot{t}) = a(\mu - \mu_c)[y(t) - y_c] + b[y(t) - y_c]^2$$

In this case we'll start from the ODE the system is reduced to, and then we'll find what the conditions are for Eq. 208 to be satisfied in order to be approximated to that ODE. Equilibria for this systems are described by the following curves:

$$\text{Eq. 245} \quad \begin{cases} y = y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c) \\ y = y_c \end{cases}$$

Their stability in the four possible cases can be studied easily (Table 4) and it is possible to plot them (Figure 45), for a particular set of parameters y_c, μ_c, a, b , by using the following code, that is similar to the one used for pitchfork bifurcation.

		$\mu < \mu_c$		$\mu > \mu_c$	
$ab < 0$	$a > 0$ $b < 0$	$y = y_c$	stable	$y = y_c$	unstable
		$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	unstable	$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	stable
	$a < 0$ $b > 0$	$y = y_c$	unstable	$y = y_c$	stable
		$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	stable	$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	unstable
$ab > 0$	$a > 0$ $b > 0$	$y = y_c$	stable	$y = y_c$	unstable
		$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	unstable	$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	stable
	$a < 0$ $b < 0$	$y = y_c$	unstable	$y = y_c$	stable
		$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	stable	$y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c)$	unstable

Table 4. The complete study of stability for the equilibria of the system in Eq. 208 when the hypotheses of PROP. 10 holds.

CODE 26. This code plots the diagram for the transcritical bifurcation like the ones in Figure 45.

```
% file name = transcritical_bifurcation_1
% date of creation = 06/06/2021
clear all
% parameters
mu_c = -2
y_c = 2
a = -2
b = -3
% plotting of the surface y'(y,mu)
```

```

n = 200;
if (a*b < 0 )
    mu (n) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
else
    mu (n) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
endif
y (1) = min ([y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(1)),y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n))]);
y(n)= max ([y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(1)),y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n))]);
d_mu = (mu(n)-mu(1))/( n+1 )
d_y = (y(n)-y(1))/( n+1 )
for i=2:n
    mu(i) = mu(i-1) + d_mu;
endfor
for j=2:n
    y(j) = y(j-1) + d_y;
endfor
for i=1:1:n
    for j=1:1:n
        f(i,j) = ( a*( mu(i) - mu_c ) + b*( y(j) - y_c ) )*( y(j) - y_c );
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
colormap ([0,0,0])
mesh(y(1:5:n), mu(1:5:n), f(1:5:n,1:5:n));
hold on
mesh(y(1:15:n), mu(1:15:n), plane_xy(1:15:n,1:15:n));
hold on
xlabel('y');
ylabel('{\mu}');
mu_c_str = num2str(mu_c);
y_c_str = num2str(y_c);
a_str = num2str(a);
b_str = num2str(b);
legenda = strjoin({'{\mu_c} = ',mu_c_str,',{y_c} = ',y_c_str,'a = ', a_str,'b = ', b_str } );
legend (legenda)
% plotting of the states of equilibrium
k = 1;
h = 1;
p = 1;
q = 1;
check_s2 = 0;
check_us2 = 0;
for i=1:1:n
    for j=1:1:n-1
        if (y(j)<y_c+d_y)
            if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
                stable(k) = y(j);
                mu_s (k) = mu(i);
                z_s(k) = 0.;
                k = k+1;
            elseif ( sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)) )
                unstable(h) = y(j);
                mu_us (h) = mu(i);
                z_us(h) = 0.;
                h = h+1;
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

endif
endif
if (y(j) > y_c+d_y)
if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
stable2(p) = y(j);
mu_s2 (p) = mu(i);
z_s2(p) = 0.;
p = p+1;
check_s2 = 1;
elseif (sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)))
unstable2(q) = y(j);
mu_us2 (q) = mu(i);
z_us2(q) = 0.;
q = q+1;
check_us2 = 1;
endif
endif
endfor
endfor
plot3( stable, mu_s, z_s, '-b','linewidth', 8);
hold on
plot3( unstable, mu_us, z_us, '-r','linewidth', 8);
hold on
if (check_s2 == 1)
hold on
plot3( stable2, mu_s2, z_s2, '-b','linewidth', 8);
endif
if (check_us2 == 1)
hold on
plot3( unstable2, mu_us2, z_us2, '-r','linewidth', 8);
endif
endif

```

Let's now find the conditions for the derivatives of $f(y(t), \mu)$ in (y_c, μ_c) such that this function can be approximated by the function $g(y(t), \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c)[y(t) - y_c] + b[y(t) - y_c]^2$ in a neighborhood of (y_c, μ_c) . The derivatives of the first and second order of $g(y(t), \mu)$ are:

$$\frac{\partial g(y, \mu)}{\partial y} = a(\mu - \mu_c) + 2b(y - y_c) \Rightarrow \frac{\partial g(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial g(y, \mu)}{\partial \mu} = a(y - y_c) \Rightarrow \frac{\partial g(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 g(y, \mu)}{\partial y \partial \mu} = \frac{\partial^2 g(y, \mu)}{\partial \mu \partial y} = a \neq 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 g(y, \mu)}{\partial \mu^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 g(y, \mu)}{\partial y^2} = 2b \neq 0$$

Let's now consider the expansion by Taylor series of f centered in (y_c, μ_c) :

$$\begin{aligned}
f(y, \mu) = & f(y_c, \mu_c) + \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} (\mu - \mu_c) + \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} (y - y_c) + \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 \mu} (\mu - \mu_c)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial^2 y} (y - y_c)^2 + 2 \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} (\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c) \right) + \dots
\end{aligned}$$

If we now consider the conditions $f(y_c, \mu_c) = 0$, $\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} = 0$, $\frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} = 0$, $\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y \partial \mu} = \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} = a$, $\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu^2} = 0$, $\frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y^2} = 2b$, then we have

$$f(y, \mu) = \frac{1}{2} (2b(y - y_c)^2 + 2a(\mu - \mu_c)(y - y_c)) + \sigma(\rho^2)$$

Then we conclude that we can study – in small enough neighborhood of (y_c, μ_c) – the system

$$\text{Eq. 246} \quad \frac{dy(t)}{dt} = f(y(t), \mu) = a(\mu - \mu_c)[y(t) - y_c] + b[y(t) - y_c]^2$$

instead of the one in Eq. 208. This proves the following proposition.

PROP. 10 (*transcritical bifurcation*). Let's consider Eq. 208. If we assume that

$$\text{Eq. 247} \quad f(y_c, \mu_c) = 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 248} \quad \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu} = 0$$

$$\text{Eq. 249} \quad \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y \partial \mu} = \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu \partial y} = a, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial \mu^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f(y_c, \mu_c)}{\partial y^2} = 2b$$

then we have that it exists a neighborhood of μ_c in \mathbb{R} such that Table 4 holds.

Also in this case, as in the previous two ones, we can integrate analytically the ODE. Since it is a Bernoulli's equation we can use PROP. 9 and we find that its general integral is

$$(y(t) - y_c)^{-1} = e^{-F(t)} \left[(y(t_0) - y_c)^{-1} - \int_{t_0}^t (be^{F(s)}) ds \right]$$

where $F(t) = \int a(\mu - \mu_c) d\tau = a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)$ and where we have considered the substitutions $\alpha \rightarrow 3$, $b(t) \rightarrow b$, $a(t) \rightarrow a(\mu - \mu_c)$, $\eta(t) \rightarrow (y - y_c)$ in Eq. 239. So, we have found the solutions

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= y_c + \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - b \int_{t_0}^t e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(s - t_0)} ds} = \\ &= y_c + \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} \int_{t_0}^t e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(s - t_0)} d[a(\mu - \mu_c)(s - t_0)]} \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 250} \quad y(t) = y_c + \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} (e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1)}$$

What is the limit of this solution for $t \rightarrow \infty$? We have

$$y(t) = y_c + \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} (1 - e^{-a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 251} \quad y(t) \rightarrow \begin{cases} y_c - \frac{a}{b}(\mu - \mu_c) & \text{for } a(\mu - \mu_c) > 0 \\ y_c & \text{for } a(\mu - \mu_c) < 0 \end{cases}$$

Figure 46. Evolution in time of the solution of Eq. 244 towards its asymptotic value, for different values of μ and for a particular initial condition and a particular set of parameters a, b .

What about the derivative?

$$\dot{y}(t) = \frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1)} - \frac{e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \left(-\frac{ab(\mu - \mu_c)}{a(\mu - \mu_c)} e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) \right)^2} =$$

$$= e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \frac{a(\mu - \mu_c) \left(\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) \right) + be^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) \right)^2} =$$

$$= e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} \frac{\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{y(t_0) - y_c} - b(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) + be^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) \right)^2} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 252} \quad \dot{y}(t) = \frac{\left(\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{y(t_0) - y_c} + b \right) e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{1}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(e^{a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)} - 1) \right)^2} = \frac{\left(\frac{a(\mu - \mu_c)}{y(t_0) - y_c} + b \right) e^{-a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{\left(\frac{e^{-a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}}{y(t_0) - y_c} - \frac{b}{a(\mu - \mu_c)}(1 - e^{-a(\mu - \mu_c)(t - t_0)}) \right)^2}$$

As for the limit of the derivative, we have

$$\text{Eq. 253} \quad \dot{y}(t) \rightarrow \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } a(\mu - \mu_c) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } a(\mu - \mu_c) < 0 \end{cases}$$

as we expected. In Figure 46 the evolution in time of Eq. 250 for $a = -1, b = -3, y_0 = 5, \mu_c = -2, y_c = 2$. It has been plotted by the following code.

CODE 27. This code plots the evolution in time of the solution of Eq. 250 towards its asymptotic value (Figure 46).

```
% file name = transcritical_bifurcation_2
% date of creation = 06/06/2021
clear all
% parameters
mu_c = -2
y_c = 2
a = -1
b = -3
y_0 = 5
% calculating y'(y,mu)
n = 100;
if (a*b < 0 )
    mu (n) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
else
    mu (n) = mu_c - 3*abs(mu_c);
    mu (1) = mu_c + 3*abs(mu_c);
endif
y (1) = min ([y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(1)),y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n))]);
y(n)= max ([y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(1)),y_c-(a/b)*(mu_c-mu(n))]);
d_mu = (mu(n)-mu(1))/( n+1 )
d_y = (y(n)-y(1))/( n+1 )
for i=2:n
    mu(i) = mu(i-1) + d_mu;
endfor
for j=2:n
    y(j) = y(j-1) + d_y;
endfor
for i=1:1:n
    for j =1:1:n
        f(i,j) = ( a*( mu(i) - mu_c ) + b*( y(j) - y_c ) )*( y(j) - y_c );
        plane_xy (i,j) = 0;
    endfor
endfor
% calculating and plotting the solution of the ODE
delta_t = 0.001;
m = 10^3;
t(1) = 0.;
for i=2:1:m
    t(i) = t(i-1) + delta_t;
endfor
for i=1:1:n
    sol(i,1) = y_0;
    for k = 2:1:m
        expo = a*(mu(i) - mu_c)*t(k);
```

```

e1 = e^expo;
eta_0 = y_0 - y_c;
sol(i,k) = y_c + ( e1/( (1/eta_0) - ( b*(e1 - 1)/( a*(mu(i) - mu_c) ) ) ) );
mu_sol(i,k) = mu(i);
endfor
endfor
for i=1:5:n
    plot3( sol(i,10:50:m), mu_sol(i,10:50:m), t(10:50:m), '-k','linewidth', 3);
    hold on
endfor
% plotting of the states of equilibrium
k = 1;
h = 1;
p = 1;
q = 1;
check_s2 = 0;
check_us2 = 0;
for i=1:1:n
    for j =1:1:n-1
        if (y(j)<y_c+d_y)
            if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
                stable(k) = y(j);
                mu_s (k) = mu(i);
                z_s(k) = t(m);
                k = k+1;
            elseif ( sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)) )
                unstable(h) = y(j);
                mu_us (h) = mu(i);
                z_us(h) = t(m);
                h = h+1;
            endif
        endif
        if (y(j) > y_c+d_y)
            if ( sign(f(i,j+1))<sign(f(i,j)) )
                stable2(p) = y(j);
                mu_s2 (p) = mu(i);
                z_s2(p) = t(m);
                p = p+1;
                check_s2 = 1;
            elseif (sign(f(i,j+1))>sign(f(i,j)))
                unstable2(q) = y(j);
                mu_us2 (q) = mu(i);
                z_us2(q) = t(m);
                q = q+1;
                check_us2 = 1;
            endif
        endif
    endfor
endfor
plot3( stable, mu_s, z_s, '-b','linewidth', 6);
hold on
plot3( unstable, mu_us, z_us, '-r','linewidth', 6);
if (check_s2 == 1)
    hold on
    plot3( stable2, mu_s2, z_s2, '-b','linewidth', 6);
endif
if (check_us2 == 1)

```

```

hold on
plot3( unstable2, mu_us2, z_us2, '-r','linewidth', 6);
endif
grid on
xlabel('y');
ylabel('{\mu}');
zlabel('time');
mu_c_str = num2str(mu_c);
y_c_str = num2str(y_c);
a_str = num2str(a);
b_str = num2str(b);
y_0_str = num2str(y_0);
titolo = strjoin({'dy/dt = a(\mu-\mu_c)(y-y_c) + b(y-y_c)^2', '{\mu_c} = '...
, mu_c_str, '{y_c} = ', y_c_str, ' a = ', a_str, ' b = ', b_str, '{y_0} = ', y_0_str );
title (titolo)

```

6.2 Bifurcation in two dimensions

In this section we are going to study systems of two ODEs of the first order:

$$\text{Eq. 254} \quad \frac{dx(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{f}(x(t), \mu) \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \dot{x}_1(t) = f_1(x_1(t), x_2(t), \mu) \\ \dot{x}_2(t) = f_2(x_1(t), x_2(t), \mu) \end{cases}$$

In particular, we will see how to study the behaviour of their equilibria, as the bifurcation parameter μ changes within an interval. We assume that this system of two ODEs satisfies the hypotheses of PROP. 2. Let's start with an example: consider the system

$$\text{Eq. 255} \quad \begin{cases} \dot{\rho}(t) = \rho(t)(\Delta\mu - \rho^2(t)) \\ \dot{\theta}(t) = -1 \end{cases}$$

which has been written in polar coordinates. We have considered that $\Delta\mu = \mu - \mu_c$. It can also be translated into the coordinates x, y :

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{cases} x(t) = \rho(t) \cos \theta(t) \\ y(t) = \rho(t) \sin \theta(t) \end{cases} &\Rightarrow \begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = \dot{\rho}(t) \cos \theta(t) - \rho(t) \dot{\theta}(t) \sin \theta(t) \\ \dot{y}(t) = \dot{\rho}(t) \sin \theta(t) + \rho(t) \dot{\theta}(t) \cos \theta(t) \end{cases} \\ \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = \rho(t)(\Delta\mu - \rho^2(t)) \cos \theta(t) - \rho(t) \dot{\theta}(t) \sin \theta(t) \\ \dot{y}(t) = \rho(t)(\Delta\mu - \rho^2(t)) \sin \theta(t) + \rho(t) \dot{\theta}(t) \cos \theta(t) \end{cases} &\Rightarrow \begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = (\Delta\mu - \rho^2(t))x(t) + y(t) \\ \dot{y}(t) = (\Delta\mu - \rho^2(t))y(t) - x(t) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Consider now that $x^2(t) + y^2(t) = \rho^2(t)$, then we have the system

$$\text{Eq. 256} \quad \begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = (\Delta\mu - x^2(t) - y^2(t))x(t) + y(t) \\ \dot{y}(t) = (\Delta\mu - x^2(t) - y^2(t))y(t) - x(t) \end{cases}$$

Equilibria in this case are those states in which the gradient of the vectorial field $\mathbf{f}(x(t), y(t))$ is zero:

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\Delta\mu - x^2(t) - y^2(t))x(t) + y(t) \\ (\Delta\mu - x^2(t) - y^2(t))y(t) - x(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

PROP. 11 (*Wilhelm's system*). If we consider a chemical reaction that contains only monomolecular and bimolecular reactions (reversible reactions are considered as two reactions) and that fits the following criteria (in decreasing order of importance):

1. it has the minimal number of reactants;
2. it has the minimal number of reactions;
3. it has the minimal number of terms in the system of differential equations;

then we find that the only possible chemical system that has bistability is the following one:

Proof. For the rate of $[X]$ we have

$$\frac{d[X]}{dt} = 2k_1[S][Y] + k_2[X]^2 - 2k_2[X]^2 - k_3[X][Y] - k_4[X] \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 258} \quad \frac{d[X]}{dt} = 2k_1[S][Y] - k_2[X]^2 - k_3[X][Y] - k_4[X]$$

For the rate of $[Y]$ we have

$$\frac{d[Y]}{dt} = -k_1[S][Y] + k_2[X]^2 + k_3[X][Y] - k_3[X][Y] \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 259} \quad \frac{d[Y]}{dt} = -k_1[S][Y] + k_2[X]^2$$

Similarly we find the rates for $[P]$, $[S]$ and in conclusion we have

$$\text{Eq. 260} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d[S]}{dt} = -k_1[S][Y] \\ \frac{d[X]}{dt} = 2k_1[S][Y] - k_2[X]^2 - k_3[X][Y] - k_4[X] \\ \frac{d[Y]}{dt} = -k_1[S][Y] + k_2[X]^2 \\ \frac{d[P]}{dt} = k_4[X] \end{array} \right.$$

7 Flux balance analysis

7.1 Introduction

DEF. 28. Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) is a mathematical method for modeling a large number of enzymatic reactions linked one to the other. Let's say we have a total of n reactions that involve m metabolites in total. Then FBA associates to this metabolic network the matrix

$$\text{Eq. 261} \quad \Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} & \dots & s_{1n} \\ s_{21} & s_{22} & \dots & s_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ s_{m1} & s_{m2} & \dots & s_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$$

where s_{ij} is the stoichiometric coefficient for the i^{th} compound of the j^{th} reaction: it is positive if the respective metabolite is produced, it is negative if it is consumed. If we have $s_{ij} = 0$ it means that the i^{th} metabolites does not participate in reaction j . This matrix is called *stoichiometric matrix*. Each column of S represents a reaction, each line is associated to a metabolite of the metabolic network.

Now, let's consider Wilhelm's system (Eq. 257), as a first application. We have four reactions ($n = 4$) and the four metabolites S, Y, X, P ($m = 4$). Then, the stoichiometric matrix is

$$\text{Eq. 262} \quad \Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} S \\ Y \\ X \\ P \end{matrix}$$

$r_1 \quad r_2 \quad r_3 \quad r_4$

where r_j is the j^{th} reaction. If

8 References

For the first chapter I relied mainly on (1) and (2), and I used (3) for the paragraph on nuclear decay.

Kinetic parameters for IDO-1 and IDO-2 are taken from (4). In the case of the parameters of IDO-1 of par. 3.4.4.1, they are from (5) (figure 3). K_M^{TECS} for LAT1 comes from (6). Kinetic parameters for TDO-2 are from (7).

For the section on Cauchy problem, I have used (8). Numerical methods are from (9). For the analytical solution of the Michaelis-Menten equation relative to the irreversible enzymatic reaction, I have followed (10), and according to his suggestion, the approximation for Lambert function is the one proposed in (11).

The chapter about inhibition took inspiration from (12) and (13). For substrate inhibition of IDO-1, I considered the model proposed in (14).

For bifurcation in one dimension I have used (15) with the examples from (16).

Definition of bistability is taken from (5). The smallest bistable chemical reaction is the one proposed in (17).

The general structure of these notes follows (12) and (18). As a reference for Octave/MATLAB syntax I have used (19) as well as (20).

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